

PREFACE – GRIP PROJECT

Within the context of the *Digital and Sustainable Northwest* (NODES) programme, financed by the Italian *National Recovery and Resilience Plan* (PNRR), *Green processes for Industrial Productions and cost-effective effluents valorisation* (GRIP) represents the flagship project of *Green technologies and sustainable industries* SPOKE 2.

GRIP addresses contemporary environmental issues by fostering Circular Economy (CE) and Industrial Symbiosis (IS) practices within the territory of Piedmont, Valle d'Aosta and the bordering provinces of Lombardy (Pavia, Como, and Varese). Through the collaboration among academic institutions and the support of a wide network of industrial and technological partners, GRIP aims at promoting the adoption of sustainable production models based on innovative valorisation technologies and platforms for residues. Particularly, the primary objective of the project is to bolster the local economy by implementing integrated and multidisciplinary solutions which minimise waste disposal and facilitate value recovery from industrial and agricultural residues and effluents. A wide range of techniques and applications are thus being investigated, spanning from biotransformation processes to convert organic residue into high-value products, to new recycling technologies for inorganic residue. From a sectoral perspective, analysed residues mainly encompass productive and post-industrial wastes from mining, construction, energy, agrifood, textile, and plastic supply chains.

GRIP is articulated into eight research modules (RMs), which collectively contribute to achieve the goal of establishing innovative transformation platforms applicable both to upstream and downstream industrial processes. Six RMs encompass process engineering studies, since they are dedicated to the development of innovative conversion techniques for specific residue streams. The remaining two RMs attempt instead to integrate and implement such results by adopting a systematic approach, considering the involvement of public entities in value creation (RM8) and combining the different transformation platform through the strategy of IS (RM6). Table 1 illustrates the respective areas of expertise of each RM.

Table 1. RMs areas of expertise

RM	Research Area
1	Mining and Construction
2	Agrifood
3	Plastic and Textile
4	Wastewater
5	CO ₂ Capture and Recovery
6	Industrial symbiosis
7	Agrifood
8	Urban Waste Management

Therefore, the nature of GRIP is twofold: the development of transformation technologies on the one hand, and the implementation of evaluation methods and digital tools on the other. Both dimensions collectively contribute to foster and broaden IS application. Combining theoretical and laboratory research, indeed, facilitates the effective industrial application of the resulting findings within the NODES territory. This feature is of great importance as it fills the gap highlighted by Sommer (2020) which has identified two separate clusters of IS projects: those focusing on process engineering and those developing theoretical instruments to promote IS. Even if both typologies are important in addressing

IS implementation, the lack of an integrated design negatively affects the overall applicability of the results among businesses. GRIP aims at solving this gap especially through the work of RM6.

RM6 FRAMEWORK SYSTEM

RM6 “*Framework System*” looks at the Circular Economy (CE) and, in particular, Industrial Symbiosis (IS) as a means of implementing the technological innovations developed by the other RMs in an integrated form. IS is a strategy for optimising waste management, and the overall industrial operations, through inter-industry collaboration, with the goal of reintegrating production residues into other production cycles. RM6 employs a multidimensional and systemic approach to assess the potential applications of the GRIP valorisation technologies at the territorial level. Therefore, it investigates the key regulatory, economic, environmental, and social aspects influencing the implementation of such innovation platforms. Such multidisciplinary nature of the RM6 is reflected in its structure, as it is composed of six research tasks, each of which is dedicated to a specific aspect of IS. The tasks are briefly outlined below:

- 6.1 *Regulation policy driving circular economy (at EU, national and local level).*
This line of research focuses on the normative and policy context related to CE and IS activities. The aim consists of exploring applicative solutions within the existing policy and regulatory framework.
- 6.2 *Enabling positive cultural change in organizations and communities to improve the acceptability of technological innovations for sustainability.*
increasing the effectiveness of circularity for business and jobs creation and just transition.
- 6.3 *Minimum environmental criteria for the Green Public Procurement.*
to support public administration in the joint development of legislative developments enabling the concrete application of the circular economy.
- 6.4 *Mapping the state of the art for Industrial symbiosis.*
to provide to the Companies proof of concepts for circular economy pathways and industrial symbiosis feasible routes.
- 6.5 *Creation of an interactive e-portal and best practices.*
exploring applicative solutions in the existing policy and regulatory framework.
- 6.6 *Life Cycle Assessments*
providing the best framework for assessing the potential environmental impacts of the developed products.

To verify the applicability of IS within the NODES territory, RM6 developed an operative model based on 1) mapping local businesses operating in GRIP productive sector, both as producer and utiliser of residue; 2) identifying legal requirement for residue, especially regarding the different paths involved by-product, waste and End-of-waste; 3) evaluating application feasibility and convenience through either TRL, Cost-benefit analysis, and LCA; 4) assessing social acceptance, and 5) defining awarding criteria for CAM. Final results will be summarised in an open-platform, to favour knowledge transfer and ease decision-making of both businesses and public administration. Figure 1 provides a synthesis of the structure of RM6’s research activity.

Figure 1. RM6 structure.

INTRODUCTION TO TASK 6.4 AND AIMS OF THE REPORT

Within RM6, the task 6.4 conducted a preliminary analysis of the state of the art of IS practices to capitalise on the results of previous experiences, highlighting both the factors that have contributed to success and those that have led to failure. The main objective of this line of research is to uncover potential IS within the NODES territory, looking at the potential implementation of GRIP transformation technologies among the local productive fabric. Therefore, the aim of task 6.4 is twofold: on one hand, it maps the state of the art of IS practices, starting from international experiences and then focusing on Italian ones; on the other hand, it maps potential IS activable at the regional scale by anchoring the new innovative platforms developed by RM1-7 to the territory. Regarding to the first phase, the emphasis is particularly placed on identifying the most frequent exchanges of by-products, waste, and End-of-Waste and, therefore, the production sectors of origin and destination of the abovementioned residues.

The work of RM6.4 is articulated into eight sections, as showed in Figure 2. The first phase concerns (i) the definition of the research object, which involved identifying the operative definition of IS, and, therefore, eligible actors, residues, and related transformation actions encompassed by the practice. It follows, in chronological order, (ii) a preliminary data collection on existing virtuous cases, encompassing the map of Eco-Industrial Parks, Regional IS, and Digital Platform promoting symbiotic exchanges, at both international and European levels. (iii) The identification of NACE-ATECO codes of original and destination sectors, and (iv) of CER codes of the residues involved by the transformation technologies developed by others RMs, lead to (v) the creation of a database reporting IS virtuous cases with respect to GRIP supply chains. Furthermore, this activity allows for (vi) the research and identification of potential production realities which can be involved in the project, putting the base to the mapping of potential IS within the NODES territory. Such territorial analysis is conducted through a Chamber of Commerce (CCIA) survey. To ascertain the viability of implementing the abovementioned conversion platforms, particularly in relation the transition from waste to End-of-Waste status, (vii) a comprehensive

search of the RECER register, which contains all EoW permits, was undertaken. Matching the obtained data allows to achieve (viii) a potential map of local producers and users.

Figure 2. Flowchart Task 6.4.

The research of task 6.4 is based on bibliographic sources, public administration data (CCIA and RECER registers), and on the results obtained at by the other RMs. In this regard, given the cross-sectional nature of RM6, the objectives of each phase are redefined from time to time on the basis of the results achieved by RM1-7: the system boundaries are progressively narrowed, e.g. residue, productive sector of origin and destination, and local production realities to be targeted.

The present report aims at summarising the work carried out by task 6.4, highlighting success cases, failure cases, difficulties encountered, technological and non-technological barriers, and benchmarks in order to identify those areas most in need of intervention. Based on the analysis of virtuous practices of IS, this report aims to illustrate how the technological platforms developed within GRIP can be implemented in the NODES area. In particular, the economic-environmental feasibility analysis makes use of the precise knowledge of legal and economic barriers.

STRUCTURE OF THIS REPORT

The present document aims at providing useful insights on the existing Industrial Symbiosis experiences. Therefore, it represents the first part of the RM6.4 research activity. The report is structured in three main parts. The first part introduces the concept of industrial symbiosis, providing in-depth information on its theoretical roots and framework. Therefore, it deepens Industrial Ecology and Circular Economy. The second part consists provides definitions and relevant information on the concepts of interest: Industrial Symbiosis, Eco-Industrial Parks, Byproducts, Waste, End-of-Waste, etc. It follows the mapping of existing Industrial Symbiosis which mainly consists of the analysis of EIPs, with a particular focus on residues exchanged and productive sectors involved, and the analysis of digital platform promoting symbiotic exchanges.

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INTRODUCTION TO THE CONCEPT: RELEVANCE AND THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK OF INDUSTRIAL SYMBIOSIS

Sustainable Development (SD) is the main challenge of our time, requiring that actual society meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet theirs. The intrinsic claim is to prevent environmental degradation, natural resources exhaustion and climate change. Prevalent solutions for this panier of problems have historically been founded on command-and-control tools, such as top-down legislation, and market-based instrument, such as taxes and incentives or the creation of new markets (i.e., cap and trade). Furthermore, especially in recent years, there has been a notable proliferation of voluntary initiatives, like environmental management systems, sustainability reports, sectoral conventions and framework agreements.

Within this context, Industrial Symbiosis (IS), a business-focused collaborative approach oriented towards resource efficiency which has been theorised and investigated over the last 30 years (Cecchin et al., 2020), is widely recognised as a strategic instrument to address SD, especially with regard to cleaner production systems (Cecchin et al., 2020; Henriques et al., 2022; Schroeder et al., 2019). Even if IS has emerged as a self-organising business strategy (Costa et al., 2010) driven by economic advantages and policy requirements (Mirata and Emtairah, 2005a), and therefore it might be conceived as a voluntary initiative, recent years have seen an increase in top-down initiatives and government economic incentives, making difficult to frame IS against the aforementioned solutions. IS could be therefore conceived as either top-down, market-based, or voluntary instruments (Artola et al., 2018) to tackle SD. The potential of IS in promoting SD is evident particularly in terms of promoting resource efficiency for industry, which has been argued to generate cost savings, with increased competitiveness and consequent potential for social benefits, which are primarily envisaged as job creation (Cecchin et al., 2020; Henriques et al., 2022; Mirata and Emtairah, 2005a).

The first systematic analysis of IS was submitted by Chertow in 2000 (Chertow, 2000), which conceived IS as an operative tool of Industrial Ecology (IE). IE emerged to contrast end-of-pipe solutions to the environmental crisis (Saavedra et al., 2018). Drawing on a metaphor with ecosystems, IE asserts that industrial systems should emulate the best features of biological ecosystems cycle, thereby optimising energy and materials consumption, minimising waste generation, and utilising effluents of one process as raw material for another (Frosch and Gallopoulos, 1989). Within this context, Chertow (2000) conceptualised IS as a strategy for implementing IE principles at the inter-firm level (Figure 3), defining it as a “concentration of place-based exchanges among different entities” consisting in material and energy flows. Focusing on closing pre-consumer loops by capturing the residue from one entity as the input for another, IS therefore clearly refers to IE (Cecchin et al., 2020).

Figure 3. Chertow's representation of IE scales of application (Chertow, 2000).

However, over the last ten years IS has been conceptualised as a subfield of a new paradigm, the Circular Economy (CE) (Cecchin et al., 2020; Le Tellier et al., 2019), which proposes a radical shift from the dominant linear model (take-make-use-dispose) to a cyclical and restorative model (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2013). CE is an umbrella concept (Kirchherr et al., 2017; Reike et al., 2018) that encompasses several previously theorised concepts, including IE, cradle-to-cradle, regenerative design, cleaner production, the ecological economy, the performance economy, and zero-waste management (Reike et al., 2018). It has gained the favour of both the academic and government circles, as evidenced by the enactment of legislation, particularly in China and Europe, that facilitates CE implementation. With respect to IS theoretical frameworks, Le Tellier et al. (2019) has been the first to introduce the CE concept therein. IS is defined by the authors as the approach to IE that applies industrial ecosystems in a restricted geographic area (Le Tellier et al., 2019). Similarly, IE is regarded as a subset of CE. The latter has indeed a wider focus and for this reason CE may be capable of scaling up IE principles to encompass the entire economic system, and not merely the industrial ones (Ghisellini et al., 2016; Le Tellier et al., 2019; Saavedra et al., 2018).

Figure 4. Positioning IS with respect to IE, CE, and SD (Le Tellier et al., 2019).

Nowadays, there is a universal agreement among the academic community to consider IS as the principal operative tool of CE at the meso-level (Ghisellini et al., 2016). Within the literature of CE, the micro level is indeed associated to products, companies, consumers, the meso-level mainly encompass eco-industrial parks, industrial cluster and district, whilst the macro level coincides with city, region, nation and beyond (Kirchherr et al., 2017).

The contribution of CE to SD has been investigated in depth, often taking as a metric the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (Berg et al., 2018; Cecchin et al., 2020; Rodriguez-Anton et al., 2019; Schroeder et al., 2019). Just recently, scholars have started to analyse the relevance of IS for the achievement of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). As observed by Henriques et al. (2022), despite IS mainly covers economic and environmental pillars of SD, the extended implementation of this business model (Implementation across industrial sectors at the national or regional level), has a considerable degree of relevance for a significant numbers of SDGs, and indirectly contributes to the achievement of various targets. Within the academic community there is a universal agreement with regard to the contribution of IS towards **SDG 6** *Ensure availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation for all*, particularly 6.3 (improve water quality by reducing pollution), **SDG 9** *Build resilient infrastructure, promote inclusive and sustainable industrialisation and foster innovation*, especially 9.4 (upgrade infrastructure and retrofit industries to make them sustainable, with increased resource-use efficiency and greater adoption of clean and environmentally sound technologies and industrial processes), and **SDG 12** *Responsible consumption and production* (Cecchin et al., 2020; Henriques et al., 2022; Schroeder et al., 2019). Furthermore, SDG 3 *Ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages*, and SDG 8 *Promote sustained, inclusive and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment and decent work for all* should be considered according to Schroeder et al. (2019); whilst, Cecchin et al. (2020) further adds SDG 2 *End hunger, achieve food security and improved nutrition and promote sustainable agriculture*, and SDG 7 *Ensure access to affordable, reliable, sustainable and modern energy for all*.

In conclusion, it is widely demonstrated the relevance of IS in tackling the contemporary environmental crisis. IS offers a systemic perspective on the ecological problem, aligning with the principles of IE and CE while addressing the unmet objectives of SD. Consequently, IS can be regarded as a pivotal operational strategy in this context. Given this relevance, this report will discuss the benefits, the criticism and the barriers of IS implementation at the regional scale.

POLICY CONTEXT

The United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) is a key proponent of global sustainable consumption and production policies. In 2002, the UN World Summit on Sustainable Development, held in Johannesburg, recommended the development and promotion of a 10-year framework of regional and national initiatives in this realm, which have been overseen by UNEP and UNDESA (United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs). Those programmes aimed at improving eco-efficiency through production chains and were often oriented to IS applications (Lehtoranta et al., 2011).

In Europe, policies have focused on reducing the environmental impact of products, rather than focusing on productive processes optimisation (Lehtoranta et al., 2011). In 2008, the European Commission (EC) introduced the Sustainable Consumption and Production and Sustainable Industrial Policy Action Plan (European Commission, 2008). In 2015, the first European Circular Economy Action Plan was presented. The Plan already acknowledged the significance of advancing innovative industrial processes, without explicitly referring to IS. The Commission proposed a comprehensive revision of waste legislation, with a particular focus on clarifying the rules on byproducts. This vision was reiterated in 2018, and later in 2020. In 2018 the European Commission indeed presented its strategic long-term vision for 2050 in “*A Clean Planet for all– A European strategic long-term vision for a prosperous, modern, competitive and climate neutral economy*”, which was then formalised in the 2020 European Green Deal. The aim of this long-term strategy is to present a vision that can lead to achieving net-zero greenhouse gas emissions by 2050 through a socially-fair transition in a cost-efficient manner (Sommer, 2020). The plan sets strategic goals and targets with respect to CO₂ and other greenhouse gas emissions reduction and waste generation prevention, therefore fostering circularity and strengthen IS (Sommer, 2020).

Under the EU Green Deal, the EU has released its new Circular Economy Action Plan, which replaces the previous CE plan of 2015. The plan explicitly refers to IS as a mean of transforming consumption and production patterns for promoting circularity within industrial supply chains and aims at creating a certification system to foster IS implementations.

Furthermore, in response to the crisis triggered by the COVID 19 pandemic, the European Union has introduced a financial recovery instrument, the Next Generation EU (NGEU), which encompasses grants and loans to tackle the economic downturn whilst pursuing a growth path that is sustainable in all respects. For instance, NGEU funded the Italian National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR), which outlines objectives, reforms and investments to be implemented within the national territory. Among those, PNRR funded the *Digital and Sustainable North West* (NODES) project, of which this report represent one of the outputs.

At the Italian level, in addition to the transposition of the previously mentioned directives, it is possible to mention some specific measures aimed at ensuring the development of IS. Of particular importance is Legislative Decree No. 112/1998, Article 26 (*Bassanini Law*), which introduces the Ecologically Equipped Production Areas (APEAs), which are conceived as innovative productive area developed and managed as a real estate development enterprise that seeks high environmental, economic, and social benefits as well as business excellence (Gallo and Gianfrate, 2011). The implementation of IS in these areas is not expressly required by the National regulation, which merely outlines the overarching

objectives to be addressed (i.e., energy saving, cogeneration from biomass and district heating, wastewater and rainwater recovery, waste management as separate collection). However, the specific regulation of APEA is devolved to the Regions, thereby allowing for a more targeted approach to the promotion of industrial symbiosis practices. To date there are 10 regions, which have already legislated on APEAs, among those, the APEAs Guidelines enacted by the Lazio Region include, among other requirements, the use of industrial symbiosis between the member companies (Iacondini et al., 2014).

Another pillar which testifies the growing attention toward IS at the national level is represented by the framework and strategic positioning document "*Towards a circular economy model for Italy*", jointly prepared by the Ministries of the Environment and Economic Development in 2017. The document highlighted the importance of IS as a systemic eco-innovation tool, thanks to the creation of networks for sharing resources and information. The need for an organic and systematic portfolio of economic instruments to support companies along the path of IS was also stressed. In this sense, the PNRR, provides for the reform of the existing circular economy strategy, including concrete measures to support the IS project through appropriate regulatory and financial instruments (Gobetti et al., 2021).

Furthermore, it is pertinent to cite the DPR 120/2017 aimed at promoting the formulation of regional guidelines for the recognition of byproduct status. The lack of a clear distinction between byproduct and waste in fact hinders the spread of IS practices. In this regard, several Regions have already enacted legislation, in particular, Emilia Romagna, Lombardy, Piedmont, and Tuscany.

DEFINITION OF THE CONCEPTS OF INTEREST

This section is intended to offer a comprehensive examination of the concepts that are the subject of this study, providing a clear and precise definitions for them in accordance with the EU and Italian legal context. The necessity for precise operational definitions is a consequence of the extensive treatment of IS in academic literature, which has resulted in a growing number of proposed definitions that are not always consistent and tend to overlap with related concepts, as IE and EIPs (Li, 2018). The aim is to provide a useful interpretation key for mapping IS in national and international contexts, which is extensive enough to be used in a variety of real cases and contexts and consistent with the legal regional background, since the GRIP project, in which the mapping process is rooted, needs to be applied at the regional level (NODES territory).

MAIN FEATURES OF INDUSTRIAL SYMBIOSIS

Following the study of Alfred Marshall on industrial districts (Desrochers, 2004, 2001; Gregson et al., 2012), who emphasised the role of productive residues new allocation within the economic industrial development path¹, IS-related practices have been dated back to the 19th century, when the exchange of byproducts was a common occurrence, especially between the chemical and textile industries (Gregson et al., 2012). This was driven by competitive pressure and the advent of new technologies (Desrochers, 2004). Despite byproducts reuse among different industries was widespread at this time, it was not oriented towards cleaner production or environmental sustainability; rather it was conceived just in terms of a productive optimisation strategy aimed at reducing waste treatment and disposal costs, gaining access to cheaper materials and energy, and generating income from production residues (Desrochers, 2004; Gregson et al., 2012).

The theorisation of IS as a business model to combine economic and environmental sustainability pertains indeed to the last 30 years, and it was driven especially by the success case of Kalundborg. The first academic definition of IS was proposed by Ehrenfeld and Gertler (1997), and since then the literature on IS experienced the emergence of a plethora of interpretations and approaches to the topic.

Li (2018) reviews the most cited definitions of IS (i.e., Chertow, 2000; Despeisse et al., 2012; Ehrenfeld, 1997; Heeres et al., 2004; Lombardi and Laybourn, 2012; Lowe and Evans, 1995; Mirata, 2004; Park et al., 2016; Tian et al., 2012; Tibbs, 1992; Valentine, 2016) highlighting their commonalities and divergences. Differences depend on the context of research, i.e., geographical, political, and economic outlying conditions, and its scope, e.g., providing policy suggestions or describing existing projects. Often these definitions are not consistent (Henriques et al., 2021; Li, 2018). For instance, some definitions set conditions for IS applications, such as geographic proximity and the involvement of diverse industries (Boix et al., 2015; Chertow, 2000), that are considered unnecessary according to other authors (Branson, 2016; Jensen et al., 2011; Lombardi and Laybourn, 2012).

The proliferation of contributions on IS has therefore resulted in a certain lack of clarity, blurring the boundaries of the concept. The attempts made by the EU Commission on Standardisation (2018) resulted therefore in a definition with a broad range of applicability, which is deemed to be overly inclusive (Sommer, 2020). IS is defined case as *“the use by one company or sector of underutilised resources broadly defined (including waste, byproducts, residues, energy, water, logistics, capacity, expertise, equipment and materials) from another, with the result of keeping resources in productive use for longer”* (European Committee for Standardisation, 2018). According to this approach IS regards inter-firm collaboration through the recirculation of a wide range

¹ In *Principle of economics*, Marshall (1890) wrote: *“many of the most important advances of recent years have been due to the utilising of what had been a waste product; but this has generally been due to a distinct invention, either chemical or mechanical”*.

of resources, therefore encompassing practices falling under other paradigms or eventually referred to by other names (i.e., reverse logistics, resource-recycling network, etc.).

IS indeed represent not a specific approach for waste management, but rather a system approach to keep resources in productive use, maintaining or increasing their value (Artola et al., 2018). The question of which resources have to be considered within the system boundaries of IS is still open for debate. As already stressed, more recent definitions tend to widen the conceptual boundaries with the risk of theoretical overlapping. For instance, Artola et al. (2018), in accordance with the EU definition (2018), broadly refers to materials, energy, waste, space and other intangible assets; whilst according to Chertow (2000), despite IS can refer either to joint provision of services or utility sharing, from the material perspective it explicitly refers only to byproduct reuse, thus excluding waste recycling. This position has been remarked by the author in subsequent works, stating that resources synergies encompassed by IS should refer to reused water, recovered energy, and material by-products (Chertow and Ehrenfeld, 2012), and that recycling plant should not be considered within IS network (Chertow, 2007).

Chertow (2000) provides the most cited definition of IS, which is considered the strictest (Li, 2018) because it draws two precise boundaries regarding the material and geographical scope of IS practice. Beside the focus on material byproduct rather than waste, from the spatial perspective Chertow (2000) explicitly refers to geographic proximity as a condition to IS: “*The keys to industrial symbiosis are collaboration and the synergistic possibilities offered by geographic proximity*” (Chertow, 2000). According to this approach IS involves geographically proximate organisations operating in different sectors of activity that engage in mutually beneficial transactions aimed at exploring novel avenues for sourcing inputs by reusing by-products and residual effluents thereby optimising the value of the residues generated by their processes. It follows that IS is conceived as a strategy operating at the high end of the waste hierarchy (Artola et al., 2018), focusing on opportunities to reduce and reuse and to move residuals up the value chain by providing resource- and energy-saving alternatives to the traditional management or recycling options.

The firsts to depart from this conceptual approach were Lombardi and Laybourn (2012), whose definition reflects a shift in perspective towards IS that highlights the importance of innovation and knowledge sharing to achieve eco-innovation, value creation, and long-term culture change (Lombardi and Laybourn, 2012). Considering the resources perspective, the focus is shifted from the optimisation of material consumption in terms of better use/reuse of productive residues, toward an emphasis on knowledge transfer among productive network to foster eco-innovative industrial systems in the long run (Domenech, 2021). Within the IS network, knowledge sharing yields mutually profitable transactions for novel sourcing of required inputs, value-added destinations for non-product outputs, and improved business and technical processes (Lombardi and Laybourn, 2012). Furthermore, Lombardi and Laybourn (2012) strongly reject the assumption of geographic proximity as a primary condition of IS in favour of wider networks not necessarily embedded in a defined territory. Their stance is evidenced by the following passage: “*We explicitly reject the argument of geographical proximity in favour of an argument rooted in innovation and knowledge-sharing networks that leads to, but is not driven by, improved efficiency in the use of materials*” (Lombardi and Laybourn, 2012).

Regarding the resource boundary, Boons et al. (2017), acknowledging the discrepancies in the particular waste management and categorisation norms across diverse case studies worldwide, adopt a broader view widening the scope of IS to include waste recycling. According to the authors IS can be described as a system of exchanges that converts various typologies of waste materials that used to be discarded into reusable productive inputs (Boons et al., 2017). The inclusion of waste materials has been widely accepted among the recent literature on IS, recycling can be included as long as it concerns an open-loop process, therefore when it involves two different sectors and foresees a different use for the recycled material than the original one.

It has to be noted that the first, indirect, attempt to expand the IS framework toward waste recovering was made in Chertow and Ehrenfeld (2012) contribution, where the authors mention the potential necessity of intermediate transformation to allow the reutilisation of some productive residues, therefore extending the material residues admissible to IS exchanges to waste, and, consequently, end-of-waste.

The necessity of intermediary actors and transformation platforms has been analysed by several authors (Artola et al., 2018; Domenech, 2021; Gregson et al., 2012; Patricio et al., 2022; Prosman and Währens, 2019). Particularly, Gregson et al. (2012) argue that, due to the growing importance of recycling and remanufacturing of secondary materials within the waste management frameworks, it becomes increasingly urgent to turn the consideration of secondary processing activities in studies of IS. In order to be able to activate IS material synergies, intermediate steps may be required to prepare or treat the residues. These steps may encompass upgrading the materials, cleaning, refurbishment and sometimes recycling might be necessary before the byproducts or flows are consumed again (Artola et al., 2018). For instance, with respect to the NISP project, over 70% of the completed synergies through the programme have required some sort of process innovation or technology developments (Domenech, 2021). Martin and Eklund (2011), and Oliveira Pavan et al. (2021) particularly emphasise this features by arguing that intermediary actor can be referred to as upcycling tenant, namely industrial plants taking and transforming wastes and by-products from several other industries which otherwise would not be reusable, to either add value, produce energy and/or create a new valuable intermediate product deployable by other productive processes.

Regarding the geographical scope of IS, the academic community is still divided into authors supporting Chertow (2000) stance (i.e., Ashton and Bain, 2012; H. Islam et al., 2016; K. Islam et al., 2016; Jacobsen, 2006; Taddeo et al., 2012), and others that non consider geographical proximity as a fundamental enabler for the promotion of synergies (i.e., Cerceau et al., 2014; Prosman et al., 2017; Sommer, 2020). Among the arguments in favour of local proximity, transport and logistics cost play an important role. Transport of resources is related to investment, cost and resource use which usually increase for longer distances (Sommer, 2020). Furthermore, for many materials logistic does not allow for larger distances to be covered (i.e. steam and water) (Sommer, 2020). Adopting a social perspective, geographic proximity allows for mutual trust and foster inter-firm cooperation (Ashton and Bain, 2012; Sommer, 2020).

However, the approach firstly proposed by Lombardi and Laybourn (2012) has paved the way for a series of experiences of wider breath, both at the regional, national, and international scale (Sommer, 2020). IS networks can be established at different spatial scales (Artola et al., 2018; Domenech, 2021), because there is no preferential boundary in which the material cycle must be closed (Bridgens et al., 2018). The feasibility of a given process to use a by-product of another company is indeed determined by the spatial-economic logic of the transactions among such industries (Lyons, 2007). Therefore, geographical scope varies across initiatives, and the literature offers several examples of IS operating at the regional scale to optimise resource use and utilise resources previously wasted or downgraded (Domenech, 2021). For instance, Jensen (2016) found that distance travelled by resources exchanged among IS projects was an average of 34 km. Velenturf and Purnell (2017) analysing the case study of Hamber region discovered that 73% of the involved synergies happened within a 120 km radius. Giunta et al. (2017) instead attempt to develop a tool to find the optimum break-even point for different typologies of residues allowing for the optimisation of management and transport costs, as well as the minimisation of energy consumption required by recovery and conversion activities.

According to the sectoral study conducted by Henriques et al. (2021), the geographical optimal scale of IS depends on the nature of the involved economic sectors and of the typology of streams or materials. For instance, in sectors that frequently process wastes with relatively low prices, such as agribusiness and energy (Henriques et al., 2021), geographical proximity plays an important role because long distance

would mean significant transport making synergies economically unfeasible. In relation to the energy sector, another premise is related to thermal losses associated to synergies in those sectors, that impose geographical proximity (Henriques et al., 2021). Resources typology substantially influences the geographical extension of IS network. In this regard, three main factors have to be considered to evaluate the proper distance of the synergistic transaction: i) type of waste stream and its physical and chemical characteristics; ii) value of the waste stream; and iii) geographical distribution of resource recovery facilities (Artola et al., 2018). Figure 5 provides some examples of resources transacted by area, based on Artola et al. (2018) analysis.

Local	Regional	National/International
Energy		
CHP	Fly ash	Fly ash
Steam	Metal and metal products	Critical materials
Heat	Some mineral waste oil	(rare earths, critical metals)
C&D waste		RDF (negative cost)
Green/Food waste		

Figure 5. Example of resources exchanged based on the geographical scope (Artola et al., 2018).

Therefore, while local proximity can foster IS activities in certain case, it is not a requirement for its establishment. It follows that, considering the geographical scope, the symbiotic exchanges of materials can occur: (1) within the same organisation among different productive lines; (2) between co-localised companies; (3) between local, not co-located, companies; and (4) between companies organised virtually in a wider region (Boons et al., 2017; Henriques et al., 2021; Shi and Chertow, 2017). The first case refers to the establishment of synergies within the boundaries of one organisation, focusing on the internally reuse productive residues generated by one process to replace inputs in other production processes of the same company (Henriques et al., 2021; Shi and Chertow, 2017). The remaining cases broadly refer to external exchanges (Henriques et al., 2021) among different plants. Depending on the geographical scope of the established synergy, they tend to be incorporated into different business models, such as Eco-Industrial Parks. Some authors (Desrochers, 2001; Henriques et al., 2021; Neves et al., 2020) extend the geographical scope of IS to the urban environment. This approach, often referred as Urban IS, refers to a network of community and industrial actors bridging local needs to improve resource utilisation by exploring synergies in urban and industrial areas, namely by using municipal solid waste into industrial companies (Henriques et al., 2021).

Adapting from Bossilkov et al. (2005) and Boons et al. (2017), the following Table 2 synthesises IS synergies according to: i) resource exchanged, ii) type of processing, which refers to the degree to which the wasted resource is being processed before it can be utilised by the other companies, and iii) geographical scope.

Table 2. Different types of synergies among industries, according to Resource typologies, Process required and Geographical scope.

Type of resource exchange	Type of processing	Geographical scope
<p>Water: exchange and reuse of cooling water and process water, any collective treatment and recycling of wastewater.</p> <p>Energy: shared use of energy infrastructure, co-generation and/or recovery of waste heat from steam and electricity generation.</p> <p>Non-process waste: may include waste generated while carrying out routine or emergency maintenance, packing materials, machinery components, general household waste, landscape waste, construction or demolition debris.</p> <p>Other: this type of exchange generally features some sort of service or utility sharing.</p>	<p>Direct use or reuse: without any further processing except for transport and storage.</p> <p>Energy recovery or alternative fuels covers waste heat recovery and alternative fuels for boilers and kilns. Shared electricity and gas utilities and co-generation facilities also fall into this category.</p> <p>Material recovery: involves separation and recovery processes to reclaim specific materials found in the by-products/waste stream for the beneficial use.</p> <p>Conversion into useful product: processing to produce a different useful product.</p> <p>Environmentally sound disposal: collective treatment of wastewater to enable its safe disposal.</p>	<p>Same organisation among different productive lines: resource exchanges and processing occur within different divisions or units of the same company.</p> <p>Between co-localised companies: resource exchanges and processing occur within a single industrial park or close proximity.</p> <p>Between local, not co-located, companies: resource exchanges and processing occur within the same city or region but not in immediate proximity.</p> <p>Between companies organized virtually in a wider region: resource exchanges and processing occur across broader geographic areas, potentially including multiple cities or regions.</p>

Bossilkov et al. (2005) eventually considered also the type of relation involved by the synergy, which can be either bilateral, multilateral, or service based. Despite reflecting an effective feature of IS, this distinction has been overcome in favour of a more systemic classification of the relation within the IS network. Although the literature covers a variety of approaches, the most commonly described IS networks fall into three typologies: i) self-organised, ii) facilitated, and iii) planned.

Self-organised networks are the result of a bottom-up approach based on the direct interaction between industrial actors, without external coordination (Sommer, 2020). Self-organised IS does not originate from the ambition to develop a network of symbiotic exchanges. Rather, the synergies that constitute the network have developed more or less autonomously and are driven by various motivations and incentives from the individual industrial actors (Boons et al., 2017), such as productive cost minimisation. In many instances, self-organised networks are localised in industrial district or manufacturing cluster, where large facilities and active policies to reduce or minimise landfill and other forms of pollution and impacts act as enabler for IS activation (Artola et al., 2018). Most of the successful examples of self-organised networks (Chertow and Ehrenfeld, 2012; Sommer, 2020) are indeed based on the anchor tenant model (Sun et al., 2017), where a central actor plays a pivotal role in network coordination, offering a multitude of potentially valuable by-products while simultaneously assuming de facto roles of coordination and connection between actors. Within this type of networks, geographical proximity, trust and equity play a key role in IS development (Chertow and Ehrenfeld, 2012).

In contrast, a facilitated network entails a certain degree of coordination conducted by a third party, who serves as a change agent (Artola et al., 2018) making the potential market for secondary resources more transparent and facilitating its emergence or increase in terms of the quantity of exchanges (Boons et al., 2017). This is achieved through the promotion of awareness and engagement among industrial actors, as well as facilitating the exchange of information and providing expertise and advice on the utilisation of resources. In many cases facilitated networks has been the result of public-private partnerships and

funding streams (Artola et al., 2018). Facilitated models indeed encompass a range of coordination actor, such as commercial brokers, public investment networks, research institutions and universities, or any combination thereof (Sommer, 2020). Literature on IS distinguishes two typologies of facilitation model, which represent the extremes of a spectrum. At one extreme there are ICT system, aimed at capturing and managing data on resource availability and potential synergies (Sommer, 2020). Waste marketplace and other related portals promoting IS exchanges fall under this category. On the other side of the spectrum there are hands-on support structures, which in many cases resembles or build on the NISP model. In these cases, IS is supported by a team of experts or practitioners that engage with firms and other stakeholders for the purpose of the development of IS project (Artola et al., 2018).

Finally planned network, also referred to as strategic network, represents a top-down approach to IS establishment. IS network is formed following a central plan or vision that includes attracting new business to regeneration sites or purpose-built developments (Sommer, 2020). The planification is often demanded to governmental actors who consciously design place-based eco-industrial development (Boons et al., 2017). Governmental actors are considered institutional anchors (Martin and Eklund, 2011a) since they trigger IS establishment through specific strategies and action plans implemented using both incentives and enforcement (Boons et al., 2017).

In most cases, the network relationships tend to be dynamic and changing over time (Artola et al., 2018; Boons et al., 2017; Domenech, 2021). It has been demonstrated that in many instances, self-organised networks have improved their performance switching toward a facilitated model (Artola et al., 2018; Branson, 2016). Similarly, many of the successful cases of top-down IS development have served as a pilot demonstrator, acting as a dissemination tool fostering self-organised replication (Boons et al., 2017).

Despite IS implementation may be associated to a number of economic, environmental and social benefit, its establishment is challenged by a range of barriers including technological lock-ins, economic disincentives, informational gaps, regulatory hurdle, organisational and uncertainty and risk-related barrier (Artola et al., 2018; Bossilkov et al., 2005; Domenech, 2021; Domenech et al., 2019; H. Islam et al., 2016).

Despite barriers act differently basing on the productive sector of reference (Henriques et al., 2021), technological and economical obstacles are seen as the most significant (Domenech, 2021). Technological barrier refers to the technology readiness level (TRL) of the production process involving the use of productive residue. As pointed out by Bossilkov et al. (2005) existing technologies do not always allow for the activation of a byproduct synergy. Reuse, recovery, and recycling routes often face technological lock-ins, hindering the adoption of innovative solutions. Economic barriers mainly refer to timing mismatches of residue generation and needs (Artola et al., 2018; Bossilkov et al., 2005; H. Islam et al., 2016) and lack of economic incentives to support the secondary materials market (Artola et al., 2018). In fact, a significant economic disincentive stems from low raw material prices, which heavily influences the secondary market (Dijk et al., 2013). Regarding to risk-related barrier, the main discussed risk related to IS refers to the possibility that long-term value chain partnerships may reduce companies' flexibility to respond to market changes (Herczeg et al., 2018a; Neves et al., 2020). Increasing the number of participants or alternative suppliers and buyers in the circular value chain could mitigate this issue, despite adding complexity (Artola et al., 2018; Herczeg et al., 2018a). However, increasing the inter-dependency among the industries can increase their vulnerability with respect to price and quantity variations (Islam et al., 2016).

Of a significant importance is the regulatory dimension, which has a twofold effect. Policy instruments can either facilitate IS formation or impose restrictions on industrial owners that hinder potential projects through policy fragmentation (Domenech, 2021; K. Islam et al., 2016). Governments can play a key role by adopting programs like tax reductions or pollution control, directly or indirectly creating economic

incentives for companies that incorporate IS in their production systems. At the same time, restrictive policies hinder the establishment of symbiotic exchanges by imposing strict requirements for residue quality (Artola et al., 2018; Domenech, 2021).

Defining the market size for IS is challenging due to unreported activities and fragmented, inconsistent data from various initiatives (Henriques et al., 2021). Despite being seen as a win-win approach, there is limited quantitative evidence of its potential (Artola et al., 2018). Benefits overviewed by the academic literature mainly encompass economic gains given by the reduction of the production costs and enhanced competitiveness, environmental benefits arising from the reduction of discarded resources, and social improvements in the form of new employments (Artola et al., 2018; Bossilkov et al., 2005; Domenech, 2021; Domenech et al., 2019; H. Islam et al., 2016). However, it should be noted that the social aspect of IS has not been investigated in depth by academics.

In conclusion, IS refers to the collaboration among companies pertaining to different industry segments and, therefore, it helps companies transcend their traditional supply chain boundaries and improve their economic and environmental performance (Herczeg et al., 2018a; Oliveira Pavan et al., 2021). The benefits of IS include: (i) economic savings from reduced input costs and revenues from higher-value byproduct and waste streams, (ii) environmental benefits from reduced overall resource needs, and (iii) social benefits such as new employment, securing existing jobs, and improving ecosystems for a cleaner and safer environment (K. Islam et al., 2016). On the other hand, the barriers to overcome are: (i) technological changes, (ii) divergences in production cycles, (iii) informational gaps about other companies' byproducts and waste flows, (iv) organizational issues like lack of trust, (v) regulatory hurdles that impede byproduct exchange or alliance creation, and (vi) uncertainty due to increased inter-dependency among industries, which raises investment risks (K. Islam et al., 2016).

MAIN FEATURES OF ECO-INDUSTRIAL PARK

As already mentioned, symbiotic exchanges can be implemented at different level, therefore involving a variety of business models (Boons et al., 2017; Henriques et al., 2021; Shi and Chertow, 2017). Eco-industrial Parks (EIPs) represent the main practical representation of IS and are currently recognised as the main operative tool to foster IS application (Côté and Hall, 1995; De Pascale et al., 2021; Domenech, 2021).

The idea of EIP was first introduced during a presentation at the UN Conference on Environment and Development in Rio de Janeiro 1992 to broadly describe industrial site oriented toward sustainability and EI principles (Côté and Hall, 1995; ElMassah, 2018). Therefore, the underlying concept was presented as industrial system spatially defined that ensures sustainability through the integration of social, economic and environmental quality aspects into siting, planning, management and operations (UNIDO et al., 2017). By early 2005, communities in Africa, Asia, Europe, South America, and US, had initiated EIP or other analogue eco-industrial development planning process (UNIDO et al., 2017), and, especially in the past two decades, the number of EIPs has rapidly grown worldwide, as also evidenced by the vast literature on the subject (ElMassah, 2018; Perrucci et al., 2022).

It should be noted that a multitude of terminologies and definitions are used by various organisations around the world to refer to EIPs or to relatively similar concepts (Domenech, 2021; ElMassah, 2018; Perrucci et al., 2022; Tudor et al., 2007; UNIDO et al., 2017). For instance, industrial corridor, special economic zones, eco-industrial network, eco-industrial development, industrial symbiosis network, carbon neutral parks, and green parks, are among the main common terms utilised to refer to EIP. The wide range of terms utilised to refer to EIPs testifies the absence of a standard framework for this type of industrial network.

The term indeed broadly refers to eco-industrial projects occurring within the narrower geographical scope of an industrial estate (Domenech, 2021), therefore implying a community of co-located businesses that cooperate with each other to reach better environmental performances (Lowe, 2001; Perrucci et al., 2022). The most cited definition of EIP belongs to Lowe (1997) (UNIDO et al., 2017), according to which EIP represent a community of manufacturing and service businesses located together on a common property, whose members seek enhanced environmental, economic and social performance through collaboration in managing environmental and resource issues (Lowe, 1997). Such industrial network is therefore able to conserve natural and economic resources (Côté and Hall, 1995) whilst pursuing a collective benefit that is greater than the sum of individual benefits each company would realise by only optimising its individual performance (Lowe, 2001, 1997).

Given the breadth of EIP definitions, different frameworks have been developed by a multitude of international actors (i.e., UNIDO et al., 2017; World Bank, 2014). Different green productive strategies have been thereby targeted as key elements of EIP implementation, ranging from resource exchange to the sharing of infrastructures and renewable energy production and consumption. EIP indeed has three main principles (Frosch and Gallopoulos, 1989), namely: i) minimisation of energy requirements, ii) use of industrial waste as input, iii) development of a diverse and resilient system. Following the IS theory, those three lines of action may be translated into the agglomerative possibilities firstly recognised by Chertow (2000): i) a shared infrastructure, ii) the joint provision of services; and iii) the creation of exchanges of byproducts, waste, energy and water (Gregson et al., 2012). Such three strategies may be pursued individually, without adopting an integrated approach. That is why EIP may be utilised to refer to industrial parks exclusively supplied with renewable energy sources, to parks engaged in green chemistry and bioeconomy processes, or to parks encompassing green building design, among others (Neves et al., 2020).

Even if IS represents just one of the possible strategies to be pursued, EIPs are mainly seen as leading actor to implement IS, allowing the joint organisation of resource flows of spatially grouped firms to achieve economic growth while reducing negative environmental externalities (De Pascale et al., 2021). Furthermore, the first EIPs experiences were characterised by IS initiatives and byproduct exchanges (Daddi et al., 2015). Due to the definite geographical scope, EIP has been conceptualised as the industrial system par excellence capable of better carrying out synergic relationships (Côté and Hall, 1995). Furthermore, the adoption of IS activities within an EIP makes the park a dynamic agglomeration of actors, involving matching and developing interest (Gregson et al., 2012), and therefore fostering continuous innovation. As pointed out by Valenzuela-Venegas et al., (2016), EIPs implementing IS practices are more likely to achieve integrated sustainability goals.

There are different types of material exchanges in EIPs: byproducts, wastes or real-value products (i.e., intermediate, EoW). The use of one company's productive residues as a feedstock for another company aims to reduce costs and optimise the overall environmental impacts. Such use of residues helps to achieve a transition from linear model toward a closed-loop system, which more closely resembles the cyclical flows of an ecosystem (ElMassah, 2018).

As for the broad IS networks, EIPs emergence can occur through a bottom-up approach, facilitated approach, or top-down planification (Perrucci et al., 2022; Zhang et al., 2015a). If self-organised EIPs emerges from existing private actors who are driven by economic motivations to exchange their resources; planned EIPs starts from conscious efforts, often promoted by governmental bodies, to identify potential collaborations between companies from different industrial sectors, with the objective of fostering resource sharing between them (Zhang et al., 2015a). In this regard, the academic literature pointed out that despite the first EIPs experiences have been characterised by a bottom-up approach, such as the examples coming from North Europe which are date back to 1960s or earlier (Artola et al.,

2018), last decades have seen a rise of planned EIPs especially in China and other Asian countries, which have actively promoted programme to transform old industrial parks into EIPs (Domenech, 2021).

Another frequent classification of EIPs indeed refers to the distinction between greenfield and brownfield (Conticelli and Tondelli, 2014; Zhang et al., 2015a). The first refers to a new industrial park, which is established with the intention of being an EIP. Therefore, greenfield parks are usually planned EIPs which are built from scratch, based on careful analysis of the design requirements and planning of how to meet these requirements (Zhang et al., 2015a). On the other hand, brownfield EIP represents industrial park which has been subjected to a systemic reorganisation of its manufacturing process, emphasising the adoption of greener technologies and the optimisation of energy, water, and material consumption within the boundaries of the park. As stressed by Conticelli and Tondelli (2014), despite greenfield may be more favourable from the perspective of efficiency, brownfield offers more opportunities for land regeneration and rehabilitation and, therefore, brownfield EIPs should be prioritise.

EIPs are also classified on the basis of the economic activities encompassed by the member businesses. Adapting from the classification proposed by the Chinese legislation (Ministry of Environmental Protection of the People's Republic of China, 2006a, b, 2009), it is possible to distinguish sector-integrated and sector-specific parks. The former, also referred as to mixed parks (Lambert and Boons, 2002), are composed of enterprises from different industrial sectors, with a lower level of coupling of the production processes (Zhang et al., 2015a). Sector-specific EIPs instead referred to parks characterised by the presence of one or more core enterprises from the same industrial sector, as well as some other enterprises from related industries.

Other differentiations made by academics pertain to the nature of the relationships among members. For instance, Zhang et al. (2015) distinguishes dependency-oriented, equally-oriented, and nested network, whilst other authors focus on the anchor-model (Kuznetsova et al., 2016; Martin and Eklund, 2011a).

Considering enablers and barriers of EIPs, the relevant issues are similar to those previously identified for IS. EIPs usually benefit from the geographic proximity, which incentives collaboration and mutual trust and, particularly, it lowers the eventual transport costs and ease the construction of shared infrastructure (i.e., sewage, pipelines etc.). At the same time, symbiotic synergies may increase operational risks, since a company using others' productive residues risk to become critically dependent on this supply, especially if a plant closes down or changes a product mix (Herczeg et al., 2018a; Lowe, 1997). Furthermore, by disclosing their inputs and outputs, companies risk providing important confidential information to competitors (ElMassah, 2018). Additionally, fluctuations in input prices, technological changes, and political climates can impact the stability of material and energy recycling loops within EIPs (Tudor et al., 2007).

OPERATIVE DEFINITION OF IS AND MAIN CHARACTERISTICS

In relation to the scope of GRIP research, a working definition of IS fitting with the boundaries of the research has been proposed.

IS encompasses network of different productive actors belonging to different productive sector that establish a series of physical synergies to exchange and reuse production residues and effluents, optimising the overall resource use and thereby achieving a better system performance.

The key elements of the proposed operative definition are the following:

- IS involves different productive actors, belonging to different industrial and manufacturing segments. Referring to productive actors rather than industrial actors widens the scope of potential IS network, enabling smaller units, which usually generate less residues, to be engaged in symbiotic relationships.
- IS involves transaction of productive residues, such as byproduct, waste, and residual utilities (residual heat, energy, wastewater). For the purposes of the present research, the joint provision of services as well as the sharing of spaces and other intangible assets (i.e., knowledge, logistics, expertise) are not considered.
- The typology of IS networks is not addressed, nor is the geographical scope, leaving space for different IS manifestations involving a multitude of transactions (i.e., bilateral, multilateral) or relations system (i.e., self-organised, planned, facilitated) that may or may not be embedded in a defined territory. From the spatial perspective, geographical proximity is not considered as a requisite, allowing for the analysis of regional and virtual IS cases.
- The environmental and economic outcomes of IS exceed those that could be achieved by the individual organisations acting independently.

Therefore, the presented working definition of IS does not include In-House Reuse, which is intended as the reuse of productive residual among the same productive chain. Despite it represent a common practice in large industries, and several authors count this practice under the IS umbrella (Patricio et al., 2022), it is herein considered as part of the manufacturing process, which does not involve any material exchange.

Furthermore, the suggested operative definition of IS fully includes recycling among possible symbiotic solutions as long as the recovered materials (EoW) is integrated in a different productive chain with respect to the original. Therefore, open-loop recycling is herein counted within the operative boundaries of IS, as it additionally results in accordance with the EU legal background. In this regard, it should be noted that widening the resource boundaries to include waste and, consequently, EoW, may imply the consideration off additional constraints which might affect the feasibility of certain physical flows. This is because the EU applies EoW criteria differently for each specific material.

A more detailed definition of the residues and actors included within the boundaries of the present research is presented in the following paragraphs.

DEFINITION OF PRODUCTIVE RESIDUES: BYPRODUCT, WASTE, END-OF WASTE

Among the physical resource flows counted within the present IS framework there are: byproduct, waste, and, consequently EoW. Furthermore, waste energy, in the forms of heat and steam, as well as wastewater are also included. In essence, the entire spectrum of production residues is encompassed within the purview of our system.

Therefore, post-consumer waste and post-industrial waste are excluded. Those categories of waste indeed do not originate from a productive process and are subject to specific collection and management regimes organised by municipalities. This indication is of particular significance, as it serves to further delineate the boundaries of the system by excluding the concept of urban symbiosis.

Furthermore, intermediate products flows are not considered. This typology of exchange is particularly significant within industrial districts; however it is not emblematic of IS exchanges which are mainly based on residual materials.

Production residues, also known as collateral products (Daquin et al., 2023), encompass all materials that are not deliberately produced in a production process but may or may not be waste. This terminology is therefore preferable rather than waste, since the latter may indicate different residue typologies according to the legislation of reference.

According to the EU, byproducts are defined as “a substance or object, resulting from a production process, the primary aim of which is not the production of that item”, which respects the following requirements: (a) further use of the substance or object is certain; (b) the substance or object can be used directly without any further processing other than normal industrial practice; (c) the substance or object is produced as an integral part of a production process; and (d) further use is lawful, i.e. the substance or object fulfils all relevant product, environmental and health protection requirements for the specific use and will not lead to overall adverse environmental or human health impacts (200/98/CE art. 5²).

In the absence of product- or sector-specific sources that define the fulfilment of the four general criteria, the onus of proof lies with the producer. As extensively discussed in the Italian Ministerial Decree 264/2016 and its related explanatory circular, the initial producer of the residue bears the burden of proof regarding the intention not to discard it, but to ensure its useful use in the same or another production cycle from the time of its production onwards. It is incumbent upon the holder of the residue (producer, and if different, intermediary and user) to demonstrate the circumstances set forth in Article 5, 2008/98/CE at each stage of the process, from production to final use. Additionally, the onus is on the producer to determine the most appropriate means of demonstrating that the four requirements pertaining to the by-product have been fulfilled. The means suggested by the regulations, such as the technical data sheet and contractual documentation, are in fact not necessary but only optional means of proof.

With a particular reference to comma 3, which states that byproducts should not undergo any treatment that differs from the normal industrial practice, to ensure that it is a normal industrial practice it may be useful to demonstrate that: i) the treatment does not affect the identity, product characteristics, structure of the chemical-physical components, or environmental quality of the material; ii) the treatment aligns with those ordinarily carried out in the production process in which the material is utilised, and, in particular, to those ordinarily carried out on the raw material that the by-product is to replace. Furthermore, the legislation allows for the treatment to be carried out by intermediaries.

In essence, a byproduct is a productive residue which was produced unintentionally and is not disposed of as traditional waste because it can be utilised in a different production chain as alternative input material.

Concerning waste, it is broadly defined by the EU directive as “any substance or object which the holder discards or intends or is required to discard” (2008/98/CE art. 3). It follows that productive waste refers to the waste materials generated during the productive process. According to the European Waste Framework Directive, material waste to be rehabilitated can undergo to recycling or recovering process. According to the legislation, recycling means “any recovery operation by which waste materials are reprocessed into products, materials or substances whether for the original or other purposes. It includes the reprocessing of organic material but does not include energy recovery and the reprocessing into materials that are to be used as fuels or for backfilling operations” (2008/98/CE art. 3). It follows, that recovery operations are mainly referred to waste-to-energy operations, thereby implying the recovery of the energy embedded in the discarded material.

² At the Italian level, the Directive 200/98/CE was transposed by the TUA 152/2006 as amended by 205/2010 article 184-bis.

Through recycling operations, material ceases to be waste and assumes the End-of-Waste (EoW) status. The EoW status can be obtained if the following criteria are fulfilled: “(a) the substance or object is commonly used for specific purposes; (b) a market or demand exists for such a substance or object; (c) the substance or object fulfils the technical requirements for the specific purposes and meets the existing legislation and standards applicable to products; and (d) the use of the substance or object will not lead to overall adverse environmental or human health impacts” (2008/98/CE art. 6).

Although EoW material may represent intermediate product, they are considered within the boundaries of the present IS research. EoW exchange flows is indeed indicative of a willingness to adopt environmentally conscious production processes, which involve a reduction in the utilisation of virgin raw materials. Therefore, EoW productive application results in accordance with the overall IS objectives.

DEFINITION OF ACTORS: PRODUCERS, INTERMEDIARIES, UTILISERS

Three main actors participate in IS network: producers, intermediaries, and utilisers. Although these actors are often labelled with different names, the decision to refer to this terminology have been made considering that it is utilised by several government bodies at the EU and Italian levels.

Producers represent the productive activity from which the residue originates, whilst utilisers are the targeted productive activity, hence they conduct the production process in which the residue will be reintegrated. Intermediaries are herein intended as productive plants dedicated to the reprocessing of byproduct or waste with the aim of return materials for further production processes.

DEFINITION OF ECO-INDUSTRIAL PARK

As observed during the previous discussion, under the label EIPs are included several typologies of industrial parks pursuing sustainable production. Herein, EIPs refers to industrial parks and area whereas IS network activities has been established. Therefore, only EIPs operating symbiotic exchanges of byproducts, waste, and EoW are considered during the research.

There are two key elements of EIP to be considered:

- Geographical proximity of resident businesses
- Implementation of IS activities, according to the IS operative definition

Regarding the first instance, although some authors include regional IS and virtual IS under the EIP umbrella (Lowe, 1997; Zhang et al., 2015a), herein EIP is intended just in terms of co-located IS network. The geographical scope of the park may vary depending on the context, for example it could range from 10 km² to broader area, as in the case of most Chinese EIPs. Regional and virtual IS will be indeed separately analysed.

Furthermore, despite the academic and grey literature (see for example, UNIDO et World) suggest that EIP should have a unique park manager, or should be located in a common property, EIPs experiences, particularly those related to brownfield may do not fulfil such requirement. Therefore, the presence of a body delegated to the management of the park is not considered as an inclusion criteria.

The relation system established within the network is not addressed, since one of the goal of the research consists of analysing main pattern of EIPs and, broadly, IS networks.

MAPPING THE EXISTING INDUSTRIAL SYMBIOSIS

MAPPING EIPs – AN OVERVIEW

The analysis of EIPs aims at understanding the main features of such industrial systems and, particularly, which productive sectors are more likely to be involved within symbiotic exchanges. In particular, the analysis has two main objectives: understanding the enabler factors to implement successful EIP, and overviewing EIPs from a sectoral perspective. Regarding the first aspect, emerging condition, ownership, and organisational structure, together with other descriptive variable such as the number of resident companies, status, activation year, and location, have been considered during the mapping. The sectorial analysis was conducted not only to understand the state of the art of EIP economic activities, but also to understand the feasibility of developing and implementing GRIP innovation at the territorial level. Residues exchanged have been therefore additionally classified basing on their original and destination productive sectors.

To gather relevant material Web of Science and Scopus have been selected as database of reference for academic peer-reviewed articles. The utilised search string has been: (TITLE-ABS-KEY ("industrial symbiosis") AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (eco-industrial park*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (EIP*)). Additional materials have been collected through the snowballing method. Once operative case studies have been identified, to widener the amount of data, a second research was made through Google Scholar, to gather additional grey literature. The query string has been set as: (TITLE-ABS-KEY ("industrial symbiosis") AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ("NAME OF THE EIP") AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (eco-industrial park*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (EIP*)).

Given that one of the principal objectives of the mapping of existing IS is to ascertain which productive residues and which industrial sectors are more closely involved in EIPs, only case studies that have been subjected to a material flow analysis have been taken into consideration. Consequently, articles and EIPs cases that merely present a descriptive account of the issue have been excluded.

A total of 54 EIPs and 7 regional IS have been mapped. Further 80 EIPs implementing IS activities have been identified through the literature review. However, due to the lack of MFA o specific exchanges analysis, these case studies have not been considered for the mapping. Table 3 lists the considered EIPs and the related relevant literature considered to extract secondary data. Furthermore, relevant information have been retrieved through official websites, where possible.

Table 3 List of considered EIPs for mapping existing IS.

	NAME	REFERENCE	OFFICIAL WEBSITE
1	RETDA	(Chen et al., 2022; Yu et al., 2015)	
2	HETDA	(Fan et al., 2017a, 2017b)	
3	SETDZ	(Dong et al., 2018; Geng et al., 2014; Zhao et al., 2023)	
4	QJIS	(Li et al., 2017; Sun et al., 2017)	
5	GUITANG GROUP	(Chertow, 2007; Shi and Chertow, 2017; Zhu et al., 2007; Zhu and Cote, 2004)	
6	PINGDINGSHAN COAL MINING GROUP	(Mathews and Tan, 2011; Ru-yin and Xiao-ting, 2009)	
7	Lubei EIP	(Mathews and Tan, 2011; Wang et al., 2010; Zhang et al., 2015b, 2015b)	Economia circolare (lubei.com.cn)

8	SIP	(Mathews and Tan, 2011; Wen and Meng, 2015)	
9	TEDA	(Geng et al., 2007; Hua et al., 2023; Li, 2011; Qi and Wang, 2011; Shi et al., 2010; Wang et al., 2021)	Tianjin Economic-Technological Development Area (teda.gov.cn)
10	Gujiao EIP	(Song et al., 2018)	
11	Yushen Industrial Park CISN	(Wang et al., 2017)	
12	DALU IP - CISN	(Wang et al., 2017)	
13	Lunan CISN	(Wang et al., 2017)	
14	Kalundborg	(Abhishek and Biswas, 2022; Branson, 2016; Desrochers, 2002; Faria et al., 2021; Gulipac, 2016; Jacobsen, 2006; Mathews and Tan, 2011; Steenmans, 2021)	Home - Kalundborg Symbiosis
15	Smilowo	(Kowalski et al., 2023)	Farmutil HS
16	Linhai	(Maynard et al., 2020)	
17	Mongstad	(Boix et al., 2017; Zhang et al., 2008) *	Home - Mongstad Industrial Park
18	Peterborough	(Steenmans, 2021)	
19	Rotterdam	(Baas, 2011, 2008; Baas and Korevaar, 2010; Steenmans, 2021)	
20	Kwinana	(KIC, 2023; Mathews and Tan, 2011; van Beers et al., 2008, 2007)	Welcome - Kwinana Industries Council (kic.org.au)
21	Gladstone	(Golev et al., 2014; Mathews and Tan, 2011; van Beers et al., 2007)	Gladstone Industry Leadership Group GILG
22	Mipo, Onsan	(Behera et al., 2012; Jung et al., 2012; Kim, n.d.; Mathews and Tan, 2011; Park et al., 2008)	
24	Choctaw	(Potts Carr, 1998; Zheng et al., 2013)	
25	Hull Cluster	(Cervo et al., 2019; Mirata, 2004; Rentería Núñez and Perez-Castillo, 2023; Velenturf, 2016)	HICP - The Largest CO2 Emitting Cluster in the UK (humberindustrialclusterplan.org)
26	British Sugar	(Rentería Núñez and Perez-Castillo, 2023; Short et al., 2014)	World class sugar producers British Sugar, UK
27	Campbell Industrial Park (AES network)	(Branca et al., 2021; Chertow and Miyata, 2011; Eckelman and Chertow, 2013)	
28	Taranto	(Notarnicola et al., 2016)	Porto Taranto
29	Grangemouth	(Harris and Pritchard, 2004)	
30	AES Guyama	(Chertow and Lombardi, 2005)	
31	Barceloneta	(Ashton, 2008, 2011, 2009; Ruiz-Puente, 2021)	
32	Hartberg Ecopark	(Gibbs and Deutz, 2007; Liwarska-Bizukojc et al., 2009)	Home - Ecopark Gewerbepark Hartberg (oekopark-gewerbepark.at)
33	Händelö bioenergy complex	(Johnsen et al., n.d.; Kastner et al., 2015; Martin and Eklund, 2011b)	About Händelö Händelö Eco-Industrial Park (heip.se)
34	Stenungsund Industrial Park	(Hackl et al., 2011, n.d.; Hackl and Harvey, 2013a, 2013b; Kastner et al., 2015; Røyne et al., 2015)	
35	Tra Noc IZ	(Stucki et al., 2019)	
36	Biopark Terneuzen	(Boons et al., 2014; Calderón, 2021; Nuhoff-Isakhanyan et al., 2017; Nuhoff-Isakhanyan and Wubben,	

		2015; Santos, 2015; Spekkink, 2015, 2013)	
37	Harjavalta	(Jyrki and Tuomo Koskenkari, 2004; Layton et al., 2016)	
38	Bazancourt-Pomacle	(Ayrapetyan et al., 2022; Morales, 2020; Morales et al., 2022; Morales and Lhuillery, 2021; Santos, 2018; Stadler and Chauvet, 2018)	
39	Mönsterås	(Baas, 2012, n.d.; Lo et al., 2023; Wolf and Petersson, 2007)	Our mill in Mönsterås (sodra.com)
40	IPOS	(Mirata, 2018)	
41	Landsrkona	(Adamides and Mouzakis, 2009; Maltin, 2004; Mirata and Emtairah, 2005b)	
42	Sotenäs	(Martin and Harris, 2018)	Symbiosis Centre - Symbiosis Centre (symbioscentrum.se)
43	Dunkirk	(Kasmi, 2021; Morales and Diemer, 2019)	
44	Kouvola	(Chiaroni and Musu, 2020; Sokka et al., 2011)	
45	Relvão Eco Industrial Park	(Costa and Ferrão, 2010; Neves et al., 2019; Reis, 2019)	
46	Koekhoven	(Boons et al., 2015)	
47	Kansas city	(Cimren et al., 2011)	
48	Nanjangud Industrial Area	(Bain et al., 2010; Herczeg et al., 2018b; Khan et al., 2023)	
49	Kokkola Industrial Park	(Haq, 2021; Salmi et al., 2012; Siskos and Van Wassenhove, 2017)	The largest inorganic chemical industry ecosystem in Northern Europe KIP - Kokkola Industrial Park KIP - Kokkola Industrial Park
50	Kaiserbaracke	(Chamber of Commerce of Molise, 2017; Lo et al., 2023)	
51	Uimaharju Bioindustrial Area	(Jussila, n.d.; Korhonen and Snäkin, 2005; Lo et al., 2023; Saikku, 2006)	
52	Rantasalmi EIP	(Lo et al., 2023; Saikku, 2006)	
53	ValuePark Schkopau	(Biedrońska, 2018; Liwarska-Bizukojc et al., 2009)	www.dow.com/valuepark/
54	Ponte a Egola APEA	(Daddi et al., 2016; Susur et al., 2019; Tiziano Marradi, 2019)	
*Additional data for Mongstad EIP has been gathered through interview.			

Table 4 summarises the economic activities and the symbiotic exchanges occurring within each EIP.

Table 4. Brief description of the main features of the considered EIPs.

ID	NAME	BRIEF DESCRIPTION
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1	RETDA	RETDA industrial system focuses on the three leading industries of cereal oil and food, pulp and paper, and automobile parts; starting with the exchange of waste/by-products within firms; gradually establishing collaborations among different industrial companies; improving the efficiency of resource flows; and continually improving the circular supply chain network.
2	HETDA	Over the past two decades, HETDA has established 4 pillar industries (home appliances, equipment manufacturing, automobile and parts, fast-moving consumer goods) and 4 emerging industries (electronic information, new materials, bio-pharmaceuticals, industrialized housing). Under the NDEIP project, the wastewater pipelines were extended to 287 km and the wastewater treatment capacity reached to 8.513E+7 t/yr. HETDA rejected some plants due to high consumption and phased out over 50 inefficient coal-burning boilers. All the 24 polluters adopted cleaner production methods. The Jinyuan thermal power plant, a model for energy conservation, adopted advanced emission reduction technology. HETDA promoted by-product exchanges and infrastructure sharing among industries, such as using fly ash for construction materials and reusing scrap metal, enhancing eco-industrial development.
3	SETDZ	There are 2021 types of industrial enterprises in SETDZ, including 83 transnational corporations and 231,000 employees. SETDZ employs a circular economic model by fostering cleaner production companies and thereby realizes a reduction of waste emissions. SETDZ has six major industrial clusters, which are equipment manufacturing, automobile and parts manufacturing, pharmaceutical and chemical, food processing, building materials, and textile industries. SETDZ establishes and improves comprehensive utilization management systems for resources, extends industrial chains, increases resource utilization, and builds demonstration bases for the sustainable development.
4	QJIS	Qijiang Industrial Park is located in Chongqing, China, which has been rapidly expanding, relying on its advantage in terms of coal production, amounting to an annual output of 10 million tons. The park primarily produces aluminum products for automotive, railway, and construction sectors, with by-products such as FGD gypsum, ammonium sulfate, coal ash, and aluminum scrap being integrated into industrial symbiosis chains. The network has 17 nodes and 84 edges, indicating a moderately connected system. Management strategies to reduce vulnerability include adopting flexible sourcing, increasing network connectivity, and implementing real-time monitoring systems.

5	GUITANG GROUP	<p>The Guitang Group (GG), which operates one of China's largest sugar refineries, has been developing and implementing an internal and external industrial symbiosis strategy for more than four decades. The GG first invested in developing its own collection of downstream companies to utilize nearly all byproducts of sugar production. This strategy has generated new revenues and reduced environmental emissions and disposal costs, while simultaneously improving the quality of sugar. Internally, the GG's complex consists of interlinked production of sugar, alcohol, cement, compound fertilizer, and paper and includes recycling and reuse. Externally, the GG has established a strong customer base as a result of its product quality, has worked to maintain and expand its supply base through technological and economic incentives to farmers (and even to competitors), and has had to react to a strong government presence that fundamentally affects its operations.</p>
6	PINGDINGSHAN COAL MINING GROUP	<p>The Pingdingshan Coal Mining Group (Pingmei), established in 1955 as a large-scale coal mine, has accumulated nearly 54 million tonnes of coal waste and emitted millions of tonnes of coal gangue, coal slime, and fly ash annually. Additionally, it has caused land subsidence and harmful emissions. Starting in the 1980s, Pingmei introduced recycling measures and cross-stream activities to utilize these wastes. By the 2000s, Pingmei had developed a significant building materials business using coal slime, fly ash, and coal gangue to produce gangue cement, fly ash cement, and fly ash concrete blocks. These initiatives improved eco-efficiency by reusing contaminants in new value chains, earning Pingmei recognition as a circular economy Pilot Demonstration site.</p>
7	Lubei EIP	<p>The Lubei Group, a large state-owned chemical complex in Wudi, Shandong Province, was established in 1977. It produces significant quantities of ammonium phosphate, sulfuric acid, cement, sea salt, sodium hydroxide, and bromine. Lubei operates three main value chains: (1) sulfuric acid-ammonium phosphate-cement chain; (2) seawater utilization chain; (3) salt-alkali-electric power generation chain. Key shared resources are sulfuric acid and seawater, with steam and electric power as primary energy flows. Waste materials like gypsum and furnace slag are repurposed, and innovative uses of former wastes, such as aquaculture with warm recycled water, enhance eco-efficiency. The building materials chain notably uses considerable waste as raw materials, saving on raw material costs.</p>

8	SIP	<p>The Suzhou Industrial Park (SIP), established in 1994 as a China-Singapore cooperation project, began seeking national EIP accreditation in 2002. The park hosts 2,400 foreign-funded enterprises, including 66 of the world's top 500 companies, spanning industries like chemicals, pharmaceuticals, healthcare, machinery, electronics, IT, and software. SIP is a major IT manufacturing hub, producing 16% of China's integrated circuit products and serving as the largest export base for LCD panels. It boasts the largest gas-fired combined cycle cogeneration plant in China, which generates power and provides district heating while reusing treated wastewater as cooling water. SIP enhances eco-efficiency through wastewater and energy exchange between residential and industrial sectors and pursues a “value chain completion” strategy to integrate firms within wider activity chains. This includes e-waste recycling across the IT value chain, from upstream electronic chemicals manufacturing through semiconductor and TFT-LCD production to downstream consumer products.</p>
9	TEDA	<p>The Tianjin Economic-Technological Development Area (TEDA), established in 1984, is a leading Eco-Industrial Park in China that integrates industrial symbiosis to enhance sustainability and economic performance. TEDA's four “pillar industries”(electronics, automobile & machinery, biotechnology & pharmaceutical, and food & beverage industries) contribute a gross industrial output value of RMB 308 billion. Key symbiotic activities include: (1) using reclaimed water from sewage treatment for industrial processes and landscaping; (2) supplying steam and hot water from coal-fired plants, with condensate recycling and desalination facilities; (3) producing soil from industrial waste and converting municipal solid waste into electricity and construction materials and (4) promoting symbiosis across electronics, automotive, biotechnology, and food sectors includes recycling materials like lead solder and food scraps.</p>
10	Gujiao EIP	<p>The Gujiao Eco-Industrial Park, established in 2012, is currently the largest coal and coal tar production base in China. It hosts 38 firms involved in coal mining, processing, wastewater treatment, power generation, construction materials, and coal-based chemicals. The park has adopted industrial symbiosis practices to optimize resource use and minimize waste. Key symbiotic activities include using coal mining byproducts as raw materials in other industrial processes, recycling wastewater, and exchanging intermediate goods among firms.</p>

11	Yushen Industrial Park CISON	<p>Yushen Industrial Park, initially built around a large coking plant, has evolved into a complex industrial ecosystem by adopting coal gasification and liquefaction technologies. The park now focuses on coal coking, gasification, and indirect coal liquefaction, with additional activities in coal chemical processing, salt chemical industries, equipment manufacturing, and new materials. The park features intricate vertical and horizontal material flows, such as coal to coal gas to synthesis gas to methyl alcohol and dimethyl ether, and coal gangue to thermal power. These flows link large enterprises with SMEs and facilitate exchanges among all enterprises, enhancing resource efficiency and supporting diverse industrial activities.</p>
12	DALU IP - CISON	<p>Based on the advantage of positioning industry, the park has dominated by coal-electricity and coal-chemical industry, striving to develop coal-chemical downstream fine chemical industry and electrolytic aluminium industry and its deep processing industry, taking the comprehensive utilization of coal residue, fly ash, waste residue, waste gas and waste water as the key, which formed a circular economy industry pattern. Among that, Yitai Group, Jiutai Group, China Power Investment Corporation, CNOOC and Huadian Coal Group are large enterprises. They become the core enterprise of the park and a large number of downstream SME build factories around them. The material mainly flow from the core enterprises to small and medium-sized enterprises. There are not only vertical material flows, but also horizontal material flows. Despite the extensive material flows, symbiotic relationships among the core enterprises are minimal, and there are only a few simple exchanges among SMEs, such as industrial wastewater being repurposed as industrial water.</p>
13	Lunan CISON	<p>Depending on the coal resource advantage, Lunan Industrial Park vigorously promoted the integration of raw materials as well as water resources and the comprehensive utilization of waste from three leading industries of the coal mining, coal-to-chemicals and electrolytic aluminum. More and more companies, such as power plants, coal chemical plants, electrolytic aluminum plants, building materials plants, sewage treatment plants and land rehabilitation companies have set up in the park. These companies are SME, and multi-level and multi-channel resource utilization occurs among the enterprises. Including vertical material flows and horizontal material flows. Lunan Industrial Park has typical characteristics of equality-based symbiosis networks.</p>

14	Kalundborg	The Kalundborg Eco-Industrial Park in Denmark is a partnership between seventeen public and private companies. Established in the late 1960s, the park includes a power plant, a refinery, a pharmaceutical manufacturer, and a gypsum board facility, among others. Key symbiotic exchanges include using excess heat from the power plant for district heating, converting refinery gas into energy, and utilizing fly ash from the power plant in cement production. Additionally, wastewater from industrial processes is treated and reused, and surplus sulfur from the refinery is used in sulfuric acid production. These exchanges create a closed-loop system that reduces waste, lowers energy consumption, and minimizes environmental impact, making Kalundborg a model for sustainable industrial development.
15	Smilowo	Farmutil is one of the largest and most modern agricultural and food concerns in Poland, with several dozen production plants throughout Poland. Smilowo EIP belongs to the Polish Farmutil agri-food consortium, consisting of 13 firms with 36 production and service installations. The implemented EIP symbiotic actions follow the Farmutil consortium strategy, creating a symbiotic production model including the whole life cycle of obtained products.
16	Linhai	Linhai Industrial Park is one of the major heavy industrial parks located in the southwest of Taiwan and was first established in 1960 and completed in 1972. The major industries that makeup Linhai include steel mills, a petrochemical complex, a coal-fired power plant, aluminum manufacturing plants, industrial gas production, and other smaller steel mills. The park covers 15.69 km ² . Among these heavy industries, China Steel Corporation (CSC) is the largest firm in the park.
17	Mongstad	The Mongstad Eco-Industrial Park (EIP) is built around an oil refinery operated by Statoil. This EIP integrates several facilities to optimize resource use and minimize waste through industrial symbiosis. The main facilities include the oil refinery, a gas processing plant, a port, significant underground storage tanks, a planned gas-fired combined heat and power (CHP) plant, coal gasification units, synthetic fuel production, carbon capture and utilization systems, and aquaculture operations. Key industrial symbiosis exchanges at Mongstad involve using refinery gases in the CHP plant to produce electricity and high-pressure steam for the refinery's operations.
18	Peterborough	It is conceived as an EIP, even if the symbiotic exchanges are few and mainly based on post-consumer waste. In addition, the symbiosis does not happen within a physical park, but it involves different company located in the same city.

19	Rotterdam	The Rotterdam Harbour and Industry Complex (HIC) evolved from an environmental sanitation area (1968–1998) into a hub for industrial symbiosis (IS) projects. Initiated by the industrial association Deltalinqs, the INES project began in 1994, involving 69 firms in environmental management and IS alliances, such as utility sharing. The subsequent INES Mainport Project (1999–2002) focused on water, CO ₂ /energy, utility sharing, waste management, and logistics. In 2003, IS efforts were incorporated into the Sustainable Rijnmond and Energy 2010 programs under the R3 Sustainable Enterprises initiative, fostering collaboration among industry, government, academia, and environmental organizations for regional sustainability.
20	Kwinana	The industrial area was established in the 1950s following a special Act of Parliament, which secured an area of about 120square kilometers (km ²) to accommodate the development of major resource processing industries in Western Australia. It is one of Australia’s largest mineral processing regions with nearly 50 successfully existing regional synergies. This positions Kwinana as a leading international example of regional synergy implementation.
21	Gladstone	Gladstone EIP (Eco-Industrial Park) in Queensland, Australia, is a significant hub for industrial symbiosis. It is one of the most industrially intensive areas in the country, contributing 30% of Queensland's exports. Major industries include alumina refining, aluminum smelting, power generation, cement clinker production, and chemical manufacturing. These industries form the Gladstone Area Industry Network (GAIN), which facilitates collaborative efforts in resource sharing and waste management. Current synergies include using alternative fuels in cement production, reusing treated effluent for industrial processes, and recycling fly ash from power plants as a cement additive.
22	Mipo, Onsan	In Ulsan, the conversion of conventional industrial complexes into EIPs had evolved on a company-to-company basis by the mid-1990s. However, prior to the launch of the EIP project in 2005, the industrial complexes were developed based on the production priority policy with supply chains and artery networks including the collective utility systems, generating huge amounts of by-products and waste materials, which were not circulated by vein networks. Thus, the major goal of the Ulsan EIP project was to innovate new opportunities, and renovate/upgrade the Ulsan Mipo-Onsan industrial complexes by transforming them into EIPs through a systematic application of industrial symbiosis. The key stakeholders in the Ulsan EIP project are the Ulsan EIP center, the Ulsan Metropolitan City government, various research and development centers, companies in the Mipo-Onsan industrial complexes and,
23	Kawasaki zero-emission industrial complex	Kawasaki eco-town is one of the most famous EIP in the world, under Japanese national eco-town project from 1997 to 2006. Industrial symbiosis in heavy industries clustered area and urban symbiosis between industrial and urban area is the feature of Kawasaki eco-town, illustrated as Fig. 5, Fig. 6. With planning and coordination, there were several urban-industrial symbiosis projects taking place, driven by heavy industries like steel plant and cement company, as well as the urban waste recycling to industrial clusters (urban industrial symbiosis).

24	Choctaw	Around 1998 an investigation was made to discover potential synergies among co-located firms in Oklahoma. These industrial partnerships include the City of Choctaw Waste Water Treatment Plant, a tire shredding company, a tire pyrolysis company, a hydroponics industry, a hard rubber tire manufacturer, a screen printer, a plastics manufacturer, a toner manufacturer, and a toner cartridge manufacturer. This collaboration repurposes waste tires into valuable materials such as extender process oil, carbon black, steel, and fiberglass pellets, using the treated wastewater for non-potable needs.
25	Hull Cluster	The Humber Eco-Industrial Park in the UK showcases the potential of industrial symbiosis to foster sustainable industrial practices. The park comprises diverse industries including cement, chemicals, minerals, and engineering, strategically located to facilitate resource sharing and collaboration.
26	British Sugar	The British Sugar Wissington factory transforms waste streams from sugar production into valuable resources. By utilizing waste heat and CO ₂ for tomato cultivation, British Sugar produces 140 million specialty tomatoes annually. The factory also processes bagasse into animal feed and captures CO ₂ for the soft drinks industry, illustrating the extensive reuse of by-products. Additionally, British Sugar has ventured into bioethanol production, converting surplus sugar into renewable fuel.
27	Campbell Industrial Park (AES network)	The Campbell Industrial Park (CIP) in Honolulu County, Hawai'i, illustrates the benefits of industrial symbiosis through its network of 11 facilities. These companies exchange water, materials, and energy, significantly reducing environmental impacts. The core of the network includes the AES coal-fired power plant, Kalaeloa cogeneration plant, and Chevron and Tesoro oil refineries. By sharing resources such as steam, water, and waste materials, they achieve substantial savings in primary energy use.
28	Taranto	The Taranto Eco-Industrial Park in southern Italy is centered around the Ilva steelwork. This industrial district includes diverse heavy industries such as steel production, oil refining, cement manufacturing, and power generation. The district generates 3.25 million tons of solid waste and consumes 182.4 PJ of energy annually. By applying industrial symbiosis principles, significant amounts of waste energy (44.6 PJ/year) and material by-products (3.28 Mt/year) like slag, mill scale, spent refractories, and coal fly ash can be efficiently recycled within various industrial sectors.

29	Grangemouth	The Grangemouth Development Group (GDG), formed in 1992 in Scotland, includes major companies, the Local Enterprise Council, and other stakeholders. GDG meetings facilitate sharing of ideas and resources, resulting in various exchanges such as steam and water sharing, and waste material utilization. Notable initiatives include the formation of the Grangemouth Water Users Group (GWUG) in 1999, aiming to sustainably manage the area's water use, which led to significant cost savings and environmental benefits.
30	AES Guyama	Current exchanges in Guayama include the new AES coal-fired power plant using reclaimed water from a public wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) for cooling, and providing steam to the oil refinery. Additional steam and wastewater exchanges are under negotiation between neighboring pharmaceutical plants, the refinery, and the power plant. Beneficial reuse of the coal ash has begun as a means of stabilizing some liquid wastes. An analysis follows of existing and potential exchanges in Guayama with the power plant and refinery as critical participants.
31	Barceloneta	The Barceloneta Eco-Industrial Park in Puerto Rico exemplifies successful industrial symbiosis, primarily driven by pharmaceutical companies. Initiated in the 1970s, this park has developed synergies where companies share resources like energy, water, and materials. Key symbiotic activities include solvent recovery by waste management firms, which distill and return solvents to the pharmaceutical companies for reuse. The treated sludge from the wastewater treatment plant is utilized as fertilizer for hay farming. These activities are coordinated through the Barceloneta Wastewater Treatment Corporation Advisory Council, which manages the region's secondary wastewater treatment plant and promotes additional collaborative projects like energy cogeneration.
32	Hartberg Ecopark	The Hartberg Eco-Industrial Park in Austria is an exemplary model of industrial symbiosis, featuring around 30 SMEs that collaborate spontaneously. Established in 1997 by Hartberg Municipality, the park spans approximately 15 hectares and integrates business, research, and entertainment. Key participants include a power plant producing energy from various sources, a cellulose insulation manufacturer, and a construction materials producer. The symbiotic relationships are evident as the power plant supplies energy to the park, and the insulation manufacturer uses waste paper from other consumers within the park. Additionally, two waste management companies recycle and compost organic waste, generating biogas for energy. The development of Ecopark Hartberg was supported not only by Hartberg Municipality, but also by land Steyer, federal government of Austria and the European Union.

33	Händelö bioenergy complex	The history of Händelö business collaborations or IS is centred primarily on the development of the CHP plant, which was sold by the municipality to EON in the early 1990s. The development of this plant has involved a shift from fossil fuels towards primarily renewable resources, and utilization of the waste streams associated with power production. One interviewee pointed out that a CHP plant is not innovative from a Swedish perspective, but in a European context this might still be considered IS. The development of this power plant, and of the Lantmännen Agroetanol plant in 2001, is the strongest evidence of IS. This was most likely when the description of Händelö as an IS started. Together with a biogas plant owned by Svensk Biogas (installed in 2007), these businesses constitute an IS. Lately, other activities have been linked to the IS of Händelö; one of these is a chemical factory (operated by AGA) that is upgrading CO ₂ from the ethanol plant. The plant is actually owned by both Agroetanol and AGA and operated through a joint venture business.
34	Stenungsund Industrial Park	The companies involved and their main products are AGA Gas AB producing industrial gases, Akzo Nobel Sverige AB producing amines and surfactants, Borealis AB producing ethylene and polyethylene (PE), INEOS Sverige AB producing polyvinyl chloride (PVC) and Perstorp Oxo AB producing specialty chemicals. The companies have recently announced a common vision called “Sustainable Chemistry 2030” with the intention to increase collaboration for energy savings, increased use of renewable resources and decreased overall emissions. The heart of the cluster is a steam cracker plant run by Borealis, which delivers both feedstock and fuel gas to the other plants.
35	Tra Noc IZ	Tra Noc IZ (1,2 - Can Tho) is the most successful EIPs project financed by UNIDO to develop EIP in Vietnam. This EIP directly engages the municipality and it is founded not just on waste and by-product exchanges, but also on sharing utilities and services. Key examples include biogas recovery for use in adjacent company boilers, leading to a 33% reduction in biomass consumption.
36	Biopark Terneuzen	It is a planned agro-industrial park located in the province of Zeeland. Initiated in 2005 and established in 2007, Biopark Terneuzen connects 23 organizations at 445 ha area. The park connects energy generators and distributors, chemical companies, food and feed producers, horticultural growers, waste/recycling companies, and business consultants. Biopark Terneuzen established a waste heat and CO ₂ supply system from the industrial companies to the local horticultural companies.
37	Harjavalta	Harjavalta is a town with mining industries. Harjavalta Industrial Park employs over 1,000 people. The Industrial Ecopark consists of thirteen firms. Outokumpu copper and nickel smelters form the heart of the area. Extra energy from their processes is utilized as electricity, high temperature steam or heating energy by the process plant or the town of Harjavalta. The energy efficient autogenous flash smelting technology was invented in Harjavalta after World War II when there was a shortage of energy in Finland.

38	Bazancourt-Pomacle	<p>The Bazancourt-Pomacle Platform entails the most remarkable example of a successful industrial symbiosis in the Bioeconomy field. It is composed by 10 actors including Vivescia / Bletanol, Cristal Union, Cristanol, Chamtor, Givaudan Active Beauty, Wheatoleo, Air Liquide, European of biomass, the Industrial research center (ARD) and an academic research center (CEBB). Within the sugar beet value chain, we can identify the following products and by-products: (1) the green sugar juice and syrups which, as a result of crystallization or distillation, will result in products such as sugar, alcohol and bioethanol. (2) the stillage, low quality syrup from crystallization, and the CO₂ resulting from distillation and crystallization. In general, by products are reused within the boundaries of the platform: low-purity syrup to be distilled into alcohol or bioethanol, CO₂ to gasify drinking beverages, pressed pulps for animal feed, and finally, the scum from syrup production as well as the stillage are reused as fertilizers</p>
39	Mönsterås	<p>In Mönsterås, a chemical pulp mill, a sawmill and a pellet production facility are co-located and partly integrated. The sawmill and the pulp mill have different owners, but are part of the same group of companies (Södra). Integrated in, and owned by, the pulp mill is a pellet production plant</p>
40	IPOS	<p>Industry Park of Sweden (IPOS) is an industrial park owned and operated by Kemira in Helsingborg, Sweden. IPOS applies an industrial symbiosis and the companies within the park collaborate around energy, material, utilities, logistics, infrastructure and services. The park hosts approx. 20 companies within chemical- and food industry, logistics and service. Main component of the collaboration is sharing of recovered energy from chemical industry company Kemira's processes. It is operational in the Helsingborg area, concentrated around the following three main actors: Kemira Kemi AB (a chemicals plant producing sulphuric acid), Öresundskraft AB (publicly owned local energy utility company) and Nordvästra Skånes Renhållnings (NSR) AB (publicly owned local waste management company). At the level of an industrial-park, a number of actors, majority working with the production of chemicals, are connected through supply- and utility-synergies (involving steam, heating, compressed air, and process and cooling water systems) within the Industry Park of Sweden (IPOS), where Kemira Kemi is a central player. The IPOS system, in turn, is a part of a wider set of synergistic connections, involving actors such as the local energy utility and waste management companies, a biogas plant, the local community, regional farmers and industries.</p>
41	Landsrkona	<p>The results from the Landskrona industrial symbiosis project are limited to the use of waste for district heating, to collective waste management, cooperation in transport and logistics, use of unprocessed waste, and use of renewable energy technologies as input energy efficiency technologies.</p>

42	Sotenäs	<p>IS network in the municipality of Sotenäs, Sweden which has been facilitated by the Sotenäs Symbiosentrum, with the overall goal to create green, local jobs while contributing to a better environment and sustainable future. A number of synergies between industrial actors have been realized, and several exchanges are awaiting permits in order to implement the necessary infrastructure to allow for the exchanges to ensue. These include renewable energy, food production, aquaculture, algae production, marine technology and innovative products upcycling waste heat, fish industry waste and other wastes from the neighboring sea to create value-added products and processes. The network includes several current firms involved in fish processing industries, algae production, a system for recycling plastic wastes from the sea and a land-based salmon farm. In the future an anaerobic digestion (biogas) plant will be included, allowing for many of the synergies to be realised.</p>
43	Dunkirk	<p>The Dunkirk urban area (north of France) has grown in a context of rapid territorial industrialization starting in the early 1990s, spurring port activity and the iron and steel industry through bilateral relations between firms which established the core for some early synergies related to waste recycling and energy flows. Since the 1960s, the industrialization of Dunkirk has had environmental consequences, which in addition to the economic crisis in the 1990s lead to compelling requests to improve quality of life and environmental regulation. To meet this request, a shared territorial action plan emerged, paving the way for industrial symbiosis implementation. The association of Economy and Ecology Partners in Local Action (ECOPAL in French), was created in 2001 as the local institution in charge of industrial ecology promotion in the territory and encouraging industrial symbiosis in Dunkirk through pooling services assistance. By-product synergies in Dunkirk industrial symbiosis also play a relevant role. The by-product synergy network is composed by 14 firms that exchange by-products like scrap, steel slag, refractory bricks, steel mill dust, acid waste, tires, solvents, animal feed and used oil.</p>

44	Kouvola	<p>The system has evolved spontaneously (meaning that it was not intentionally developed as an industrial symbiosis) around an integrated pulp and paper manufacturer, the Kymi mill of the UPM Kymmene Corporation. Paper production began at the site in 1874. This symbiotic network includes a power plant that uses wood residues and sludge from the mill to generate heat and electricity, supplying both the mill and the town of Kouvola. Additionally, the network comprises three chemical plants that receive energy and purified water from the mill and, in turn, provide chemicals for the paper production process. Notably, the calcium carbonate plant utilizes carbon dioxide from the mill's flue gases. The municipal sewage plant also integrates with the mill by sending nutrient-rich sludge, reducing the need for additional chemicals in wastewater treatment.</p>
45	Relvão Eco Industrial Park	<p>This was the result of the interaction between national, local government, industries, and other entities who, from a set of concerted actions, such as the provision of a large area at lower prices for industries implementation, holding meetings to inform and promote relationships between agents, and through waste management facilities, provide a cluster for waste treatment and recovery, attract more companies to the site and make them participate in the industrial symbiosis network, and thus contribute to the development of the municipality. These entities engage in exchanges of materials like containers, acids, biomass, plastics, metals, and sludge.</p>
46	Koekhoven	<p>A farmers' partnership started a bio-gas cogeneration plant in 2006 using manure and biomass streams from farms. The heat is used to dry manure, which is transferred to greenhouses in the nearby greenhouse park. Linkages continue to evolve through joint ventures beyond agriculture. In the same area, other linkages are emerging. the 140-hectare greenhouse park Koekhoven has been established; it houses 70 ha of greenhouse firms. Greenhouses in this park use cogeneration for heating and transmit the generated power to the power grid. A biogas cogeneration firm uses manure and corn from various farmers to generate electricity. This firm transmits power to the grid and the heat generated goes to manure-drying and a greenhouse in the park. This firm has joint ventures with others: first, to remove the packaging from organic waste from retailers so that the waste can be used as input for the biogas installation; second, to commercialise dried manure pellets; and, third, to invest in cogeneration of jatropha oil.</p>

47	Kansas city	<p>The Kansas City By-Product Synergy (BPS) network employs the Eco-Flow™ model to optimize material flows among participating companies. This network involves about 150 nodes and 100 arcs, connecting various suppliers and customers. this network has nine participants: Cook Composites & Polymers (CCP), Gerdau-Ameristeel (GA), Hallmark (HM), Harley Davidson (HD), KCMO Solid Waste (KCW), KC Power & Light (KCP), Lafarge (L), Missouri Organics (MO), and Systech (S). The suppliers are companies that have waste materials such as bottom ash, food waste, scrap metal, millscale, and polyethylene. The customers are the companies that can use these waste materials as inputs to their processes. If waste materials from suppliers are converted into byproducts, then these products can be exchanged, sold, or transferred free of charge between suppliers and customers. These wastes have a variety of possible uses for customers as substitutes for materials (e.g., fuels, solvents) that are normally procured from outside the network. A customer’s process that uses by-products from a supplier as inputs is defined to be a “synergy.” There are 30 types of by-product materials (wood chips and solid waste are used twice) and 15 types of potential uses (i.e., synergies) in the Kansas City BPS network.</p>
48	Nanjangud Industrial Area	<p>Many of the industries in the region are based on processing agricultural products and thus generate organic residues from their production. These materials are easily recovered because they are not hazardous and have high calorific and nutritive content. Indian industries have utilized agricultural residues as fuels in their production processes for centuries. The biomass residues used for energy generation in NIA tend to remain at the facilities where they are generated, or are purchased from specialist suppliers. Three facilities produce electricity in grid-tied power plants, taking advantage of the Karnataka State Electricity Supply Act (1991) that encourages independent production in order to ease the burden on generating capacities at state utilities. All use majority biomass feed stocks, and use supplemental coal to supply sufficient energy density to reduce incomplete combustion. Biomass residues are easily combustible in boilers designed for coal. The energy efficiency of the boilers may be lower when fueled by biomass, as it is less energetically dense per unit volume.</p>

49	Kokkola Industrial Park	<p>Kokkola Industrial Park (KIP) is Northern Europe's largest ecosystem of inorganic chemical industry, where several companies leading in the chemical and metal processing industries operate. In the Park, there are 16 industrial / manufacturing companies and over 60 service companies, which support the core functions of industrial companies. Industrial companies in the Park implement the synergy between the company's production process and the further processing of by-products arising therefrom. Thus, material and energy flows become more efficient and the amount of process waste can be significantly reduced. KIP is involved in, among others, a national eco-industrial park network project founded by Sitra. Behind the Park's success, there is a strong, decades-long cooperation and living in so-called industrial symbiosis. Many levels of different synergies, such as utilization of process industry's side streams, centralized service production, and the joint development of business culture especially around EHSQ (environment, health, safety, quality), have been established between companies.</p>
50	Kaiserbaracke	<p>Symbi project INTERREG Kaiserbaracke is a successful example of an industrial symbiosis that involves SMEs, local authorities and public agencies and where companies act only as business partners. At the Kaiserbaracke industrial park, wood is used as a raw material for energy production. The Holz Niessen company is a timber sorting centre. As a result of the wood sorting process at the Belwood sawmill, 50% of the wood is turned into finished and semi-finished products, with the remainder being bark, sawdust, and scrap wood. Production wastes are treated entirely on-site to produce heat (Renogen company), pellet (Delhez company), semi-finished wooden products. The Renogen company then contributes with its co-generation centre that allows for the production of heat and mechanical energy which is then converted into electricity. Heat is used both to produce pellet in Delhez and wood plank in Belwood by drying sawdust. Surplus heat is sold to the public electricity network. Ashes from the combustion of biomass are used in the construction industry for the production of clinker or ballast. The next stage of the project development was joined by Spi + , the economic development agency for the province of Liège, which is responsible for the development of the infrastructure of the industrial park. The area where the park is located belongs to Amblève municipality.</p>

51	Uimaharju Bioindustrial Area	<p>The Uimaharju bioindustrial area is located close to the Uimaharju district of Joensuu, about 45 kilometres northeast of the centre of Joensuu. The area is located in the immediate vicinity of the main road 73 and along the railway line between Joensuu and Nurmes and has timber loading and storage areas. In the regional land use plan, the area is marked as an area for employment and energy infrastructure. Updating of the local detailed plan for the area began in spring 2016. There are several companies operating in the area and the most important of them are the Enocell Mill and the Uimaharju Sawmill, which are both owned by Stora Enso. As a whole, there are currently approximately 350 people working in the area.</p> <p>Current situation and outlook for the future In 2019, the Enocell Mill is still producing bleached pulp from softwood and dissolving pulp from birch. Dissolving pulp is used in the production of textiles and other special products. There is an increasing interest in renewable and recyclable materials. Dissolving pulp can be used as an alternative material to replace cotton and different oil-based materials, such as polyester. Stora Enso is investing in the conversion of the Enocell Mill into a mill producing solely dissolving pulp. In the future, the mill will be able to produce both traditional pulp and renewable material, dissolving pulp, to be used by the textile industry, among others.</p>
52	Rantasalmi EIP	<p>The first planned ecopark in Finland. It is situated in the Rantasalmi station area, it hosts a cluster of mechanical wood processing companies, such as Rantasalmi Oy, Sil-Kas Oy, and Korpionhaka, which utilize wood-derived wastes for energy production. The project is coordinated by Rejlers Oy, the park also incorporates broader regional cooperation, including companies like Suur-Savon Sähkö Oy and Parlatuote Oy, expanding the network of resource and energy exchanges.</p>
53	ValuePark Schkopau	<p>The main objective of ValuePark® was to establish an integrated value-creating network of raw material suppliers, downstream investors and service providers so as to encourage benefits from the cost synergies and economies of scale of sharing services and resources. The ValuePark® is located in the small town of Schkopau (Germany). The main industrial activity in this town is the large chemical and plastics company Dow Olefinverbund GmbH, which manufactures polyolefins. The profile of its production as well as the excellent infrastructure, e.g. cheap pipeline transportation of raw materials from all over Germany made this enterprise the ideal anchor company, which attracts the other enterprises. ValuePark was established in 1998 and its area comprises of 150 ha. Currently, 13 German and international enterprises are involved in cooperation with Dow Olefinverbund GmbH. Various services such as counselling for planning and obtaining permits, a wastewater treatment plant, emergency services, analytical services, rail dispatching, and different utilities (i.e. water, cooling water, nitrogen, other industrial gases, natural gas) can be supplied by the anchor company. Owing to the idea of ValuePark® and the attractive conditions of development, the investors created 700 new jobs.</p>

54	Ponte a Egola APEA	It is an older and smaller industrial production system in Tuscany, which was established in 1970. As in the first case, the emergence of the brownfield EIP experimentation has been observed as a combination of top-down and self-organised approaches. The EIP experimentation has been highly influenced by the EMAS-certificated Tannery District to which Ponte a Egola pertains. Under the vision of the Tannery District, many efforts have been put into the recovery and reuse of by-products and the use of shared facilities. On the other hand, the top-down planned EEPA programme has also been followed for improving the green areas, waste management, shared infrastructure and services, and energy efficiency at the system level. The EEPA process started in 2013 and the qualification was obtained in 2016. It is the first and only certified EEPA in Tuscany.
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EIPs have been firstly classified according to their geographical location, considering the city, the country and the broader regional area in which they are established. The activation year and the number of resident companies have been also counted. Furthermore, government economic incentives such as tax reductions, funding and subsidies, have been identified where present. Additional relevant variables have been considered to compile a comprehensive overview of the enablers of EIPs, which are explained below.

- Depending on the **type of initiative**, EIPs have been classified as
Private – the park is owned by or/and it comprises only private enterprises,
Public – the park is owned by a public body, such as state or municipality,
Mixed – a combination of the abovementioned.
- Depending on the typology of the **industrial site**, a distinction was made between
Greenfield - completely new IP; and
Brownfield - existing IP in transition or already became EIP.
- Depending on the emerging condition, referred to as **network structure**, three modalities have been identified
Bottom-up - spontaneously created by the self-organisation of neighbour companies
Facilitated - designed and managed by a third-part (i.e. national or international programs, ICT based); and
Top-down - planned by the state or by other organisations.
- Depending on the **encompassed industrial sectors**, a preliminary differentiation was made between
Sector integrated - also called mixed parks, they involve multiple industrial sectors; and
Sector specific - parks with primarily one main sector or correlated sectors.

The following table summarises the results for each EIPs. Activation year and number of resident companies were not always possible to identify. Particularly, with regard to brownfield site, the year of creation of the industrial site is shown in brackets, whilst outside the parentheses the year of transition from IP to EIP is reported. Such transition is not always institutionally recognised (i.e., through the adherence to EIP programmes or certification schemes). For instance, self-organised systems emerge to tackle environmental restrictions or to gain competitiveness through the reduction of productive costs. In these cases, symbiotic exchanges emerged as nudge practice, rather than in an integrated and systemic manner, and they are not always tracked, making difficult to indicate the exact year of transition.

Table 5. Mapping EIPs main characteristics.

ID	NAME	COUNTRY	MACRO-REGION	ACTIVATION YEAR	N OF COMPANIES	TYPE OF INITIATIVE	INDUSTRIAL SITE	NETWORK STRUCTURE	TYPE OF EIP (ref industrial sector)	SPECIFIED	GOVERNMENT INCENTIVES
1	RETDA	China	Asia	1991	>165	Public	Brownfield	Top-down	Sector integrated		YES
2	HETDA	China	Asia	(1993) 2010	1200	Public	Brownfield	Top-down	Sector integrated		YES
3	SETDZ	China	Asia	(1988) 2014	121	Public	Brownfield	Top-down	Sector integrated		YES
4	QJIS	China	Asia	2006	ND	Public	Brownfield	Top-down	Sector integrated		YES
5	GUITANG GROUP	China	Asia	(1956) late '80	7	Public	Brownfield	Top-down	Sector specific	Sugar	YES
6	PINGDINGSHAN COAL MINING GROUP	China	Asia	(1954) '80	3 main	Public	Brownfield	Top-down	Sector specific	Mining and quarryng	YES
7	Lubei EIP	China	Asia	2002	>1000	Public	Brownfield	Top-down	Sector specific	Petrochemical	YES
8	SIP	Singapore	Asia	2002	>3000	Public	Brownfield	Top-down	Sector integrated		YES
9	TEDA	China	Asia	(1984) 2008	931	Public	Brownfield	Top-down	Sector integrated		YES
10	Gujiao EIP	China	Asia	2012	38	Public	Greenfield	Top-down	Sector specific	Petrochemical	YES
11	Yushen Industrial Park CISN	China	Asia	ND	ND	Public	Brownfield	Top-down	Sector specific	Petrochemical	YES

12	DALU IP – CISN	China	Asia	ND	ND	Public	Brownfield	Top-down	Sector specific	Petrochemical	YES
13	Lunan CISN	China	Asia	ND	ND	Public	Brownfield	Top-down	Sector specific	Petrochemical	YES
14	Kalundborg	Denmark	Europe	1972	16 + 3	Private	Greenfield	Bottom-up	Sector integrated		YES
15	Smilowo	Poland	Europe	(1982) late '90	13	Private	Brownfield	Facilitated	Sector specific	Agripark	NO
16	Linhai	Taiwan	Asia	1993	25	Mixed	Brownfield	Facilitated	Sector integrated		YES
17	Mongstad	Norway	Europe	ND	61	Mixed	Greenfield	Facilitated	Sector specific	Petrochemical	YES
18	Peterborough	UK	Europe	2015	3	Mixed	Brownfield	Facilitated	Sector integrated		YES
19	Rotterdam	Netherlands	Europe	1994	69	Mixed	Brownfield	Facilitated	Sector integrated		YES
20	Kwinana	Australia	Oceania	1940 (1991)	31	Private	Brownfield	Facilitated	Sector integrated		YES
21	Gladstone	Australia	Oceania	2004	8	Private	Brownfield	Facilitated	Sector specific	Mining and quarryng	NO
22	Mipo, Onsan	Korea	Asia	2005	30	Mixed	Brownfield	Facilitated	Sector integrated		YES
23	Kawasaki zero-emission industrial complex	Japan	Asia	1997	8	Public	Brownfield	Facilitated	Sector integrated		YES
24	Choctaw	USA	America	1995		Private	Brownfield	Bottom-up	Sector integrated		NO
25	Hull Cluster	UK	Europe	1960	10 main	Mixed	Brownfield	Facilitated	Sector integrated		YES
26	British Sugar	UK	Europe	1985	3	Private	Brownfield	Top-down	Sector specific	Agripark	NO

27	Campbell Industrial Park (AES network)	USA	America	(1958) 2005	11	Private	Brownfield	Top-down	Sector integrated		YES
28	Taranto	Italy	Europe	1960	10	Private	Brownfield	Bottom-up	Sector integrated		NO
29	Grangemouth	UK	Europe	1992	12	Mixed	Brownfield	Facilitated	Sector specific	Petrochemical	YES
30	AES Guyama	USA	America	2002	8	Mixed	Brownfield	Bottom-up	Sector integrated		YES
31	Barceloneta	USA	America	1978	14	Private	Brownfield	Bottom-up	Sector specific	Pharmaceutical	YES
32	Hartberg Ecopark	Austria	Europe	1997	30	Mixed	Greenfield	Facilitated	Sector integrated		YES
33	Händelö bioenergy complex	Sweden	Europe	1990	7	Mixed	Greenfield	Bottom-up	Sector integrated		YES
34	Stenungsund Industrial Park	Sweden	Europe	1970	5	Private	Greenfield	Bottom-up	Sector specific	Petrochemical	YES
35	Tra Noc IZ	Vietnam	Asia	2015	58	Mixed	Brownfield	Top-down	Sector integrated		YES
36	Biopark Terneuzen	Netherlands	Europe	2007	23	Private	Greenfield	Top-down	Sector specific	Agripark	YES
37	Harjavalta	Finland	Europe	1944	13	Private	Brownfield	Bottom-up	Sector specific	Mining and quarryng	YES
38	Bazancourt-Pomacle	France	Europe	1950	10	Private	Brownfield	facilitated	Sector specific	Agripark	Yes
39	Mönsterås	Sweden	Europe	1959	6	Private	Brownfield	Bottom-up	Sector specific	Wood-paper	NO
40	IPOS	Sweden	Europe	2006	20 (3 big)	Private	Greenfield	Top-down	Sector integrated		YES
41	Landsrkona	Sweden	Europe	2002	20+	Mixed	Brownfield	Facilitated	Sector integrated		YES

42	Sotenäs	Sweden	Europe	nd	10	Mixed	Brownfield	Facilitated	Sector specific	fishing industry	YES
43	Dunkirk	France	Europe	(1960) 2001	14	Private	Brownfield	Facilitated	Sector integrated		YES
44	Kouvola	Finland	Europe	1874	9	Private	Brownfield	Bottom-up	Sector specific	pulp and paper	YES
45	Relvão Eco Industrial Park	Portugal	Europe	2006	25	Mixed	Brownfield	Facilitated	Sector integrated		YES
46	Koekhoven	Belgium	Europe	2006	70	Private	Greenfield	Facilitated	Sector specific	Agripark	YES
47	Kansas city	USA	America	2011	9	Private	Brownfield	Facilitated	Sector specific	Metal	YES
48	Nanjangud Industrial Area	India	Asia		60	Private	Brownfield	Bottom-up	Sector integrated		NO
49	Kokkola Industrial Park	Finland	Europe	2006	20	Mixed	Brownfield	Facilitated	Sector specific	Petrochemical	YES
50	Kaiserbaracke	Belgium	Europe	2004	5	Mixed	Brownfield	Facilitated	Sector integrated		YES
51	Uimaharju Bioindustrial Area	Finland	Europe	1967	7	Private	Brownfield	Bottom-up	Sector specific	pulp and paper	YES
52	Rantasalmi EIP	Finland	Europe	2004	8	Mixed	Brownfield	Top-down	Sector specific	pulp and paper	YES
53	ValuePark Schkopau	Germany	Europe	1998	14	Private	Greenfield	Top-down	Sector specific	Petrochemical	YES
54	Ponte a Egola APEA	Italy	Europe	1970 (2013)	115	Private	Brownfield	Bottom-up	Sector specific	Tannery	YES

From a geographical perspective, the only continent not represented within the sample is Africa. No African EIP has been indeed included. Within the academic literature several examples related to EIP planning in South Africa, Egypt, and other Maghreb countries can be retrieved. However, they refer to theoretical cases which are not currently under implementation (ElMassah, 2018). The growing importance of IS is STILL testified by the wide diffusion of EIPs beyond the traditional western countries. For instance, China resulted to be the country most engaged in EIPs activities, representing 22% of the initiatives mapped within the sample. Considering the macro regions, Europe and Asia are the most represented continents, accounting respectively to 54% and 33% of the total mapped cases. In Europe, the majority of cases are located in northern countries; especially in Sweden (11%), and Finland (9%). Northern Europe has a long history of symbiotic activities, which can be dated back to the 1960s or earlier (Artola et al., 2018), whilst Asia has approached EIPs more recently. The ecological burdens caused by the rapid industrialisation in Asian countries might have emphasised the necessity to create more sustainable industrial systems, making IS a key strategy.

Considering the initiatives' nature, which can be either public, private or mixed initiatives, among the mapped EIPs private initiatives resulted the most frequent (43%). However, public EIPs represent the main EIP model in Asia, whereas most of the mapped cases resulted to be owned by the state or by other governmental bodies (i.e., municipalities). On the opposite side, European and American countries resulted to be more likely to promote private EIPs, and mixed EIPs. In this regard, if US EIPs are mainly private initiatives, in Europe mixed initiative represent a significant share (44%) of the total EU EIPs. Coherently government incentives, although being widespread, are more evident in Asia and Europe, whilst the complete absence of such incentives has been retrieved mainly in US, and Australian experiences.

Regarding to the physical industrial site, only 19% of the mapped EIPs are located in a greenfield, whilst the majority have emerged in brownfield. Greenfields are mainly distributed in the European territory and are particularly related to the establishment of petrochemical complexes and agriparks³, therefore industrial systems which highly rely on new cleaner technologies. The high presence of brownfield indicates that IS is often implemented as a strategy to shift toward a cleaner production system, rather than as an original business model.

Regarding the network structure, which can be conceived as the approach with which the EIP has emerged, there is no predominant approach. Bottom-up EIPs represent 24% of the sample, Facilitated 39%, and Top-down 37%. Considering the geographical distribution, results show that self-organised networks and facilitated networks are particularly diffused in western countries, especially in Europe, whilst top-down approaches are more adopted among Asian countries. This information is coherent with the overall national policies. As already mentioned, Asian countries had to face the environmental externalities caused by the rapid industrialisation (Domenech, 2021). Therefore, government bodies had planned in a top-down manner the establishment, or the transition, of EIPs. On the other side, the EIPs development in Europe has been slower and more embedded to the territory, partly due to the relocation of primary industries to third countries and the lack of dedicated mechanisms to plan IS (Neves et al., 2020). Bottom-up approaches indeed tend to create IS networks with a local focus, emphasising the importance of geographical proximity to ease collaboration.

From a sectoral perspective, the preliminary analysis shows that half of the sample is comprised by sector-specific EIPs, therefore industrial network encompassing one or few productive sectors. Among them, petrochemical EIPs are the most diffused, followed by agriparks, and industrial network linked to Pulp and Paper manufacturing. Agriparks are implemented in Europe and represent a new and innovative approaches to combine agriculture with biorefinery. In this regard, Netherlands is among the key players,

³ Agriparks are EIPs devoted to agricultural and biorefinery activities (Boons et al., 2015).

and several efforts to convert traditional greenhouses in agriparks are being made. Paper related EIPs are also distributed only within the European territory, particularly in northern countries, where the forestry industry has consistently constituted the primary driving force behind the local economy. Results of this descriptive univariate analysis are summarised in the figure below.

Figure 6. Summary of the results of the descriptive analysis of EIPs.

MAPPING REGIONAL IS – AN OVERVIEW

The research for EIPs case studies led to the identification of seven initiatives with a broader geographical scope. These cases represent regional IS, sometimes referred as to regional EIPs, namely symbiotic network established within wider territory than traditional parks. Table 6 lists regional symbiosis initiatives which fit the same inclusion criteria adopted for the mapping of EIPs (i.e., presence of symbiotic exchanges, secondary data related to MFA).

Table 6. Overview of mapped regional IS.

	NAME	BRIEF DESCRIPTION
1	Sarnia	<p>The Sarnia-Lambton Eco-Industrial Park, known as ‘Chemical Valley’, is an advanced example of industrial symbiosis. This industrial complex, active since the 1990s, includes some 19 chemical and petrochemical companies, including Dow Chemical Canada Inc., Bayer Rubber Inc., Nova Chemicals (Canada) Ltd. and Imperial Oil. The companies work together to optimise the use of resources and reduce environmental impact through these project: (1) power / steam cogeneration project; (2) use of desulphurized gypsum from power station in gypsum board plant; (3) lightweight Mineral aggregates; (4) energy from waste; (5) energy from post-consumer plastic resources; (6) co-product sulfuric acid.</p>
2	Styria	<p>Styria's industrial symbiosis complex comprises many companies in the same sector, including six cement factories, six paper factories, three used oil dealers, two power plants and two building material plants. This redundancy is necessary to meet the large demand for inputs and outputs of these companies. The diversity of sources ensures that the by-products and wastes of these companies are delivered to downstream companies that use these resources. This allows the downstream industries to withstand the impacts of changes in the production processes of upstream companies and vice versa, ensuring mutual stability. There are already established routes between cement and power plants, and new routes can be created to further improve the network.</p>
3	Jyväskylä	<p>The Jyväskylä industrial symbiosis complex, developed in the 1990s, represents a model of industrial ecology by integrating energy production and the utilisation of industrial and domestic waste. The system involves several companies and sectors, including the Rauhalahki combined heat and power plant (CHP) that produces electricity and heat using mainly sawmill waste, forest waste and peat. The Rauhalahki power plant supplies electricity to all residential, industrial and service sectors in Jyväskylä. In addition, waste heat from electricity production is used for district and industrial heating. The main enterprises involved include the Kangas Paper Mill, which receives industrial steam from the CHP plant, and the Plywood Mill in Säynätsalo, which supplies wood waste to the plant and receives electricity and heat in return. In addition, sawmills and regional forestry companies supply wood residues and forest waste as fuel. This integration of production systems and energy consumption significantly reduces the consumption of imported fossil fuels, thus decreasing GHG. The use of waste incineration ash for gardening and land construction projects highlights further reuse of waste materials, contributing to a more sustainable resource cycle.</p>

4	Forth valley region	<p>The industrial symbiosis complex in the Forth Valley region of Scotland comprises a large cluster of chemical and petrochemical industries located mainly in the Grangemouth area. This industrial symbiosis project has been developed since 1992 and involves major companies such as BP, Ineos, and Calor Gas, along with the support of local authorities such as Forth Valley College and Falkirk Council. The project began as a joint public-private initiative with a focus on improving resource efficiency and reducing waste. The main industrial symbiosis activities include the exchange of materials and by-products between companies, such as the use of fly ash from power plants in cement plants and the reuse of waste heat.</p>
5	Kymi EIP	<p>The studied symbiosis (situated in Kymenlaakso, South-Eastern Finland) contains five interconnected industrial facilities centered around a pulp and paper mill. This network mainly involves the UPM Kymmene Corporation's pulp and paper plant, a power plant using wood residues and sludge, three chemical plants and a municipal wastewater treatment plant. The pulp and paper mill was initially founded in 1872 by the Kymijoki River, evolving in symbiosis around 90'. Over time the symbiosis has extended to include chlorine dioxide, calcium carbonate and hydrogen peroxide plants, a power plant, and a landfill. In addition, the pulp and paper mill has incorporated power production, water purification and wastewater treatment systems, providing services for the industries and the municipality. The symbiosis produced 773 000 tons of products in 2005, of which 720 000 was paper (c.a. 7% of annual Finnish paper production).</p>
6	Kemi-Tornio	<p>The industrial symbiosis complex in the Kemi-Tornio region of Finnish Lapland was formally launched between 2001 and 2003. The project involves several key companies from the forestry, steel and mineral production sectors. The main participating industries include steel plants and chemical plants. The complex was facilitated by public and private organisations, with strong support from local and regional authorities. The forestry, paper, steel and mining industries work closely together to reuse industrial by-products, turning residues from one production into resources for another. The industrial ecosystem in the Kemi-Tornio region is dominated by large-scale industrial operations, such as the Outokumpu stainless steel plant, Metsä Group forestry industry plant, StoraEnso forestry industry plant and Outokumpu Kemi chrome mine. The Kemi unit of the Lapland University of Applied Sciences is the major educational and public-sector applied research institute in the Kemi-Tornio region. The vast majority of the R&D work takes place within Kemi-Tornio Industrial ecosystem companies.</p>

7	Altamira-Tampico	<p>The IS complex in the Altamira-Tampico industrial corridor formally began between 1997 and 1999, although the region had been home to industrial settlements since the 1960s. As the number of companies grew in the 1980s, mainly in the petrochemical sector, the need to manage the environmental impact emerged, leading to the formation of an industrial symbiosis network. It now involves more than 30 companies, including large international and national consortia such as BASF, DUPONT, Mexichem and ALFA, operating in sectors such as petrochemicals, plastics and chemicals. The Association of Industrialists of Southern Tamaulipas (AISTAC) played a crucial role in facilitating cooperation between the companies. Industrial symbiosis exchanges include the recovery of CO₂ for the production of carbonated beverages, the recovery of hydrochloric acid reused internally or sold for domestic and semi-industrial uses, and the use of waste polymer resins transformed into construction materials. Other initiatives include the cleaning and recycling of chemical containers classified as hazardous waste, the recovery of ferric chloride used as a coagulant in water treatment, and energy synergies, where residual natural gas is used for steam production shared between different companies.</p>
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Regional initiatives have been assessed with the same metrics adopted for EIPs, therefore considering the location, emergence, type of initiative, network, sectoral focus, government incentives etc, as shown in Table 7. The industrial site has not been classified, since the system boundaries of such initiatives go beyond a single industrial site.

Almost all the considered regional IS have been activated during the '90ies, except for Kymi EIP which has older roots that can be dated back to the last decade of the XIX century. Among the seven cases, five are located within the European territory, of which three in Finland, whilst the remaining are from Canada (Ontario) and Mexico (Altamira-Tampico).

Four out seven regional symbiosis have a mixed nature, whilst government incentives have favoured the establishment of IS activities in most of the cases.

There are no evidence of top-down planning of regional IS, instead such initiatives seems to emerged especially through facilitation or following a bottom-up approach. In wider area, facilitation indeed represent a key tool to favour the implementation of symbiotic activities, since the lack of geographical proximity hinders information exchanges, and, consequently, the possibility to cooperate.

Given the wide scope of those initiatives, most of them are sector integrated, hence they do not focus on specific productive chain. The three sector-specific IS are related to the petrochemical sector.

Figure 7 summarises the descriptive univariate analysis of the mapped regional IS cases.

Table 7. Overview of mapped Regional IS.

ID	NAME	REGION	COUNTRY	MACRO REGION	ACTIVATION YEAR	N OF COMPANIES	TYPE OF INITIATIVE	NETWORK STRUCTURE	TYPE OF EIP (ref industrial sector)	SPECIFIED	GOVERNMENT INCENTIVES
1	Sarnia	Sarnia (Ontario)	Canada	America	1995	19	Private	Bottom-up	Sector specific	Petrochemical	YES
2	Styria	Styria	Austria	Europe	1990	19	Private	Bottom-up	Sector integrated		NO
3	Jyväskylä	Jyvaskyla	Finland	Europe	1990	Not specified	Private	Facilitated	Sector integrated		YES
4	Forth valley region	Scotland	UK	Europe	1992	10	Mixed	Facilitated	Sector specific	Petrochemical	NO
5	Kymi EIP	Kymenlaakso	Finland	Europe	1874	5	Mixed	Bottom-up	Sector integrated		YES
6	Kemi-Tornio	Lapland	Finland	Europe	2001	7	Mixed	Facilitated	Sector integrated		YES
7	Altamira-Tampico	Altamira-Tampico	Mexico	America	1997	30	Mixed	Facilitated	Sector specific	Petrochemical	YES

Figure 7. Results of the descriptive analysis of the mapped Regional IS.

MAPPING THE RESIDUE EXCHANGES WITHIN EIPs AND REGIONAL IS

This section provided an in depth analysis of the productive sectors mainly involved in symbiotic exchanges. This is done by mapping the overall exchanges within the samples of both EIPs and Regional IS. Productive residues are identified, as well as productive sectors of origin and destination. In this regard, productive sectors have been identified by NACE codes.

The overall analysis results in the mapping of 836 symbiotic exchanges occurring within the EIPs and IS regional sample. A list with commonly exchangeable residues has been compiled based on the secondary data provided by the sample (Table 8), which resulted on the identification of 263 productive residues.

Table 8. List of exchanged productive residues within the sample.

	RESIDUE EXCHANGED	f	%
1	Steam	71	8,50%
2	Ashes	57	6,83%
3	Wastewater	45	5,39%
4	Heat	34	4,07%
5	Carbon dioxide CO ₂	27	3,23%
6	Sludge	27	3,23%
7	Biomass	26	3,11%
8	Bark and scrap wood	25	2,99%
9	Reclaimed water	21	2,51%
10	Water H ₂ O	17	2,04%
11	Hydrogen H ₂	14	1,68%
12	Residual oil	11	1,32%
13	Flue gas	9	1,08%
14	Miscellaneous inert waste	8	0,96%
15	Plastic residues	8	0,96%
16	Sawdust	8	0,96%
17	Carbon trioxide CO ₃	7	0,84%
18	Tyre shreds	7	0,84%
19	Alkali slag	6	0,72%
20	Ammonia NH ₃	6	0,72%
21	C&D waste	6	0,72%
22	Sulphur	6	0,72%
23	Sulphuric acid H ₂ SO ₄	6	0,72%
24	Vinasse	6	0,72%
25	Animal dejection	5	0,60%
26	Blast furnace slag	5	0,60%
27	Calcium carbonate CaCO ₃	5	0,60%
28	Condensate steam	5	0,60%
29	Ethylene	5	0,60%
30	FGD gypsum	5	0,60%
31	Hydrochloride HCl	5	0,60%
32	Nitrogen N ₂	5	0,60%
33	Carbide slag	4	0,48%
34	Chlorine Cl ₂	4	0,48%
35	Demineralised water	4	0,48%
36	Electricity	4	0,48%
37	Gypsum	4	0,48%
38	Hydrogen Peroxide H ₂ O ₂	4	0,48%
39	Lime klin dust	4	0,48%
40	Natural gas	4	0,48%
41	Sodium hydroxide NaOH	4	0,48%
42	Stillage	4	0,48%
43	Tunneling gangue	4	0,48%
44	Washed gangue	4	0,48%
45	Ammonium chloride solution	3	0,36%

46	Bauxite	3	0,36%
47	Boiler slag	3	0,36%
48	Carbon black	3	0,36%
49	Coal gangue	3	0,36%
50	Coal slime	3	0,36%
51	Digestate	3	0,36%
52	Fermentation residue	3	0,36%
53	Fibre sludges	3	0,36%
54	Jute sacks	3	0,36%
55	Lead slags	3	0,36%
56	Meat residues	3	0,36%
57	Metal scraps	3	0,36%
58	Molasses	3	0,36%
59	Riffler waste	3	0,36%
60	Solvents	3	0,36%
61	Steel slag	3	0,36%
62	Sulphur dioxide SO ₂	3	0,36%
63	Textile scraps	3	0,36%
64	Waste Paper	3	0,36%
65	Abrasives	2	0,24%
66	Aluminum slag	2	0,24%
67	Ammonium sulphate	2	0,24%
68	Argon	2	0,24%
69	Bagasse	2	0,24%
70	Black liquor	2	0,24%
71	Boiler fuel	2	0,24%
72	Cardboard	2	0,24%
73	Cinder sand	2	0,24%
74	Coke oven gas	2	0,24%
75	Crop residues	2	0,24%
76	Dust	2	0,24%
77	Ethanol	2	0,24%
78	Food grade alcohol	2	0,24%
79	Glucose syrup	2	0,24%
80	Iron residues	2	0,24%
81	Light hydrocarbons	2	0,24%
82	Magnesium sulfate MgSO ₄	2	0,24%
83	Manure pellets	2	0,24%
84	Methanol CH ₃ OH	2	0,24%
85	Mill scale	2	0,24%
86	Mother liquor	2	0,24%
87	Off-spec materials	2	0,24%
88	Oxygen O ₂	2	0,24%
89	Paper	2	0,24%
90	Phosphate PO ₄	2	0,24%
91	Plasticiser oil	2	0,24%
92	Pulp	2	0,24%

93	Refractory Bricks	2	0,24%
94	Residual resin	2	0,24%
95	Reverse osmosis water	2	0,24%
96	Rubber residues	2	0,24%
97	Sodium hydroxide (NaOH)	2	0,24%
98	Spent catalysts	2	0,24%
99	Spent lead acid batteries	2	0,24%
100	Spent oil	2	0,24%
101	Spent solvents	2	0,24%
102	Steel and Iron scraps	2	0,24%
103	Sugar beet substrates	2	0,24%
104	Thick brine	2	0,24%
105	Waste etching solution	2	0,24%
106	Waste ink	2	0,24%
107	Waste packaging	2	0,24%
108	Zinc powder and flakes	2	0,24%
109	Acid and solvent fraction	1	0,12%
110	Acids	1	0,12%
111	Activated carbon	1	0,12%
112	Activated sludge	1	0,12%
113	Alcohol residues	1	0,12%
114	Autoclave residue	1	0,12%
115	Batteries and oil filters	1	0,12%
116	Bioethanol	1	0,12%
117	Black glass	1	0,12%
118	Boiler blowdown	1	0,12%
119	Brine (seawater, sulfate ions)	1	0,12%
120	Broken rice	1	0,12%
121	Carniccio	1	0,12%
122	Caustic soda	1	0,12%
123	Cement klin dust	1	0,12%
124	Cereals	1	0,12%
125	Chemical butadiene	1	0,12%
126	Chips sawdust	1	0,12%
127	Chlorine Dioxide ClO ₂	1	0,12%
128	Chlorine Trioxide ClO ₃	1	0,12%
129	Citrus residues	1	0,12%
130	Clay oil	1	0,12%
131	Coal mine overburden	1	0,12%
132	Coal slag	1	0,12%
133	Coke	1	0,12%
134	Coke breeze	1	0,12%
135	Compressed air	1	0,12%
136	Copper residues	1	0,12%
137	Corn	1	0,12%
138	Crude benzol	1	0,12%
139	Crystal silicon	1	0,12%

140	Dissolving pulp	1	0,12%
141	Disulfuric Acid H ₂ SO ₇	1	0,12%
142	Electric Arc Furnace Reduction Slag	1	0,12%
143	Electric Arc Furnaces Dust	1	0,12%
144	Electric Arc Furnaces Oxiding Slag	1	0,12%
145	Electro-chemical waste	1	0,12%
146	Empty toner cartridges	1	0,12%
147	Excavated material	1	0,12%
148	Exhaust gas	1	0,12%
149	Exhausted Chrome Tanning production	1	0,12%
150	Expired bread	1	0,12%
151	FDG sludge	1	0,12%
152	Ferrous iron	1	0,12%
153	Filter sugarcane mud	1	0,12%
154	Flax waste	1	0,12%
155	Flour	1	0,12%
156	Fuel pellets	1	0,12%
157	Fumaric acid	1	0,12%
158	Galvanized plate scrap	1	0,12%
159	Gel coats	1	0,12%
160	Glass	1	0,12%
161	Glucose	1	0,12%
162	Glycerol	1	0,12%
163	Granular activated carbon (GAC)	1	0,12%
164	Green and clear glass	1	0,12%
165	Ground slag	1	0,12%
166	Hazardous waste	1	0,12%
167	Heavy ends	1	0,12%
168	Insulation material	1	0,12%
169	Isobutylene C ₄ H ₈	1	0,12%
170	Lead dust	1	0,12%
171	Log panels and floor board	1	0,12%
172	Magnesium oxide MgO	1	0,12%
173	Methyl Diethyl amine C ₅ H ₁₃ NO ₂	1	0,12%
174	Middings coal	1	0,12%
175	Mine water	1	0,12%
176	Molten aluminium	1	0,12%
177	Mycelium protein waste	1	0,12%
178	Nickel residues	1	0,12%
179	Ni-kivi	1	0,12%
180	Nitramine H ₂ N ₂ O ₂	1	0,12%
181	Nitrogen NO	1	0,12%
182	Odour	1	0,12%
183	Organic waste from a 1,4-butanediol	1	0,12%
184	Oxalic acid C ₂ H ₂ O ₄	1	0,12%
185	Ozone O ₃	1	0,12%
186	Pallets	1	0,12%

187	PCB	1	0,12%
188	Peroxymonosulfuric acid H_2SO_5	1	0,12%
189	Pharmaceutical waste	1	0,12%
190	Phosphorus gypsum and other ammonium phosphate products	1	0,12%
191	Pig manure	1	0,12%
192	Pine oil	1	0,12%
193	Pine oil pitch	1	0,12%
194	Plastic packaging	1	0,12%
195	Plastic pellet	1	0,12%
196	Polydrums	1	0,12%
197	Polyester resin	1	0,12%
198	Poultry litter	1	0,12%
199	Powder paint	1	0,12%
200	Prebaked anodes	1	0,12%
201	Precipitate	1	0,12%
202	Primary Liquid Fuel Steam	1	0,12%
203	Propylene	1	0,12%
204	Pulping chemicals	1	0,12%
205	Recovered lead	1	0,12%
206	Recovered monomer	1	0,12%
207	Red mud	1	0,12%
208	Residual crude mixture	1	0,12%
209	Residual hemicellulose	1	0,12%
210	Rice bran	1	0,12%
211	Salty gypsum product (with sulfate ions)	1	0,12%
212	Saturated brine	1	0,12%
213	Secondary brine (seawater, sulfate ions)	1	0,12%
214	Sewadge pellets	1	0,12%
215	Shredder residues	1	0,12%
216	Silica fume	1	0,12%
217	Sodium sulfate	1	0,12%
218	Soil	1	0,12%
219	Spent acid	1	0,12%
220	Spent activated carbon	1	0,12%
221	Spent grain	1	0,12%
222	Spent Organic Solvent	1	0,12%
223	Starch	1	0,12%
224	Steel wires	1	0,12%
225	Stone	1	0,12%
226	Sugarcane pith	1	0,12%
227	Sulphur slag	1	0,12%
228	Sulphuric Acid H_2SO_6	1	0,12%
229	Super sacks	1	0,12%
230	Tertiary brine (seawater, sulfate ions)	1	0,12%
231	Thiamine (vitamin B1)	1	0,12%
232	Titanium dioxide TiO_2	1	0,12%

233	Titanium gypsum	1	0,12%
234	Trioxidane H ₂ O ₃	1	0,12%
235	Waste clay	1	0,12%
236	Waste corn	1	0,12%
237	Waste edible oils	1	0,12%
238	Waste energy	1	0,12%
239	Waste gas	1	0,12%
240	Waste grain	1	0,12%
241	Waste MeOH	1	0,12%
242	Waste paper pulp (fine material)	1	0,12%
243	Waste steel/iron	1	0,12%
244	White liquor	1	0,12%
245	Wood pellets	1	0,12%
246	Yeast slurry	1	0,12%
247	Zinc residues	1	0,12%
248	Waste copper foil	1	0,12%
249	Waste PCB	1	0,12%
	Total	835	

As shown in Table 8, among the productive residues exchanged, the most frequent result to be utilities-related resources. Steam, wastewater and heat are among those exhibiting the higher frequency. Observing the first 10 most frequent exchanged residues figure also carbon dioxide, reclaimed water, and pure water. This kind of exchanges required geographical proximity, since these resources are not easy to stock and transport by trail or road. Indeed, they often necessitate ad hoc infrastructures to be transferred, such as pipelines, which by nature require local proximity. Industrial sectors engaged in such exchanged are several, since these kinds of resources are almost always necessary to run manufacturing activities. Of particular importance seems to be the exchange of steam between cogeneration power plant and non-metallic mineral manufacturing (i.e, manufacture of glass, clay building materials, cement and plaster, etc.) designated to the construction sector.

From a material perspective, the most exchanged resources result to be ashes and sludge, followed by general biomass and bark and wood. The exchange of ashes and sludges is well documented in the academic literature, testifying that the utilisation of these residues has a wide range of application with high TRLs. Considering the productive sectors associated with the *producer* and *utiliser* of the residues, most of the ashes originated from energy plants and are reutilised within the construction sector (non-metallic mineral manufacturing) where are mainly utilised as concrete filler, and alternative cement fibre. Sludge is mainly originated from wastewater treatment plant, and are particularly utilised in agriculture directly, as soil conditioner or mulch for landscaping, and indirectly, through the manufacture of fertiliser.

Generally speaking, the most involved productive sector in symbiotic activities result to be:

- On the producer side – energy power plant (D35), particularly thermal plant and cogeneration plant which account for 11% of the sample, manufacture of pulp and paper (C17.1) which represent 5% of the sample, wastewater treatment plant (E36, E37) (4,5%), followed by the petrochemical sector (C19.1, C20.11).
- On the utiliser side – the manufacture of construction materials, particularly in concrete, (C23) account for more than 10%, followed by energy power plant (D35) (9%), fertiliser manufacture (5%) and pulp and paper manufacture, which represent less than 5% of the sample.

Table 9 illustrates the trajectory of the residues between original and destination sectors, which are individuate with NACE codes, among each mapped EIPs.

Table 9. Productive sectors of origin and destination identified by NACE codes

PARK NAME	RESIDUE	PRODUCTIVE SECTOR OF ORIGIN (NACE)	PRODUCTIVE SECTOR OF DESTINATION (NACE)
RIZHAO	Textile scraps	C13 (13.1, 13.2, 13.3, 13.9) C14 (14.1, 14.2, 14.3)	C32.4
	Vinasse	C11.01	C20.15
	Vinasse	C11.02	C20.15
	Vinasse	C11.05	C20.15
	Vinasse	C20.14	C20.15
	Ashes	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Ashes	D35 (35.21 35.3)	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Ashes	D35 (35.21 35.3)	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Sludge	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)	C20.14, C20.15
	Sludge	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Sludge	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)	C20.15
	Sawdust	C16.1 C16.2	C20.15
	Bark and scrap wood	C16.1 C16.2	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)
	Bark and scrap wood	C16.1 C16.2	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Molasses	C10.81	C20.14
	Molasses	C10.81	C10, C11
	Metal scraps	C27.11	C24.5
	Biomass	A3 (3.1, 3.2)	C20.20
	Carbon dioxide CO ₂	C11.05	C11.05
	Carbon trioxide CO ₃	C11.05	C10
	Clay oil	C10.6 (10.61, 10.62)	C23.3
	Waste clay	C23.3	C20.15
	Coal slag	D35 (35.21 35.3)	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Citrus residues	C20.20	C10.91
	Condensate steam	C10.41	D35 (35.21, 35.3)
	Steam	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)	A3.21 A3.22
	Sludge	E36, E37	E36, E37
Reclaimed water	E36, E38	D35 (35.21, 35.3)	
Reclaimed water	E36, E39	C24 (24.1, 24.2, 24.3, C24.52)	
HEFEI	Ashes	D35 (35.21 35.3)	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Ashes	C22.11	C23
	Crop residues	A1 (1.1, 1.2)	C20.14 D35.21
	Crop residues	A1 (1.1, 1.2)	C22.11
	Iron residues	C27.11	C24.5
	Steel and Iron scraps	C29.1	C29 (29.2, 29.3)
	Steel and Iron scraps	C29.1	N82.9 C10
	Steam	D35 (35.21 35.3)	C29.1

	Steam	D35 (35.21 35.3)	C29.2, C29.3
	Steam	D35 (35.21 35.3)	ND
	Steam	D35 (35.21 35.3)	ND
SHENYANG	FGD gypsum	D35 (35.11, 35.21 35.3)	C23.6
	Ashes	D35 (35.11, 35.21 35.3)	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Steam	D35 (35.11, 35.21 35.3)	C20
	Steam	D35 (35.11, 35.21 35.3)	C10, C11
	Steam	D35 (35.11, 35.21 35.3)	C24.5 (24.51, 24.52, 24.53)
	Activated carbon	C29.1	C10, C11
	Spent activated carbon	C10, C11	C29.1
	Mycelium protein waste	C10, C11	C10.91
	Hydrochloride HCl	C21 (21.1, 21.2)	C29.1
	Oxalic acid C ₂ H ₂ O ₄	D35 (35.11, 35.21 35.3)	C20
	Sodium sulfate	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)	C23
	Mother liquor	D35 (35.11, 35.21 35.3)	C20.15
	Animal dejection	A1 (1.4, 1.5)	C20.15 C20.20
	Chlorine Cl ₂	C20	C20.16
	Carbide slag	D35 (35.11, 35.21 35.3)	C20
Biomass	C10, C11	C20.15	
QIJANG	FGD gypsum	D35.11	C23.6
	FGD gypsum	D35.11	C20.15
	Prebaked anodes	D35 (35.21 35.3)	C27.3
	Molten aluminium	C23.51	C27.3
	Aluminum slag	C23.51	C23.53
	Nitramine H ₂ N ₂ O ₂	D35.11	C20.15
	Reclaimed water	E36, E37	D35 (35.11, 35.3)
	Ashes	D35 (35.11, 35.3)	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Ashes	D35 (35.21 35.3)	C23
	Heat	D35 (35.11, 35.3)	ND
	Heat	D35 (35.21 35.3)	ND
GUITANG	Molasses	C10.81	C20.14
	Alcohol residues	C20.14	C20.15
	Bagasse	C10.81	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)
	Bagasse	C10.81	D35 (35.21, 35.3)
	White liquor	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)
	Black liquor	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)	C20 (20.13, 20.14)
	Sludge	C20 (20.13, 20.14)	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Carbon dioxide CO ₂	C10.81	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Filter sugarcane mud	C10.81	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)

	Sugarcane pith	C10.81	D35 (35.21, 35.3)
	Flue gas	D35 (35.21 35.3)	C20.11
	Ashes	D35 (35.21 35.3)	C20.15
	Ashes	C10.81	C20.15
	Coal slime	B5 (5.1, 5.2)	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Ashes	B5 (5.1, 5.2)	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
PINGMEI	Coal gangue	B5 (5.1, 5.2)	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Methanole CH ₃ OH	C19 (19.10, 19.20)	C20
LUBEI	Brine (seawater, sulfate ions)	A3.21	C20.13
	Secondary brine (seawater, sulfate ions)	C20.13	C23.52
	Tertiary brine (seawater, sulfate ions)	C23.52	C20.15
	Wastewater	C23.52	B8.93
	Wastewater	A3.21	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Saturated brine	C23.52	C20 (20.13, 20.14)
	Chlorine Cl ₂	C20 (20.13, 20.14)	C20.13
	Salty gypsum product (with sulfate ions)	C23.52	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Sulphur dioxide SO ₂	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)	C20.2, C20.5
	Ashes	D35 (35.11, 35.21 35.3)	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Sulphur slag	C20.15	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Phosphorus gypsum and other ammonium phosphate products	C20.15	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Alkali slag	C20.13	C24.42
	Red mud	B5 (5.1, 5.2)	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Sulphuric acid H ₂ SO ₄	C20.2, C20.5	C24.41, C24.53
	Sulphuric acid H ₂ SO ₄	C20.2, C20.5	C20.15
	Hydrochloride HCl	C20 (20.13, 20.14)	C24.41, C24.53
	Phosphate PO ₄	C20.15	C20.15
	Phosphate PO ₄	C20.15	A8.99
	Ferrous iron	C24.41, C24.53	C27.2
	Titanium dioxide TiO ₂	C24.41, C24.54	C27.2
	Titanium gypsum	C24.41, C24.55	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Water H ₂ O	D35 (35.11, 35.21 35.3)	C20.13
	Steam	D35 (35.11, 35.21 35.3)	C24.42
	Steam	D35 (35.11, 35.21 35.3)	C23.52
SIP	Waste copper foil	C24.44	E39
	Sludge	C24.44	E39
	PCB	C26.11	C27.3
	Sludge	C26.11	E39

	Waste PCB	C26.11	E39
	Waste etching solution	C26.11	E39
	Waste etching solution	C26.11	E39
	Electro-chemical waste	C26.11	C20
TEDA	Wastewater	E36	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Steam	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	E36
	Steam	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	ND
	Condensate steam	ND	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Ashes	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	E39, N81.3
	Ashes	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Reclaimed water	E36, E37	ND
	Reclaimed water	E36, E37	C23
	Reclaimed water	E36, E37	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Galvanized plate scrap	C29.1	C29.1
	Sludge	C29.1	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Spent lead acid batteries	C27.3	C23.43
	Spent lead acid batteries	C27.2	C23.43
	Lead slags	C27.3	C23.43
	Lead slags	C29.1	C23.43
	Lead slags	E38.32, C24.43, 24.53	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Carbon black	C19.20	C29 (29.2, 29.3)
	Rubber residues	C29 (29.2, 29.3)	C20.17
	Fermentation residue	C11 (11.01, 11.02, 11.03, 11.05, 11.06)	E39, N81.3
	Fermentation residue	C11 (11.01, 11.02, 11.03, 11.05, 11.06)	C20.15 C20.20
	Bark and scrap wood	C31	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Dust	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	B6.2, C23.52
	Thick brine	E36	C20.13
	Thick brine	E36	E36
	Mother liquor	C10.84	C20
	Sludge	C21 (21.1, 21.2)	C20.15
	Sludge	C21 (21.1, 21.2)	E39, N81.3
Alkali slag	C20 (20.13, 20.14)	E39, N81.3	
GUIJIAO	Coal gangue	B5 (5.1, 5.2)	C19 (19.10, 19.20)
	Natural gas	B5 (5.1, 5.2)	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Coal slime	B5 (5.1, 5.2)	C19.10
	Coke oven gas	C19.10	C20.15
	Coke breeze	C19.11	C23.52
	Coke	C19.12	C20.16
	Ashes	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	B5.1
	Ashes	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	C24.42

	Ashes	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Carbide slag	C23.52	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
YUSHEN CISN	Tunneling gangue	B5 (5.1, 5.2)	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Coal gangue	C19.10	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Washed gangue	C19.10	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Ashes	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	C20.11
	FGD gypsum	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	C23
	Boiler slag	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	C23
	Ashes	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Crude benzol	C19.10	C19.20
	Sulphur	C19.10	C20
	Thiamine (vitamin B1)	C19.10	C20
	Carbide slag	C20.16	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Carbide slag	C19.10	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	C&D waste	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65) F43.11, 43.12	C20.2
	C&D waste	F43.11, 43.12	C20.5
	Plastic residues	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)	C20.16
	Textile scraps	C13 (13.1, 13.2, 13.3, 13.9) C14 (14.1, 14.2, 14.3)	C23 (23.2, 23.3, 23.4)
	Metal scraps	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	C23.49
	Crystal silicon	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	C23.49
	Carbon dioxide CO ₂	C19.10	C20.11
	Sulphur dioxide SO ₂	C20.14	C20.11
	Nitrogen NO	C20.14	C20.11
	Ammonia NH ₃	C20.14	C20.15
	Ammonia NH ₃	C20.14	C13
Ammonia NH ₃	C20.14	C22.1	
DALU	Tunneling gangue	B5 (5.1, 5.2)	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Washed gangue	C19.10	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Ashes	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	C24.42
	Ashes	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Boiler slag	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	FGD Gypsum	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Ashes	C19 (19.10, 19.20)	C23
LUNAN	Bauxite	B5 (5.1, 5.2)	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Bauxite	B8 (8.1, 8.9)	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)

	Mine water	B5 (5.1, 5.2)	E36, E37
	Tunneling gangue	B5 (5.1, 5.2)	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Tunneling gangue	B5 (5.1, 5.2)	E39
	Washed gangue	C19.10	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Washed gangue	C19.10	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Coal slime	C19.10	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Middings coal	C19.10	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Ashes	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Boiler slag	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Ashes	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Ashes	C19 (19.10, 19.20)	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Alkali slag	C19 (19.10, 19.20)	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
KALUNDBORG	Waste gas	C19.20	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Wastewater	C19.20	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Wastewater	C19.20	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Steam	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	C19.20
	Steam	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	D35 (35.21, 35.3)
	Heat	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	A1 (1.1, A1.2, A1.3)
	Gypsum	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	C23.52
	Sulphur	C19.20	C20.15
	Sulphur	D35.21	C20.15
	Biomass	A1 (1.1, 1.2) A2 (2.1, 2.2, 2.3)	C20.14 D35.21
	Biomass	A2 (2.1, 2.2)	C20.14 D35.21
	Residual hemicellulose	C20.14 D35.21	C21
	Biomass	C10.6	D35.21
	Biomass	C20.14 D38.21	D35.21
	Yeast slurry	C21 (21.1, 21.2)	D35.21
	SMILOWO	Pig manure	A1.46
Meat residues		C10.1	A10.9 (10.91, 10.92)
Meat residues		C10.1	C20.14 D35.21
Meat residues		A1.47	C20.15
Natural gas		C10.1	C10.11, C10.41
Steam		D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	C10.11, C10.41
Ashes		D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	C20.15
Ashes		D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	A10.9 (10.91, 10.92)
Odour		C10.11, C10.41	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
Waste grain		C10.61	C10.91

LINHAI	Coke oven gas	C24 (24.1, 24.2, 24.3, C24.52)	C19 (19.10, 19.20)
	Steam	C24 (24.1, 24.2, 24.3, C24.52)	C19 (19.10, 19.20)
	Steam	C24 (24.1, 24.2, 24.3, C24.52)	C20
	Steam	C24 (24.1, 24.2, 24.3, C24.52)	C25.1
	Steam	C24 (24.1, 24.2, 24.3, C24.52)	C24
	Argon	C20	C24 (24.1, 24.2, 24.3, C24.52)
	Argon	C24 (24.1, 24.2, 24.3, C24.52)	C24
	Hydrogen H ₂	C19 (19.10, 19.20)	C24 (24.1, 24.2, 24.3, C24.52)
	Hydrogen H ₂	G47.3	C24 (24.1, 24.2, 24.3, C24.52)
	Nitrogen N ₂	C24 (24.1, 24.2, 24.3, C24.52)	C19 (19.10, 19.20)
	Nitrogen N ₂	C24 (24.1, 24.2, 24.3, C24.52)	C20
	Aluminum slag	C24	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)
	Electric Arc Furnaces Dust	C24	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)
	Electric Arc Furnaces Oxidizing Slag	C24	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)
	Electric Arc Furnace Reduction Slag	C24	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)
	Alkali slag	C20	C19 (19.10, 19.20)
	Dust	C24	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)
	Spent Organic Solvent	C24	E39
	MONGSTAD	Wastewater	C19.20
Wastewater		C19.20	C20.16
Wastewater		C19.20	ND
Hydrogen H ₂		C20.11	C19.20
Hydrogen H ₂		C20.11	C24 (24.1, 24.2, 24.3, C24.52)
Sludge		A3 (3.1, 3.2)	D35.21
Biomass		A3.2	D35.21
Plastic residues		C20.16, C20.17	C20.16
Plastic residues		C13 (13.1, 13.2, 13.3, 13.9) C14 (14.1, 14.2, 14.3) C20.16	C20.16
Plastic residues		N82.9	C20.16
Recovered monomer		C20.16	C19.20
Carbon dioxide CO ₂		C19.20	E39
Carbon trioxide CO ₃		E39	C20.16, C20.17
	Jute sacks	A1.27 C10.83	A2

PETERBOROUGH	Jute sacks	A1.27 C10.83	C14.1
	Jute sacks	A1.27 C10.83	F42.91
ROTTERDAM HARBOR	Biomass	A1 (1.1, 1.2) C10 (10.3, 10.6)	D35.21
	Biomass	A1 (1.1, 1.2) C10 (10.3, 10.6)	C20.1 (20.14, 20.16)
	Biomass	A1 (1.1, 1.2) C10 (10.3, 10.6)	C20.15 C20.20
	Biomass	A1 (1.1, 1.2) C10 (10.3, 10.6)	C20.14; C20.15
	C&D waste	F43.11, 43.12	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Carbon dioxide CO ₂	C19.20	A1 (1.13, 1.22, 1.23, 1.24, 1.27, 1.28)
	Carbon trioxide CO ₃	C20.11	C20.17
	Steam	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	C20.17
	Steam	C20.16	C20.17
	Steam	C20.17	C20
	Steam	C20.17	C20.6
	Water H ₂ O	C20.17	C20.16
	Water H ₂ O	C20.17	C20.11
	Water H ₂ O	C20.17	C20
	Water H ₂ O	C20.17	C20.6
	Heat	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	A3.2
	KWINANA	Spent catalysts	C19.20
Hydrogen H ₂		C19.20	C20.11
Hydrogen H ₂		C19.20	C24.45
Hydrogen H ₂		C20.11	C24.45
Hydrogen H ₂		C24.45	C20.15
Hydrogen H ₂		C20.15	C20.11
Hydrogen H ₂		C20.11	D35 (35.21, 35.3)
Carbon dioxide CO ₂		C24.45	C20.11
Carbon dioxide CO ₂		C24.45	C20.15
Carbon dioxide CO ₂		C20.15	C20.11
Carbon dioxide CO ₂		C20.15	C24.42
Carbon dioxide CO ₂		C20.11	C24.42
Carbon dioxide CO ₂		C20.11	D35 (35.21, 35.3)
Biomass		C24.42	A1.49
Bauxite		C24.42	E36, E37
Sludge		E36, E37	A1.3
Sulphur		C19.20	C24.45
Sulphur		C19.20	C20.13
Sulphur		C24.45	A7.29
Nickel residues		C24.45	B5, B7, B8, E39
Ammonium sulphate		C24.45	C20.15
Ammonium sulphate	C24.45	C20.15	

Ashes	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
Gypsum	C20.15	C24.42
Methyl Diethyl amine C ₅ H ₁₃ NO ₂	C20.15	C19.20
Coal mine overburden	B5 (5.1, 5.2)	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
Spent catalyts	C19.20	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
Lime klin dust	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)	C24.1
Lime klin dust	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)	C23 (23.20, 23.52)
Hydrochloride HCl	C23 (23.20, 23.52)	C20.13
Ammonium chloride solution	C23.3	B7.2
Ammonium chloride solution	C23.3	C20.13
Ammonium chloride solution	C20.13	C23.99
Sulphuric acid H ₂ SO ₄	C20.13	C20 (20.13, 20.14)
Sulphuric acid H ₂ SO ₄	C20 (20.13, 20.14)	C20.13
Silica fume	C24.53	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
C&D waste	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65) F43.11, 43.12	C16.22, C16.23
Cardboard	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)	C17.12, C23.99
Blast furnace slag	C23.99	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
Steam	C24.10	C20.11
Steam	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	C23 (23.20, 23.52)
Steam	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	C19.20
Steam	C23 (23.20, 23.52)	C20 (20.13, 20.14)
Reclaimed water	E36, E37	C23 (23.20, 23.52)
Reclaimed water	E36, E37	C20.15
Reclaimed water	E36, E37	C19.20
Reclaimed water	E36, E37	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
Water H ₂ O	C23 (23.20, 23.52)	C20 (20.13, 20.14)
Reverse osmosis water	C23 (23.20, 23.52)	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
Wastewater	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	C23 (23.20, 23.52)
Wastewater	C20 (20.13, 20.14)	C23 (23.20, 23.52)
Wastewater	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	C19.20
Wastewater	C20.13	C20.15
Wastewater	C19.20	C20.15
Demineralised water	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	C20.15
Demineralised water	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	D35 (35.21, 35.3)

	Boiler blowdown	D35 (35.21 35.3)	D35 (35.21, 35.3)
	Flue gas	C19.20	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Electricity	C23 (23.20, 23.52)	C20 (20.13, 20.14)
	Electricity	C24.42	C20.11
	Reclaimed water	E36, E37	C24.42
GLADSTONE	Ashes	D35 (35.11, 35.21 35.3)	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Caustic soda	C24.42	C24.42
	Ashes	C24.42	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Tyre shreds	E38.12	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Solvents	E38.12	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Reclaimed water	E36 E37	C24.42
MIPO	Wastewater	C20.16, C20.17	E39
	Steam	E39	C20.16, C20.17
	Steam	E39	C20.10
	Steam	C20.16, C20.17	C20
	Steam	E38.2	C20
	Steam	C20 (20.1, 20.3, 20.4, 20.6)	C20.10, C22.1
	Steam	C24.44	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)
	Steam	C24.43	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)
	Steam	E38.21	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)
	Zinc residues	C24.44	C24.43
	Copper residues	C24.43	C24.44
	Waste MeOH	C27.3	C24.45
	Organic waste from a 1,4-butanediol	C20.17	E36, E37
	Ammonia NH ₃	E36, E37	E36, E37
	Calcium carbonate CaCo ₃	C24 (24.1, 24.2, 24.3, C24.52)	C24.4 (24.43, 24.44, 24.45)
	Magnesium oxide MgO	C24 (24.1, 24.2, 24.3, C24.52)	C24.4 (24.43, 24.44, 24.45)
	Magnesium sulfate MgSO ₄	C23.99	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)
	Magnesium sulfate MgSO ₄	C23.99	C21 (21.1, 21.2)
	Residual oil	C20.16, C20.17	C23.52
	Residual oil	C20	C23.52
	Residual oil	C29.1	C23.52
	Residual oil	C30.11	C23.52
	Zinc powder and flakes	C24-43	C20.3
	Zinc powder and flakes	C24, C25	C27.3
	Carbon dioxide CO ₂	C24.43	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)
	Activated sludge	C19.20	E38
CHOCTAW	Tyre shreds	E38.32	C22.11
	Tyre shreds	C22.11	C20.17
	Carbon Black	C22.11	E38.32
	Carbon Black	C20.17	C22.1 (22.11, 22.19)
	Plasticiser oil	C22.11	C20.16

	Plasticiser oil	C20.17	C22.11
	Steel wires	C22.11	C24 (24.1, 24.2, 24.3, C24.52)
	Empty toner cartridges	C38.12	E38.32
	Reclaimed water	E36, E37	E39, N81.3
	Reclaimed water	E36, E37	C22.11
	Reclaimed water	E36, E37	A1 (1.13, 1.22, 1.23, 1.24, 1.27, 1.28)
	Reclaimed water	E36, E37	C20.16
	Heat	C22.11	A1 (1.13, 1.22, 1.23, 1.24, 1.27, 1.28)
	Heat	C20.17	C22.11
HULL	Primary Liquid Fuel Steam	C20	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Acid and solvent fraction	C20	C20.3
	Biomass	C20	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Biomass	C10.2	C10.91
	Biomass	C10.2	A1 (1.1, 1.2, 1.61)
	Calcium carbonate CaCo ₃	B8.91	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Cement klin dust	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)	C23.99
	Waste edible oils	C10.2	C20.20
	Hydrogen H ₂	C20	C19.20
	Gypsum	C20	C23.62
	Sawdust	C31	A1 (1.1, 1.2, 1.61)
BRITISH SUGAR	Soil	C10.81	E39, N81.3
	Stone	C10.81	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Pulp	C10.81	C10.91
	Lime klin dust	C23.52	C10.81
	Precipitate	C10.81	A1 (1.1, 1.2, 1.61)
	Steam	D35 (35.11, 35.21 35.3)	C10.81
	Heat	C10.81	C10.81
	Heat	C10.81	A1.13
	Flue gas	D35 (35.11, 35.21 35.3)	A1.13
	Residual resin	C10.81	A1.13
	Residual resin	C10.81	C10.91
	Vinasse	C10.81	C10.91
	Carbon dioxide CO ₂	C10.81	A11 (11.04, 11.07)
	Carbon trioxide CO ₃	C10.81	C32.99
	Bioethanol	C10.81	H49.3
CAMPBELL	Ashes	D35 (35.11, 35.21 35.3)	B8, E39
	Ashes	D35 (35.11, 35.21 35.3)	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Ashes	D35 (35.11, 35.21 35.3)	B8, E39

	Ashes	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	E39
	Reverse osmosis water	E36, E37	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Water H2O	C19.20	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Steam	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	C19.20
	Tyre shreds	E39	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Residual oil	E39	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Granular activated carbon (GAC)	C19.20	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
TARANTO	Demineralised water	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	C19.20
	Demineralised water	C24 (24.1, 24.2, 24.3, C24.52)	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Steam	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	C19.20
	Steam	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	C24 (24.1, 24.2, 24.3, C24.52)
	Water H2O	C19.20	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Condensate steam	C19.20	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Exhaust gas	C24 (24.1, 24.2, 24.3, C24.52)	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Blast furnace slag	C24 (24.1, 24.2, 24.3, C24.52)	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Mill scale	C24 (24.1, 24.2, 24.3, C24.52)	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Ashes	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Ashes	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)	C23
	C&D waste	F43.11, 43.12	E23.7
	C&D waste	F43.11, 43.12	C23
	Vinasse	A1.21	C11.02
	Wastewater	C10.41	A1 (1.1, 1.2, 1.61)
GRANGEMOUTH	Heavy ends	C19.20, C20.16, C20.17	C19.20
	Steam	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	C19.20
	Steam	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	C20.16
	Steam	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	C20
	Steam	C20	C20.2
	Off-spec materials	C19.20	C20
	Off-spec materials	C22.2	C20.16
	Compressed air	C20.11	C19.20
	Nitrogen N ₂	C20.11	C19.20
	Sludge	C19.20	C20.15
AES	Reclaimed water	E36, E37	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Wastewater	C21 (21.1, 21.2)	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)

	Steam	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	C20
	Ashes	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	E39
	Ashes	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	E39
	Ashes	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	E39
	Ashes	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	C23
	Condensate steam	C20	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
BARCELONETA	Sludge	E36, E37	A1.19
	Wastewater	C21 (21.1, 21.2)	E36, E37
		C21 (21.1, 21.2)	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Fermentation residue	C21 (21.1, 21.2)	C10.91
	Pharmaceutical waste	C21 (21.1, 21.2)	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Steam	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	C21 (21.1, 21.2)
	Spent solvents	C21 (21.1, 21.2)	C20.12
	Spent solvents	C21 (21.1, 21.2)	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Animal dejection	A1 (1.4, 1.5)	A1 (1.1, 1.2, 1.61)
	Rice bran	A1.12 C10.6	C10.91
Broken rice	A1.12 C10.6	C11.05	
HARTBERG	Waste Paper	I56.10	C17.12, C23.99
	Waste Paper	J58.1	C17.12, C23.99
	Waste Paper	I59.14	C17.12, C23.99
	Insulation material	C17.12	C16.4
	Natural gas	D35.21	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Heat	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	C17.12, C23.99
	Heat	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	D35.21
HANDELO	Bark and scrap wood	C16.10	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Bark and scrap wood	A2 (2.1, 2.2)	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Biomass	A2 (2.1, 2.2)	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Cereals	A1.12 C10.6	C20.14 D35.21
	Expired bread	C10.7 G47.24	C20.14 D35.21
	Stillage	C20.14	C10.91
	Stillage	C20.14	D35.21
	Digestate	D35.21	D35.21
	Digestate	D35.21	A1 (1.13, 1.22, 1.23, 1.24, 1.27, 1.28)
	Digestate	D35.21	A1 (1.13, 1.22, 1.23, 1.24, 1.27, 1.28)
	Steam	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	C20.14 D35.21
	Condensate steam	C20.14	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Heat	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	ND

	Ethanol	C20.14	D38.21
	Glycerol	D38.21	D35.21
	Carbon dioxide CO ₂	C20.14	C20
STENUNGSUN D	Flue gas	C19.20	C20.16 C22.2
	Flue gas	C19.1	C20.13
	Flue gas	C19.1	C20.11
	Flue gas	C19.1	C20
	Hydrogen H ₂	C20.16	C19.1
	Hydrogen H ₂	C19.1	C20
	Natural gas	C19.1	C20
	Ethylene	C19.20	C20.16 C22.2
	Ethylene	C19.1	C20.13
	Ethylene	C19.1	C20.11
	Ethylene	C19.1	C20
	Propylene	C19.1	C20
	Steam	C19.20	C20.16 C22.2
	Steam	C20.16	C19.1
	Steam	C20.16	D35 (35.21, 35.3)
	Steam	C20.11	C20.11
	Steam	C20	D35 (35.21, 35.3)
	TRA NOC IZ	Biomass	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
Waste steel/iron		E38.12	C24 (24.1, 24.2, 24.3, C24.52)
Steam		C20.15	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)
Steam		C20.15	C10.91
Steam		C20.15	C20.15
Wastewater		ND	E36, E37
Wastewater		E36, E37	ND
Wastewater		C11 (11.04, 11.07)	E36, E37
Wastewater		C11.05	E36, E37
Wastewater		C10.5 (10.51, 10.52) A1.41	E36, E37
TERNEUZEN	Biomass	A1 (1.1, 1.2, 1.4, 1.5)	D35 (35.21, 35.3)
	Biomass	C20.14 D35.21	D35 (35.21, 35.3)
	Biomass	D35 (35.21 35.3)	D35 (35.21, 35.3)
	Starch	C10.6	C20.14 D35.21
	Carbon dioxide CO ₂	C20.15	A1 (1.1, 1.2, 1.61)
	Heat	C20.15	A1 (1.13, 1.22, 1.23, 1.24, 1.27, 1.28)
	Heat	D35 (35.21 35.3)	A1 (1.13, 1.22, 1.23, 1.24, 1.27, 1.28)
	Wastewater	B8 (8.1, 8.9)	E36, E37
	Wastewater	D35 (35.21 35.3)	E36, E38
	Wastewater	C20.15	E36, E39
	Wastewater	A1 (1.1, 1.2, 1.4, 1.5)	E36, E40
	Wastewater	C20.14	C10 C11

	Reclaimed water	E36, E37	A1 (1.13, 1.22, 1.23, 1.24, 1.27, 1.28)
	Steam	C20.14	C10 C11
HARJAVALTA	Hydrogen H ₂	C20.11	C24.45
	Nitrogen N ₂	C20.11	C24.44
	Nitrogen N ₂	C20.11	C24.45
	Oxygen O ₂	C20.11	C24.44
	Ozone O ₃	C20.11	C24.45
	Ammonia NH ₃	C20.2, C20.5	C24.45
	Ni-kivi	C24.44	C24.45
	Autoclave residue	C24.45	C24.44
	Waste energy	C24.44	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Steam	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	C20.11
BAZANCOURT	Sugar beet substrates	C10.81	C20.14 D35.21
	Sugar beet substrates	C10.81	C20.14
	Food grade alcohol	C20.14 D35.21	C20.4
	Food grade alcohol	C20.14 D35.21	C20.41
	Stillage	C10.81	C20.14 D35.21
	Stillage	C10.81	C20.15
	Flour	C20.14 D35.21	C10.62
	Glucose syrup	C10.62	C20.14 D35.21
	Glucose syrup	C10.62	C20.14
	Glucose	C10.62	C20.14
	Carbon dioxide CO ₂	C20.14 D35.21	C20.11
Carbon trioxide CO ₃	C20.11	C20.14	
MONSTERAS	Bark and scrap wood	C16.10	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)
	Sawdust	C16.10	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)
	Methanole CH ₃ OH	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)	C20.14 D35.21
	Bark and scrap wood	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)	C16.29
	Pine oil	C16.10	D38.21
	Steam	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)	C16.1
	Steam	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)	C16.29
	Electricity	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)	C16.1
	Electricity	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)	C16.29
	Heat	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)	ND
IPOS	Sludge	E36, E37	A1 (1.1, 1.2, 1.61)
	Sludge	E36, E37	ND
	Reclaimed water	E36, E37	D35 (35.11, 35.3)
	Wastewater	D35 (35.11, 35.3)	Q86.1
	Ashes	D35 (35.11, 35.3)	D35 (35.21, 35.3)
	Heat	C20	D35 (35.21, 35.3)
	Heat	D35 (35.11, 35.3)	D35 (35.21, 35.3)
	Heat	E36, E37	D35 (35.21, 35.3)
	Hydrogen Peroxide H ₂ O ₂	C20	C20
	Hydrogen Peroxide H ₂ O ₂	C20	C20

	Sulphuric acid H ₂ SO ₄	C20	C20
	Hydrochloride HCl	C20	C20
LANDSKRONA	Heat	E38.22	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Heat	E38.32, C24.43, 24.53	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Wastewater	C23.19	N82.9 C10
	Wastewater	N82.9 C10	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Ethanol	N82.9 C10	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Green and clear glass	C23.19	C23.19
	Black glass	C23.19	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Miscellaneous inert waste	E38.2	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Plastic pellet	E38.2	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Biomass	A1.64	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
SOTENAS	Animal dejection	A3 (3.1, 3.2)	E36, E37
	Animal dejection	A3.2	E36, E37
	Water H ₂ O	A3.2	E36, E37
	Water H ₂ O	A3.21 A322	A3.21 A322
	Heat	E36, E37	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
DUNKIRK	Steam	C24 (24.1, 24.2, 24.3, C24.52)	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Heat	C24 (24.1, 24.2, 24.3, C24.52)	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Blast furnace slag	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	F42.11
	Ground slag	F42.11	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Tyre shreds	C22.11	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Solvents	C23	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Spent oil	C23	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Refractory Bricks	C24 (24.1, 24.2, 24.3, C24.52)	C23 (23.2, 23.32)
	Refractory Bricks	C24 (24.1, 24.2, 24.3, C24.52)	C23 (23.2, 23.32)
	Steel slag	C24 (24.1, 24.2, 24.3, C24.52)	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Miscellaneous inert waste	F43.11, 43.12	C24 (24.1, 24.2, 24.3, C24.52)
	Steel slag	C24.10 E38.22	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Steel slag	C24.10 E38.22	A1 (1.1, 1.2, 1.61)
KOUVOLA	Sludge	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Sludge	E36, E37	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)
	Wastewater	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)
	Wastewater	C20.11	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)
	Wastewater	C20.11	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)
	Water H ₂ O	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)	C20 (20.13, 20.15)
	Water H ₂ O	C20.11	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)
	Water H ₂ O	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)
	Ashes	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	E39

	Hydrogen Peroxide H ₂ O ₂	C20.11	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)
	Miscellaneous inert waste	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)	E39
	Calcium carbonate CaCo ₃	C20 (20.13, 20.15)	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)
	Carbon dioxide CO ₂	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)	C20 (20.13, 20.15)
	Chlorine Cl ₂	C20.11	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)
	Sodium hydroxide (NaOH)	C20.11	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)
	Sodium hydroxide (NaOH)	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Sludge	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Steam	D35 (35.11, 35.21 35.3)	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)
	Steam	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)	C20.11
	Steam	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)	C20 (20.13, 20.15)
RELVAO EIP	Ashes	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)	C20.15
	Biomass	A1 (1.1, 1.2, 1.4, 1.5)	C20.15
	Biomass	D35 (35.21 35.3)	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)
	Batteries and oil filters	E38.32	E38.22
	Residual oil	E38.32	E38.22
	Acids	E38.22	E38.22
	Recovered lead	E38.22	C20.51
	Sludge	E36, E37	C20.15
	Sludge	A1.47	C20.15
	Carbon dioxide CO ₂	E38.22	A3.21 A322
KOEKHOVEN	Animal dejection	A1.4 (1.41, 1.42)	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Corn	A1.13; C10.6	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Manure pellets	D35 (35.11, 35.21 35.3)	E39, N81.3
	Manure pellets	D35 (35.11, 35.21 35.3)	A1 (1.1, 1.2, 1.61)
	Biomass	A1 (1.1, 1.2, 1.4, 1.5)	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Heat	D35 (35.11, 35.21 35.3)	A1 (1.13, 1.22, 1.23, 1.24, 1.27, 1.28)
KANSAS	Polyester resin	C20.16, C20.17	E39
	Super sacks	C20.16, C20.17	E39
	Gel coats	C20.16, C20.17	C30.91
	Shredder residues	C24 (24.1, 24.2, 24.3, C24.52)	E39
	Mill scale	C24 (24.1, 24.2, 24.3, C24.52)	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Miscellaneous inert waste	C17.29	E39
	Biomass	C17.29	E38
	Miscellaneous inert waste	C17.29	C24 (24.1, 24.2, 24.3, C24.52)
	Miscellaneous inert waste	C17.29	C30.91
	Waste packaging	C17.29	C30.91
	Waste packaging	C17.29	E39
	Waste ink	C17.29	C30.91

	Waste ink	C17.29	E39
	Polydrums	C30.91	E39
	Pallets	C30.91	E39
	Rubber residues	C30.91	E39
	Plastic residues	C30.91	E39
	Plastic residues	C30.91	E38
	Metal scraps	C30.91	C24 (24.1, 24.2, 24.3, C24.52)
	Alkali slag	C30.91	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Alkali slag	C30.91	C17.29
	Abrasives	C30.91	C30.91
	Abrasives	C30.91	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Miscellaneous inert waste	C30.91	C30.91
	Miscellaneous inert waste	C30.91	E39
	Sludge	C30.91	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Powder paint	C30.91	C30.91
	Solvents	C30.91	C20.16, C20.17
	Spent oil	C30.91	E38
	Bark and scrap wood	E38	C30.91
	Bark and scrap wood	E38	C17.29
	Bark and scrap wood	E38	E39
	Glass	E38	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	FDG sludge	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Ashes	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
NANJANGUD	Boiler fuel	B6.10	C14.1
	Boiler fuel	B6.10	C27.32
	Biomass	C10, C11	C19.20
	Sawdust	C16.21	B6.1
	Ashes	C16.21	C23.70
	Spent acid	C20.14	C13
	Carbon dioxide CO ₂	C10.81	C11.07
KOKKOLA	Sulphuric Acid H ₂ SO ₄	C20.13 C20.14	C24.41
	Peroxymonosulfuric acid H ₂ SO ₅	C20.13 C20.14	C23.43 E38.22
	Sulphuric Acid H ₂ SO ₆	C20.13 C20.14	C20.15
	Disulfuric Acid H ₂ SO ₇	C20.13 C20.14	C20.20
	Sulphur dioxide SO ₂	C23.41	C20.13 C20.14
	Heat	C23.41	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Heat	C20.13 C20.14	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Steam	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	C20 (20.13, 20.15)
	Steam	C20.20	C20.15 C20.20
	Lime klin dust	C23.52	C20 (20.13, 20.15)
	Carbon dioxide CO ₂	C20 (20.13, 20.15)	C20.11
	Carbon trioxide CO ₃	C20.11	A7.29

	Hydrochloride HCl	C20.15	C20 (20.13, 20.15)
KASERBARACK E	Bark and scrap wood	A2.40	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Bark and scrap wood	A2.40	C16.29
	Sawdust	A2.40	C16.1, C16.2
	Ashes	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	C23
UIMAHARJU	Black liquor	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Bark and scrap wood	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Bark and scrap wood	C16.10	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Chips sawdust	C16.10	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)
	Oxygen O2	C17.11	C20.11
	Carbon dioxide CO ₂	C17.11	C20.11
	Dissolving pulp	C17.11	C13.1
	Pulping chemicals	C17.11	C20
	Wastewater	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)	E36, E37
	Sludge	E36, E37	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Ashes	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	C20.15
RANTASALMI	Sawdust	F41.2	D35 (35.21, 35.3)
	Sawdust	C24.2	D35 (35.21, 35.3)
	Sawdust	F43	D35 (35.21, 35.3)
	Bark and scrap wood	F41.2	C19.20
	Cardboard	F41.2	C19.20
	Plastic packaging	F41.2	C19.20
	Log panels and floor board	F43	F41.2
	Heat	D35 (35.21, 35.3)	ND
VALUE PARK	Wood pellets	N82.9	C20.16
	Heat	C20.16	C23
	Heat	C20.16	H49.2
PONTE EGOLA	A Exhausted Chrome Tanning production	C15.11	C24.45
		C15.11	C20.15
		C15.11	E36, E37
		C23	E36, E37
		E36, E37	A1 (1.1, 1.2, 1.61)
		E36, E37	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
SARNIA	Carbon dioxide CO ₂	C20.15	A1 (1.13, 1.22, 1.23, 1.24, 1.27, 1.28)
	Heat	C20.15	A1 (1.13, 1.22, 1.23, 1.24, 1.27, 1.28)
	Carbon dioxide CO ₂	C20.15	C11.07
	Carbon dioxide CO ₂	C20.14 D35.21	C11.04, C11.07
	Ammonia NH ₃	C20.15	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Residual oil	C19.20	C20.13
	Residual oil	C20.13	C19.20
	Chemical butadiene	C20	C20.16, C20.17
Isobutylene C ₄ H ₈	C20	C20.17	

	Residual crude mixture	C20	C19 (19.10, 19.20)
	Waste corn	A1.13; C10.6	C20.14 D35.21
	Spent grain	C20.14 D35.21	A1 (1.4, 1.5, 1.62)
STYRIA	Bark and scrap wood	C16.10	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)
	Waste paper pulp (fine material)	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)	C16.29
	Fibre sludges	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)	C23.3
	Ashes	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Bark and scrap wood	C16.10	C23.3
	Bark and scrap wood	C16.10	C16.1, C16.2
	Textile scraps	C13 (13.1, 13.2, 13.3, 13.9) C14 (14.1, 14.2, 14.3)	C23 (23.2, 23.3, 23.4)
	Pine oil pitch	C20	C23.3
	Flax waste	A1.16	C23 (23.31, 23.32)
	Ashes	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)	B5, B7, B8
	Ashes	D35 (35.11, 35.21 35.3)	B5, B7, B8
	Ashes	D35 (35.11, 35.21 35.3)	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Gypsum	D35 (35.11, 35.21 35.3)	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Excavated material	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)	C23
	Tyre shreds	C29.1	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Residual oil	C29.1	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Iron residues	C29.1	C24.51
	Cinder sand	C24, C25	C23
	Cinder sand	C24, C25	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Lead dust	C23.43	C20.12
JYVASKYLA	Bark and scrap wood	C16.21	D35 (35.21, 35.3)
	Steam	D35 (35.21 35.3)	C16.21
	Steam	D35 (35.21 35.3)	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)
	Heat	D35 (35.21 35.3)	ND
	Heat	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)	A1 (1.1, A1.2, A1.3)
FORTH VALLEY	Sewadge pellets	E36, E37	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Ashes	D35 (35.11, 35.21 35.3)	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Ashes	D35 (35.11, 35.21 35.3)	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65) E39
	Sludge	C20	E38.22
	Fuel pellets	E38	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Tyre shreds	C29.1	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Ethylene	C20.1	C19.20
	Poultry litter	A1.47	C20.15 C20.20
KEMI-TORNIO	Riffler waste	C16 (16.1, 16.2)	E39, N81.3
	Riffler waste	C16.1 C16.2	A1 (1.4, 1.5, 1.62)
	Riffler waste	C16.1 C16.2	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Ashes	C16.1 C16.2	E39, N81.3

	Ashes	C16.1 C16.2	C23.70
	Ashes	C16.1 C16.2	B7.29
	Blast furnace slag	C24.45	C24.45
	Blast furnace slag	C24.45	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Carbon dioxide CO ₂	C24.45	C23.99
KYMI EIP	Bark and scrap wood	A2 (2.1, 2.2)	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)
	Bark and scrap wood	A2 (2.1, 2.2)	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Pulp	C17.11	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)
	Bark and scrap wood	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Bark and scrap wood	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Sodium hydroxide NaOH	C20.11	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)
	Sodium hydroxide NaOH	C20.11	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)
	Sodium hydroxide NaOH	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Sodium hydroxide NaOH	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)
	Chlorine Dioxide ClO ₂	C20.11	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)
	Chlorine Trioxide ClO ₃	C20.11	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)
	Wastewater	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)	E36, E37
	Wastewater	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)	E36, E37
	Wastewater	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	E36, E37
	Wastewater	C20 (20.13, 20.15)	E36, E37
	Wastewater	C20.11	E36, E37
	Wastewater	C20.11	E36, E37
	Sludge	E36, E37	E36, E37
	Ashes	D35 (35.11, 35.21, 35.3)	E39
	Carbon dioxide CO ₂	C17.11	C20 (20.13, 20.15)
	Carbon trioxide CO ₃	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)	C20 (20.13, 20.15)
	Calcium carbonate CaCo ₃	C20 (20.13, 20.15)	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)
	Calcium carbonate CaCo ₃	C20 (20.13, 20.15)	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)
	Chlorine Cl ₂	C20.11	E36, E37
	Water H ₂ O	E36, E37	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)
	Water H ₂ O	E36, E37	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)
	Water H ₂ O	E36, E37	C20 (20.13, 20.15)
	Water H ₂ O	E36, E37	C20.11
	Hydrogen Peroxide H ₂ O ₂	C20.11	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)
	Trioxidane H ₂ O ₃	C20.11	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)
	Heat	C17.11	C20.11
	Heat	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)	C20.11
	Heat	C17.11	C20 (20.13, 20.15)
Heat	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)	C20 (20.13, 20.15)	
Fibre sludges	C17.11	E39	
Fibre sludges	C17.1 (17.11, 17,12)	E39	
ALTAMIRA	Residual oil	C20.17	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Residual oil	C23.99	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Paper	C20.17	E38.32

	Paper	C23.99	E38.32
	Bark and scrap wood	C20.17	E38.32
	Bark and scrap wood	C23.99	E38.32
	Steam	C23.99	C20.17
	Steam	C23.99	C20
	Steam	C23.16	C20.17
	Steam	C20.16	C20
	Steam	C20.16, C20.17	C20.16
	Wastewater	C20.17	C23.99
	Plastic residues	C20.17	E38.32
	Light hydrocarbons	C20.16	C20.16
	Light hydrocarbons	C20.16	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Fumaric acid	C20.16	C10 C11
	Plastic residues	C22.22	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Flue gas	C23.99	C20.11
	Flue gas	C20.16	C20.11
	Carbon dioxide CO ₂	C20.11	C20.11
	Hazardous waste	C20.16, C20.17	C23 (23.51, 23.52, 23.65)
	Reclaimed water	C20.16, C20.17	C20.16
	Reclaimed water	E36, E37	C19.20
	Wastewater	C20.16	C20.16, C20.17
	Wastewater	B6.10	E36, E37

In conclusion, the analysis of the existing IS exchanges within EIPs and regional IS demonstrates that IS implementation varies significantly across different initiatives, influenced by local policies, pre-existing industrial structures. The commodity product of the residue particularly affects the feasibility of symbiotic exchange as well as the geographical break-even. The main key challenges to facilitate IS implementation are therefore related to the licensing process, the role of intermediaries, the reclassification of waste, and the identification of the most effective technology for minimising environmental impact throughout the waste's life cycle (Soares et al., 2023)

MAPPING EXISTING IS DIGITAL PLATFORM

Digital platforms are at the forefront of the European Union's Circular Economy Action Plan, which underscores the transformative role of digitalisation in realising a sustainable and efficient circular economy. These platforms leverage cutting-edge technologies, such as data analytics, the Internet of Things (IoT), and Artificial Intelligence (AI), to connect stakeholders across various sectors. By facilitating communication and resource sharing, digital platforms can streamline material flows, reduce waste, and accelerate the adoption of circular practices.

Digitalisation acts as a catalyst for innovation within the CE by offering unprecedented opportunities for cross-sector collaboration and resource optimization. As businesses and governments across Europe increasingly recognise the need for sustainable practices, digital platforms are emerging as a critical tool in reshaping production processes and integrating value chains.

The Circular Economy Action Plan emphasizes the need for stakeholders to adopt digital solutions that can promote resource efficiency, knowledge and technology transfer to encourage the dissemination and transition towards a low-carbon economy. Digital platforms facilitate this shift by enabling real-time data collection and analysis, allowing for better decision-making and more efficient management of materials. As noted by

Pagoropoulos et al. (2017) and Antikainen et al. (2018), these technologies empower organisations to create interconnected cycles that support a more sustainable approach to production and consumption.

However, the adoption of digital platforms in the context of the CE is not without challenges. Studies by Trevisan et al. (2023) and Krom et al. (2022) highlight several barriers that must be addressed to unlock the full potential of digitalization. These include financial constraints, technological limitations, and policy-related hurdles. Additionally, knowledge management and the integration of digital solutions into existing business practices are significant challenges that require careful consideration.

The primary objective of this section is to provide a comprehensive overview of state-of-the-art digital platforms dedicated to the CE and IS. These platforms play a pivotal role in promoting sustainable business practices, facilitating resource exchange, and fostering collaboration among companies. To achieve this objective, several sub-objectives have been identified:

1. Investigate the main services offered:

- Examine the range of services provided by these platforms, including case studies, best practices, toolkits, networking opportunities, and collaborative project facilitation.
- Analyse how these services support businesses in implementing circular economy principles and industrial symbiosis strategies.

2. Map the Key Public and Private Operators:

- Identify and map the major public and private entities managing these platforms.
- Understand the roles and contributions of different stakeholders, including chambers of commerce, industry associations, supranational organisations, and private companies.

3. Understand Usage Dynamics and Factors of Acceptability and Usability:

- Explore how businesses and other users interact with these platforms.
- Identify the factors that influence the acceptability and usability of the platforms, such as ease of navigation, availability of relevant resources, and user support services.

To achieve this, data was collected on digital platforms initiatives at both national and international levels. The state-of-the-art review was developed through the following steps:

1. Mapping of existing platform

- **Comprehensive Literature Review:** Identified relevant fields of application.
- **Desk Research and EU Database Analysis:** Examined the European Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform (ECESP).

2. Database creation

3. **Selection and Analysis of Existing Platforms:** development of criteria to evaluate and compare current digital platforms in the field.

4. **Overview of the Italian Panorama:** Analysis of Italy's landscape in industrial symbiosis and circular economy digital initiatives.

The first step of the research was an exploration of the literature related to online platforms and digital advances in the field of circular economy and industrial symbiosis.

From the preliminary review, a rich panorama of recent articles emerged on digital solutions to favour circular economy principles and industrial symbiosis processes.

To perform this exploratory literature research, the following databases were chosen: Scopus, and Web of Science.

For the searches, different methods were pursued, starting from the use of Boolean operators (AND and OR), different sets of keyword combinations were employed following the database's specific search requirements. The

main keyword combination that was defined is: ("industrial symbiosis" AND (digital-platform OR tools) AND "circular economy" AND network). The second combination is: ("industrial symbiosis" AND (platform OR tools) AND "circular economy").

These studies delve into the advantages and challenges associated with the implementation of such digital platforms (Trevisan et al., 2023; Neri et al., 2023; Fraccascia and Yazan, 2018; Pigosso et al., 2018). Furthermore, many articles offer in-depth analyses of the platforms' functionalities, often through the examination of interesting case studies (Cutaia et al., 2015; Soares et al., 2023; Pizzi et al., 2021; Angelis-Dimakis et al. 2022).

Based on a comprehensive review of the existing literature, we selected a set of platforms to start defining criteria to develop an in-depth analysis to understand their role in the development and promotion of IS practices. These platforms offer a diverse range of functions, from resource sharing and waste management to collaborative networks and marketplace activities. By examining these case studies, we aim to highlight successful approaches and identify common factors that contribute to the success of these platforms.

The following table (Table 10) summarises the platforms selected for our analysis from literature, along with a brief description of their core functions, geographic scope, and the sector(s) they serve. These case studies represent a broad spectrum of industries and applications, providing valuable insights into how digital platforms can facilitate circular economy principles.

Table 10. Reviewed IS platforms.

Article reference	Case study platform
Cutaia et al. (2015).	SUN platform network http://www.industrialsymbiosis.it/piattaforma
Portas, Roberto & Ruiz-Puente, Carmen. (2017).	SymbioSys https://www.simbiosy.com/
Hsien, C. et al.,(2020).	Maestri platform https://maestri-spire.eu/
Pizzi et al. (2021)	Circularity.com https://circularity.com/
Angelis-Dimakis et al. (2022)	Swan project https://swan-interreg.com/
Soares et al.(2023)	Upvalue platform https://upvalue.pt/

Barbero et al. (2023)	Digicirc https://matchmakingtool.digicirc.eu/KnowledgeHub/Index
Aid et al. (2015)	Looplocal (doesn't exist anymore)
Fric, Urška & Rončević, Borut. (2018).	E-Simbioza e-Simbioza
Franzò, Simone & Urbinati, Andrea (2023).	Sfridoo https://sfridoo.softtr.app/resource
Scolaro, A. M., Marchi, L., & Sara, C. (2021).	Borsino rifiuti https://www.borsinorifiuti.com/2020/index.php
Moodie, J., Salenius, V., & Leino, J. (2019).	Baltic industrial symbiosis https://interreg-baltic.eu/project/bis/
Grabham, S., & Manu, E. (2022).	Digiplace https://digiplaceproject.eu/about
Grabham, S., & Manu, E. (2022).	Digiplace https://digiplaceproject.eu/about
Mossali, E., Diani, M., & Colledani, M. (2020, December).	Digiprime https://www.digiprime.eu/partners/
Krom, P., Piscicelli, L., & Frenken, K. (2022).	indusym https://www.indusym.nl/over-ons/indusym flow2 https://www.floow2.com/our-solutions.html

Bianchini, M., Maffei, S., & Sedinì, C. (2023)	Circuloop https://circuloop.it/app/
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In parallel with the literature analysis, we undertook a comprehensive process of desk research to examine the main existing platforms that support IS. This desk research involved a detailed exploration of online resources, reports, and platform websites to identify key players in the digital landscape that are driving circular practices. A crucial source for this phase has been the EU platform about circular economy, which functions as a repository of numerous case studies selected. (<https://circulareconomy.europa.eu/platform/en/dialogue/existing-eu-platforms>)

The objective of this analysis was to create an accurate inventory and a taxonomy of platforms to evaluate their scope, functionalities, and activities at both national and European levels. This method used to analyse the digital platform has been chosen because of three main purposes: understanding the relation between their ownership, services offered, and accessibility; acknowledging what interactions are recurring for the different services the platform offers; and identifying patterns, both common and uncommon, recurring in these types of platforms. To ensure a more consistent and comprehensive assessment of these tools, we established a set of criteria that would allow us to compare and understand the array of the fifty-two platforms considered in this research. The criteria included factors such as the platform's primary purpose, user base, geographical reach, technology stack, business model, and contributions to circular economy principles. By analysing these aspects, it was possible to identify recurring interactions for the different services offered by the platforms. This analysis revealed patterns in the operation and effectiveness of these platforms, demonstrating, for example, that European co-founded platforms are generally more accessible but less personalised, whereas business-oriented platforms are more customised and effective in their services.

Table 11 summarise the result of the research, providing an overview of the analysed platforms and highlights the criteria used to evaluate them. This structured approach allowed us to categorise the platforms based on their features.

The analysis revealed various categories dedicated to IS initiatives, each with distinct objectives and functionalities. The identified functions include:

- **Good Practices Repositories:** Platforms that collect and share successful case studies and examples of best practices in circular economy and industrial symbiosis.

- **Marketplaces:** Digital spaces where companies can buy and sell resources, materials, and by-products, promoting the reuse and recycling of goods.
- **Matching Platforms:** Tools that facilitate the identification and connection of potential partners for resource exchange and collaboration.
- **Industrial Symbiosis:** Systems that support the development of mutually beneficial relationships between companies for the sharing and reuse of resources.
- **Training:** Educational programs and resources that provide knowledge and skills for implementing CE and IS practices.

These initiatives, including projects funded by the European Union, span several countries and often involve networks of partners.

To better understand the landscape of these initiatives, it is helpful to examine the specific categories of platforms that support these functions. The first category identified includes the **platforms dedicated to industrial symbiosis**. They aim at facilitating symbiotic relationships, which enable companies to identify and establish partnerships for the exchange of resources and by-products. These platforms offer matchmaking tools to help businesses find suitable partners, along with resource databases and logistics coordination services to facilitate trade and optimise resource utilisation. The second category identified are **databases of circular good practices** networks, serving as hubs for sharing circular practices and best practices among companies and stakeholders. These platforms offer training, knowledge sharing, and resources to support companies in implementing waste reduction, recycling, and reuse strategies, thus promoting efficient and sustainable resource management. The third category involves **waste marketplaces**, providing virtual platforms for buying, selling, and trading waste materials and by-products. Through research, mapping services, contractual negotiation, and transaction monitoring, these platforms facilitate exchanges between companies, contributing to the recovery and reuse of materials and reducing the environmental impact associated with the production and disposal of waste materials. Furthermore, among the multitude of digital platforms focusing on the circular economy, another distinction arises between open, semi-accessible, and closed platforms. **Open access** platforms allow free and unlimited availability to all users, fostering open sharing of knowledge and resources. **Semi-open access** platforms provide limited information, requiring registration or prior information to access additional services. **Closed platforms**, on the other hand, are generally private consultancy service providers, offering specialised services such as the facilitation of symbiotic relationships and the management of circular practice networks.

In Italy, the digital platform landscape is rich and diverse, reflecting the country's commitment to innovation and sustainability. A prime example is the research lab ENEA's establishment of the Italian Platform for Circular Economy (ICESP). This platform serves as a comprehensive database of best practices in the circular economy, offering valuable resources and insights. Furthermore, Enea founded a dynamic network to support the development of industrial symbiosis, fostering collaboration and knowledge-sharing among various stakeholders. In parallel, also the Chamber of Commerce from different Italian regions have made significant contributions in introducing and promoting circular economy platforms. Over the past few years, they have developed a range of platforms designed to enhance sustainability practices across industries. One example is Albo Circular, which map exemplary practices, providing a repository of successful circular economy initiatives. Additionally, other platforms, such as Elenco Sottoprodotti, focus on mapping material flows and end-of-waste streams.

These platforms also offer matchmaking services, connecting businesses and organisations to facilitate collaboration and drive innovation in the circular economy. At the NODES territory, the data published on the website reveals that a significant portion of resource exchanges occurs within the agroindustry, specifically in sectors such as farming, cereal and agricultural cultivation. The primary new functionality of these resource exchanges is the generation of energy.

In addition to these public initiatives, private services are also contributing significantly to the circular economy in Italy. Companies such as Sfridoo and Circularity provide specialised matchmaking and consultancy services. These private platforms play a crucial role in connecting businesses with circular economy opportunities, offering expert advice and facilitating the exchange of materials and resources. Through their efforts they facilitate businesses optimise resource use, reduce waste, and implement sustainable practices effectively.

Table 11. IS platform database.

NAME	DESCRIPTION	PRIVATE / PUBLIC	ACTIVE / INACTIVE	SECTORS AND AREA SERVED	PRIMARY SERVICE	SECONDARY SERVICE	
albo circular	A free tool designed for all companies offering or seeking solutions and products in the Circular Economy promoted by Confindustria Emilia Area Centro.	Public	Active	ND	Good practices	Consultancy + Certification	/
Sfridoo	An online marketplace born to give new life to production waste, protecting the environment and creating a virtuous model for businesses.	Private	Active	Different industry/waste categories	Marketplace	Consultancy	Dissemination
Circularity	Circular economy platform dedicated to companies that want to recycle production waste and reduce their environmental impact through sustainable transport, the recovery of their waste and the use of secondary raw materials.	Private	Active	Different industry/waste categories	Marketplace	Consultancy + Assessment + Professional Training	Dissemination (Blog)

<u>ICESP</u>	ICESP is configured as a network whose objective is to create a point of national convergence on the initiatives, experiences, critical issues, prospects and expectations on the circular economy that our country wants and can represent in Europe with a single voice, promoting the Italian way of creating a circular economy also through specific dedicated actions.	Public	Active	ND	Good practices	/	Dissemination
<u>Elenco Sottoprodotti</u>	Platform that allows by-product producers and potential users to make requests and offers public	Public	Active	Different industry/waste categories	Matching	/	Dissemination (not updated)
<u>EcoDesk Web</u>	The Chambers of Commerce offer EcoDesk, a software solution aiding businesses in navigating environmental obligations and opportunities. EcoDesk facilitates compiling registers and forms, tracking waste from production to sale of recovered materials. It interoperates with Vi.Vi.Fir for virtual validation of waste transport forms and enables access to transporter registrations through the National Register of Environmental Managers' telematic data service.	Public with private participation	Active	ND	Good practices	Training	Consultancy (forse è un sec
<u>ENEA Industrial Symbiosis</u>	The Industrial symbiosis platform is a tool aimed at businesses and other operators present in the area. It aims to bring together supply and demand of resources, understood as materials, energy by-products, water, services and skills, and activate transfers between companies.	Public	Active	Different industry/waste categories	Industrial Symbiosis	Good practices + research	/

<u>Borsino Rifiuti</u>	Facilitation of the management of waste produced by private individuals, companies and public bodies. An innovative model actively involves both those who manage waste recycling and those who produce it, creating a connection between supply and demand through a dedicated delivery network. Their mission is based on four fundamental pillars: Digital Waste Management, a B2B and B2C sponsorship platform, the combination of waste from public bodies and the combination of by-products and secondary raw materials to reduce production waste.	Private network	Active	Waste (urban and special waste)	Good practices	Matching + Marketplace	/
<u>Atlante economia circolare</u>	Is an interactive web platform that records and recounts the experiences of economic and associative realities committed to applying the principles of the circular economy in Italy. The Atlas, conceived and created by the CDCA - Documentation Center on Environmental Conflicts with the support of Erion, aims to be a tool for raising awareness, information and documentation aimed at all those who care about the balance between economy and ecology and who wish to direct their consumption responsibly. Among the objectives of the Atlas is the networking of businesses and associations capable of connecting with each other and increasing potential synergies and their visibility. By browsing between regions and categories, users can consult the descriptive sheets of the individual areas mapped for free	Public	Active	Different industry/waste categories	Good practices + Reserach + Dissemination	/	/
EUROPEAN PROJECT							
<u>Baltic Industrial Symbiosis</u>	The project aimed at screening resources and matchmaking companies eager to find sustainable green business models. The business companies received a detailed review of their specific resource streams and advice on what resources they should focus on in relation to resource optimisation. Training and peer-to-peer exchanges were held to build capacity among industrial symbiosis practitioners. The project organised so-called Living Labs as innovative arenas for start-ups and SMEs as well as large companies to analyse, test, and discuss their resource flows and the development of new products.	Public and private network	Active	Different industry/waste categories	Industrial Symbiosis	Call to action (to access fundings)	Dissemination

<u>CircLean</u>	CircLean is a European network of stakeholders interested in fostering the future of industrial symbiosis in the European Union. It brings together industries, public authorities, industry associations and researchers. We will make available tools that evidence the impact of industrial symbiosis. Through our expertise and experience in the field, we will ensure that these tools reflect the needs and realities of European businesses, especially those in the chemical, steel, metal, construction and waste management sectors. We hope to inspire others to be leaders for change by sharing experiences and good practices both on new technologies as much as on successful industrial symbiosis programmes	Public and private network	Active (not working)	Different industry/waste categories	Matching	/	/
<u>Digicirc</u>	DigiCirc is a digital platform designed to foster collaboration among companies, public bodies, and researchers with a shared goal: to create a more sustainable economy through circularity. By promoting the efficient use of materials and energy, extending product lifecycles, and ensuring that waste becomes valuable input for others, DigiCirc aims to transform our economic systems into more sustainable and interconnected ones.	Public and private network	Project ended	Different industry/waste categories	Matching	/	/
<u>Maestri</u>	The MAESTRI project seeks to enhance the sustainability of European manufacturing and process industries through a flexible, scalable management system known as the MAESTRI Total Efficiency Framework. This innovative approach aims to improve companies' environmental and economic performance by providing clear guidance and simplifying the implementation of efficiency measures.	Public and private network	project ended (not updated since 2019)	Oil and gas, electric power plants, construction, metalmechanics, and chemistry	Industrial Symbiosis	Consultancy + Management support	/
<u>SWAN - Interreg</u>	Digital solid-waste reuse platform, which maps solid waste in the Balkan region and Cyprus, acting as the basis for the establishment of solid-waste reuse value chains. The SWAN platform, previously discussed by Angelis-Dimakis et al. (2021), is an open access tool able to map and match solid waste sources with potential waste re-users, and propose waste reuse loops and value chains in the countries of Greece, Bulgaria, Albania, and Cyprus («SWAN»).	Public and private network	Project ended (the website is active)	Metal-mechanics, chemistry, construction, among others	Matching	Costum solution	Dissemination

<u>DigiPLA CE</u>	Digital platform digital services for the Architecture and construction fields. It is a platform based on an EU-wide consensus involving a large community of stakeholders, resulting in a strategic roadmap for successful implementation of this architecture.	Public and private network	Project ended	Construction and demolition	Digital transformation	Consultancy + Management support	/
<u>Scaler Project</u>	SCALER (SCALing European Resources with industrial symbiosis) aims to increase the uptake of industrial symbiosis across Europe. Under the European Union's Horizon2020 initiative, the project will develop a set of best practices, tools and guidelines, helping businesses and industrial sites work together to ensure sustainable resource use.	Public and private network	ended (the website is active and updated to 2024)	Different industry/waste categories	Industrial Symbiosis	Good practices	Dissemination
<u>FiberEUse</u>	The objectives of FiberEUse revolve around implementing and showcasing large-scale remanufacturing technologies to facilitate profitable reuse options for recycled composite materials. These technologies aim to streamline operations, reduce costs significantly, adhere to EU Directives, and minimize environmental impacts for Glass Fiber Reinforced Polymer (GFRP) and Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymer (CFRP) composites. The project also seeks to establish new value chains and demo-cases across various manufacturing sectors, subjecting them to thorough assessments like Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and the EU Environmental Technology Verification (ETV) program. Additionally, FiberEUse aims to develop an innovation strategy that mobilizes and connects stakeholders across the composite industry, including original equipment manufacturers (OEMs), suppliers, technology providers, designers, and end-user associations. This strategy intends to create a communication platform for disseminating results, overcoming innovation barriers by aligning regional regulations, and demonstrating the economic viability of remanufacturing options. Ultimately, the project aims to shift perceptions from mere "recycling" to a focus on "valorization through reuse and remanufacturing."	Public and private network	Inactive (website works but is not up to date)	Fiber-reinforced composite materials	Marketplace	R/D	/

<u>Life m3p</u>	Material Match Making Platform, focusing on Circular Economy and Industrial Symbiosis, aims to develop an industrial waste valorization system, based on the characterization and classification of their properties, through an on-line platform dedicated to combining materials and waste.	Public and private network	Project ended (2019)	Miscellaneous materials, power, and water	Industrial Symbiosis	Match Making • Assessment	Dissemination
<u>DigiPrime</u>	Is a digital platform for creating circular business models based on the data-enhanced recovery and reuse of functions and materials in cross-sectorial value networks. the aim was to create and operate a federated model of digital platforms for cross-sector business in the circular economy. DigiPrime will be validated through several cross-sectoral pilots, further detailed in 20 use cases covering different European industrial sectors (automotive, renewable energy, electronics, textile, construction), and by additional pilots in new sectors, funded through an open call mechanism.	Public and private network	Project ended (2021)	Automotive • Renewable energy • Electronics • Textile • Construction	Technology transfer	Material Match Making Platform	Call to action (to access fund)
<u>REPAiR</u>	An online tool designed for workshop sessions where small groups of participants cooperatively develop strategies for a more circular economy with a special focus on waste and resource management.	Public and private network	Project ended (2020)	Different industry/waste categories	Management support for the sustainable development of local and regional planning authorities, NGOs, public and private waste management companies	Consortium	Dissemination

<u>Urban Mine Platform</u>	<p>This platform serves as a comprehensive repository, showcasing available data related to products introduced to the market, existing stocks, compositions, and waste flows for electrical and electronic equipment (EEE), vehicles, and batteries across EU 28 Member States, Switzerland, Norway, and Iceland (specifically for vehicles). For batteries, EEE, and vehicles, the data is categorized into three main sections: The Urban Mine: This section illustrates the number and types of products entering the market, existing in-stock (in use and hibernated), and becoming waste (or leaving stock in the case of vehicles). Compositions: Detailed specifications are provided for key components, materials, and elements (e.g., aluminium, copper, gold, neodymium) present in BATT, EEE, and vehicle products. Waste Flows: This section covers reported collection amounts, estimates for small batteries and unsorted municipal solid waste containing EEE products, supplementary battery and EEE recycling flows, exported used vehicles, and the unknown whereabouts of vehicles, batteries, and electronics.</p>	Public and private network	ended (2018)	Waste flows for electrical and electronic equipment (EEE) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vehicles • Batteries 	Database	/	/
Danmark							
<u>waste-outlet</u>	<p>Is a platform that function as digital waste marketplace where is possible to buy or sell residual or secondary raw material, through a bidding process.</p>	Private	Active	Different industry/waste categories	Marketplace	Matching	/
<u>Dansk symbiose center</u>	<p>Is a project that promotes industrial symbiosis and regional development across the Baltic Sea region. Means to connect companies from different industries in order to use one company's waste, in the form of e.g. energy, ingredients or materials, as a resource for the next company. The project establishes peer-to-peer exchange for industrial symbiosis practitioners. It develops new business and finance models and sets up the BSR Industrial Symbiosis Council as a platform for dialogue and policy learning.</p>	Public and private network	Ended (2019), Its activities have been transferred to Kalundborg Symbiosis.	Different industry/waste categories	Industrial Symbiosis	Project accelerator/incubator	/

Netherlands							
indusym	We support the energy transition by collecting and processing data on energy and water. On the other hand, we stimulate the circular economy by creating connections between companies for optimal use of residual flows. It maps the various residual flows in companies and creates a picture of opportunities within a territory. This allows projects to be initiated to develop alternative and sustainable processing methods. In this way, industrial zones become more sustainable and optimized, with the ultimate goal of 100% circular industrial zones.	Public and private network	Inactive (website works but is not up to date)	Different industry/waste categories	Industrial Symbiosis	Marketplace <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technology transfer • Tool/worker sharing 	Dissemination (news)
Symbiosis4Growth	The Excess Materials Exchange (EME) is a digital marketplace where companies can exchange excess materials with each other.	Public and private network	active	exchange (residual) materials, energy, knowledge, capacity, facilities and innovation	Industrial Symbiosis	Project accelerator <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Good practices • Research • Dissemination 	/
accez.	A platform which aims to foster circular economy practices in the southern Netherlands. It pools initiatives by several regional universities and public and private actors in the following fields: area development, circular agriculture, manufacturing industries, plastic. The platform bolsters cooperation between partners to develop solutions for knowledge-intensive issues. To do so, they oversee and fund triple-helix research projects. The end-goal of the platform is to enhance the regional knowledge base and networks, with a view to substantially accelerating the transition to a circular economy.	private	active	area development circular agriculture manufacturing industries plastic. agriculture/ construction /2B services, Circular action for climate neutrality, Innovation and investment, Research	Project accelerator <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Good practices • Research • Dissemination 	/	/

<u>oogstkaart</u>	Mapping and cataloging of residual materials and raw materials to be purchased or sold and reused in new applications. Oogstkaart offers comprehensive insights into the availability of reclaimed and circular materials in the construction and real estate sector, facilitating both procurement and sale transactions. Essentially, the platform serves as a mapping tool for the urban mining potential of the Netherlands.	Public and private network	is not been updated since 2023	construction	Marketpace	Consultancy + Management support	/
<u>circles</u>	CIRCLES is a platform dedicated to disseminating circular economy solutions in the Eastern Netherlands. It encourages entrepreneurs to participate in the green transition, promoting their sense of ownership in the transition process. It offers a space for stakeholders to interact and exchange views on circular economy – digitally or physically - or simply a space to establish partnerships. Several organisations – public, private and NGOs – interact in a range of ways, including workshops, publications, opportunities to access finance. One of the initiatives, for instance, consists of a space to submit ideas. If viable, cooperation with regional universities can be established, and entrepreneurs can collaborate to reach solutions	Public and private network	active	raw materials, energy or other innovative ideas	Good practices + knowledge sharing	Technology transfer • Tool/worker sharing	Dissemination
<u>floow2.</u>	sharing marketplace technology matches demand and supply of resources so you can use idle assets, make procurement cost savings and become more sustainable. Even better: sharing marketplaces can be applied to any type of resource – from furniture to medication – and used by any sector, from health to retail.	private	active	Construction, healthcare, agriculture	Marketplace • Technology transfer • Tool/worker sharing		
Belgium							
<u>Vlaanderen Circulair</u>	Flanders Circular is the hub and inspiration for the circular economy in Flanders. It is a partnership of governments, companies, civil society and the knowledge world that take action together.	private and public network	active	Bio-economy Circular Construction Chemicals/Plastics Manufacturing Industry Food Chain Water Cycles	Project accelerator •Good practices •Reserach •Dissemination	policy instruments, circular procurement, communication, innovation and entreprene	

						urship, financing, jobs and skills, and research	
<u>irisphere</u>	The IRISPHERE program coordinated by citydev.brussels aims to stimulate the development of the circular economy in the Brussels-Capital Region. It aims to guide Brussels companies in improving the circularity of materials and to increase inter-company cooperation at the regional level. With this in mind, the IRISPHERE team assists you free of charge to implement synergies focused on materials and services.	private and public network	Ended in 2021 (is still online)	construction, resources and waste management, logistics, and retail businesses	Consultancy + Management support	Project accelerator • Good practices • Reserach • Dissemination Facilitation and Networking • Training and Workshops Project Support	
Portugal							
<u>upvalue</u>	A digital matchmaking platform that aggregates relevant information and provides innovative technical support for matching waste and by-products with potential applications, The role of Upvalue is to aggregate information and provide innovative technical support in terms of matching waste and by-products with potential applications.	private	Active	Different industry/waste categories	Marketplace	Matching • Consultancy + Management support	
Spagna							

<p><u>simbiosy</u></p>	<p>The SymbioSyS tool, based on ICT-web systems, promotes the sustainable use of resources through Industrial Symbiosis (IS) strategies and facilitates networking among companies. Its primary objectives are: (1) building a large database that stores both tacit knowledge of experiences and practices and explicit information about activities; (2) detecting potential synergies for substitution and mutuality and providing feasibility studies; and (3) visualizing and mapping IS synergies by georeferencing to analyze variables such as distances, transportation routes, and optimal locations for new facilities. Implemented as a client-server model, it allows multiple users to simultaneously connect and access the application via a web service. The tool has been tested within an industrial park community consisting of 25 small and medium-sized enterprises from different sectors (e.g., automotive, building sector), allowing the visualization of both types of synergies, resource exchanges, and joint waste management opportunities. The functions and performance of the tool are demonstrated through the case study.</p>	<p>Public and private network</p>	<p>is not been updated since november 2023</p>	<p>Metallic and electric waste, tires, batteries, paint, lubricants, plastic packages, wood, municipalities, business associations, public administrations, private companies, technological parks, and rural areas.</p>	<p>Consultancy + Management support</p>	<p>Project accelerator <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reserach • Training and Workshops Project Support</p>	
<p><u>residuore curso</u></p>	<p>The Catalan Raw Materials and By-Products Exchange, is a free service designed to maximize waste reuse, promote recycling, and help companies reduce costs and improve competitiveness. It manages a database of companies offering or seeking materials for reuse and recycling, thus lowering search costs. Additionally, it organizes information and networking activities focused on waste and resource management.</p>	<p>Public and private network</p>		<p>plastic and rubber paper and paperboard metal animal and vegetable organic wood and biomass inorganic and glass textiles and leather saline, wastewater and process water sewage sludge</p>	<p>Marketplace</p>	<p>Matching <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consultancy + Management support </p>	

Inghilterra							
<u>.balebid</u>	marketplace specifically designed for the brokerage and trading of recyclable material and recycling equipment.	private	active	Different industry/waste categories	Marketplace	Consultancy + Management support	
<u>wastematch</u>	reuse / re-engineering of surplus furniture recovery , exchange platform	private		furniture	Marketplace	Consultancy + Management support	
<u>wastetrade</u>	WasteTrade is an online marketplace that connects the producers, recyclers and manufacturers of waste material globally. On the WasteTrade platform there are material listings and filter by preferences, whether that's location, quantity, volume or to find a specific grade of material or recycled product. WasteTrade's will also calculate shipping costs, compliance, documents, exchange rates and carbon footprint all at the click of a button. WasteTrade has partnered with the artificial intelligence tool ThinkCarbon to provide carbon footprint analysis of any proposed deals prior to agreement and to allow for informed and carbon-efficient decision making.	private	active	plastic	Marketplace	Matching • Management support • Logistics Coordination	
Francia							
<u>economie circulaire</u>	This collaborative platform organizes circular economy knowledge and mobilizes actors at regional, national, and international levels. It targets professionals involved in circular economy projects, including local authorities, companies, developers, consultants, and associations. The platform features 9 regional platforms, 1 international hub, 18,000 members, 1,200 referenced initiatives, and 300,000 annual users.	Public and private network	active	Different industry/Circular Innovation Ecosystem, knowledge sharing (thematic seminars and	Good practices + Reserach + Dissemination	Technology transfer • Tool/worker sharing	

				workshops , company seminars)			
<u>inex-circular</u>	Inex Circular is a digital solution that enables users to find outlets for their excavated soil and connect local waste producers and recyclers. iNex (Eco System Exchange) is a web platform designed to find practical solutions in a local area using big data techniques and knowledge on resources reusing. The platform instantly shows synergy potentials, simulates alternative network configurations, and for each of them assesses the effects in terms of environmental and economic benefits («INex Circular»).	Public and private network	ended ()	Different industry/Circular Innovation Ecosystem, knowledge sharing (thematic seminars and workshops , company seminars)	Reserach + Dissemination (workshop)	Consultancy + Management support	
Germania							
<u>renewtex.</u>	This innovation network aims to transform the carpet and rug industry from linear to circular. Currently, it operates as a moderated matchmaking platform, connecting people to advance shared ideas and needs through technological projects. It also supports companies in finding investment strategies and launching projects.	Public and private network	active	textile	Good practices + Reserach + Dissemination	Collaborative Network	
<u>Dialogplattforme Recycling</u>	Platform for strengthening the contribution of secondary raw materials to the security of supply of raw materials. In dialogue with industry, science and administration, options for action are developed as part of the recycling raw materials dialogue platform with the aim of improving the safe and sustainable supply of metals and industrial minerals from secondary raw material sources to German industry from recycling.	Public and private network	Ended in 2023	metals and industrial minerals	consulting services	Good practices + Reserach + Dissemination	
Austria							

circulareconomyforum.at	This platform fosters learning and dialogue to promote knowledge exchange and identify synergies among companies, politics, science, research, and design. It operates innovatively, supports comprehensive transformation, links interdisciplinary expertise, and facilitates decision-making. The forum promotes new business partnerships, enhances the Austrian circular economy, and encourages collaborative projects and initiatives.	Public and private network	active	Circular Innovation Ecosystem, knowledge sharing (thematic seminars and workshops , company seminars)	Good practices + Reserach + Dissemination	Consulting and Support
Swiss						
genie	Genie.ch is a collaborative platform dedicated to promoting and creating industrial ecology projects. It provides concrete answers to the Geneva entrepreneurs who wish to move towards greater respect for the environment while meeting their economic performance objectives.	Public and private network	active	energy, construction, waste valorization	Good practices + matching + resource sharing + Dissemination	Consulting and Support
Romania						
rocesp.ro	A network platform aimed at creating a national hub for circular economy initiatives, experiences, and expectations in Romania, promoting a unified Romanian approach in Europe. Its objectives include disseminating knowledge, fostering dialogue and synergies, mapping good practices, integrating initiatives, facilitating cross-sectoral interactions, and showcasing Romanian excellence in circular economy. The platform operates under a charter of goals and regulations, ensuring shared commitment among involved organizations to achieve common objectives.	Public and private network	ended in 2021 (still online)	private institutions, academia, research organizations, NGOs, and businesses	Good practices + Reserach + Dissemination	DisseminationFacilitation and Networking •Training and Workshops

<p><u>Coaliția pentru Economie Circulară (CERC)</u></p>	<p>The Circular Economy Coalition (CERC) promotes the EC Circular Economy Action Plan in Romania, fostering new markets, business models, and economic growth. It supports its members in transitioning to a circular economy and engages with national and EU policies to enhance the legislative framework. CERC seeks strategic partnerships with local and international organizations and academia to develop studies and support circular economy programs.</p>	<p>Public and private network</p>	<p>active</p>	<p>businesses, public institutions, and NGOs.</p>	<p>Good practices + Reserach + Dissemination</p>	<p>DisseminationFacilitation and Networking •Training and Workshops</p>	
<p>Slovacchia</p>							
<p><u>circular-slovakia.</u></p>	<p>The Slovak Environmental Strategy prioritizes transitioning to a circular economy. Circular Slovakia, established in October 2019 by the Slovak Ministry of Environment, the Embassy of the Kingdom of the Netherlands, and other key stakeholders, aims to facilitate discussions and partnerships between the public and private sectors. It shares national and international good practices and raises awareness of the circular economy.</p>	<p>Public and private network</p>	<p>active</p>	<p>agriculture, forestry, fisheries, mining, manufacturing , water supply, waste management, construction, trade, transport, accommodati on, food services, information and communicati on, finance, professional services, public administration , education, healthcare, and arts.</p>	<p>Reserach + Dissemination</p>	<p>Consulting and Support</p>	

esimbioza.fis	e-Symbioza is a Slovenian e-platform for waste resource exchange. Over an extended period in valorization of one company's waste as a valuable raw material for another remained untapped due to the absence of a straightforward connection between businesses.	Public and private network	not active anymore	Waste from the extraction of minerals, mud, paper, and hazardous waste			
Serbia							
circulareconomy-serbia	The Digital Platform for Circular Economy (CE HUB) by the Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Serbia provides business communities with information on improving knowledge, EU events, grants, financial support, business models, and potential savings from transitioning to a circular economy. It aims to connect businesspeople across sectors, showcase best practices and projects, and foster future cooperation and investments with national and international partners.	Public and private network	not updated since 2023 (still online)	waste management, manufacturing, energy, agriculture, and public institutions.	Good practices + Reserach + Dissemination	DisseminationFacilitation and Networking •Training and Workshops	
Czech Republic							
Cyrkl	international green tech that deals with consultancy focused on the management of waste in a circular way. Platform that functions as a marketplace where you can sell or buy industrial waste, by-products, secondary raw materials or recycled materials.	private	active	Different industry/waste categories	Marketplace	Consultancy	
Finland							
sitra.fi	The Finnish Innovation Fund Sitra collaborates with partners to pioneer sustainable well-being and shape the future. Since 2015, Sitra has led efforts towards a circular economy, aiming to reduce consumption and fossil fuel use. Its current focus includes supporting a fair transition to a circular economy, promoting sharing-based business models, advancing circular trade policies, understanding digitization's environmental effects, and safeguarding biodiversity through the circular economy.	Public and private network	active	industries such as waste management, manufacturing, energy, and consumer goods	Good practices + Reserach + Dissemination	DisseminationFacilitation and Networking •Training and Workshops	

Norway							
empower.eco	Digital platform that works as deposit system for plastic waste. Empower is a Norwegian start-up using blockchain technology that rewards community action collects plastic waste giving new value to it.	private	active	Plastic, municipalities, business associations, public administrations, private companies, technological parks	Consultancy	Marketplace	
Lituania							
https://circuloop.lt/app/	circuloop is a platform helping its participants to design circular products & services . It provides a variety of resources and a circular design journey to increase circularity. This platform is intended to be used as a pre-accelerator for circular design.	Public and private network	active	eco design	Good practices + Reserach + Dissemination	Technology transfer • Tool/worker sharing	

In order to develop a proposal for a new platform to foster IS at the NODES territory, the present analysis suggests that it should incorporate a range of features that facilitate the efficient use of resources, promote collaborations, and enable the sharing of knowledge and services. At the end of the research phase the key features identified of such a platform include:

- **Knowledge Sharing and Expert Collaboration**

A relevant example is CircleAid by Vlaanderen Circulair, it proposes a feature that aims to connect users with experts in various fields relevant to the circular economy. CircleAid by Vlaanderen Circulair exemplifies this by showcasing different experts and specifying their areas of expertise. This helps users find the right expert for their needs, fostering collaboration and innovation. The platform can include detailed profiles of experts, their past projects, and how they can assist businesses or individuals in implementing circular practices.

- **Community and Networking Features**

Building a community around the platform can enhance user engagement and collaboration. Forums, discussion boards, and networking opportunities allow users to share ideas, seek advice, and form partnerships. This sense of community can drive collective progress towards a more circular economy.

- **Advanced Tagging System for User Needs**

An advanced tagging system is crucial for helping users identify and select their specific needs effectively. Genie.ch provides an excellent example with its robust tagging system, which allows users to precisely define their requirements and find corresponding solutions or partners. Tags can be based on various criteria such as industry, material type, service required, and more, enabling a highly customised and efficient search process.

- **Resource Marketplace and Material Exchange**

Many digital platforms for the circular economy include a “marketplace” where users can exchange resources and materials. This can help reduce waste by ensuring that materials are reused or recycled instead of discarded. The marketplace can list available materials, their condition, and potential uses, facilitating transactions between businesses looking to buy or sell surplus resources.

- **Comprehensive Search Menu and Service Overview**

Another essential feature is an intuitive search menu that provides a clear overview of the different services offered. The platform we took as example is Cyrkl, that stands out with its user-friendly interface that allows users to easily search for and select multiple services. This functionality ensures that users can find exactly what they need without sifting through irrelevant information. The platform should offer filters, categories, and a comprehensive search functionality to streamline the user experience.

- **Case Studies and Best Practices Database**

Many digital platforms dedicated to the CE and IS often include a repository of case studies and best practices, which can be a source of inspiration for users and practical examples of circular economy principles in action. This feature can highlight successful projects, detailing the steps taken, the challenges faced and the results achieved. It serves as an educational tool and a source of motivation for users to adopt circular practices. This section typically includes:

1. Descriptions of Successful Initiatives: These provide an overview of the strategies and business models employed by various companies to implement circular economy principles. The descriptions often highlight key achievements and the impact of these practices on sustainability and economic performance.
2. Detailed Reports: Some platforms offer downloadable PDF reports that delve deeper into the specifics of each case. These reports usually cover the planning, execution, and outcomes of the initiatives, providing valuable insights and lessons learned.

Often this repository of best practice is proposed as in many case studies in our analysis, on a **geographic map**. A geographic map feature that integrates a database of best practices is an invaluable tool for a digital platform in the circular economy. This interactive map can visually display real-world examples of successful circular economy initiatives, categorised by location.

Users can explore various regions to see how different communities and businesses have implemented circular practices. By clicking on specific markers on the map, users can access detailed case studies, including descriptions of the projects, the challenges faced, the solutions implemented, and the outcomes achieved.

Moreover, this feature can facilitate networking opportunities by identifying nearby experts, collaborators, or resources, thereby enhancing regional circular economy networks and promoting localised sustainability efforts.

- **Chamber of Commerce Platforms**

Platforms operated by chambers of commerce or similar organisations often function as databases or showcases for businesses exemplifying circular economy practices. They provide:

Case Studies: Detailed profiles of companies that have successfully adopted circular economy models. These profiles typically include information on the business's background, the circular strategies implemented, and the benefits realised.

Networking Opportunities: Tools and resources for businesses to connect, share knowledge, and explore potential collaborations.

- **Data-Driven Insights**

Providing real-time data and analytics can help users make informed decisions. This feature can track resource usage, resource logistic information, and other relevant metrics, offering insights that can lead to more efficient exchange. Data visualisation tools can help users understand the economic and environmental convenience of the exchange.

By integrating these features, a digital platform for the circular economy can effectively support businesses and individuals in their journey towards sustainability. Such a platform not only facilitates resource efficiency and waste reduction but also fosters a collaborative environment where knowledge and expertise are readily accessible.

CONCLUSIONS

This report has provided an overview of IS initiatives, mapping both EIPs and Regional IS at the international level, with a special focus on the European experiences. Furthermore, the in-depth analysis of digital platforms promoting IS activities has highlighted important information to guide the creation of the platform envisaged by the GRIP project (RM6.5). The results discussed are crucial to understand the feasibility of IS implementation at the territorial level, and, therefore, its replication possibilities. IS is indeed a key strategy to tackle the ecological burden whilst pursuing an economic advantage and, within the GRIP project context, it shows the potential to integrate all the technologies in the industrial structures already present in the NODES territory.

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MAPPING INDUSTRIAL SYMBIOSIS – II° part

INTRODUCTION AND AIMS OF THIS REPORT

The present report represents the second part of the Deliverable *Mapping Industrial Symbiosis* edited by RM6.4. As already stressed in *Mapping Industrial Symbiosis – I° part*, RM6 seeks to create a framework system with twofold objectives: (i) to valorise GRIP results and (ii) to demonstrate the feasibility of applying them in an integrated way, and eventually replicate them in different regions. The overarching idea is to integrate the different processing technologies developed within the GRIP project through the strategy of Industrial Symbiosis (IS). IS, therefore, is seen as a tool to both (i) combine different transformation platforms and (ii) implementing them at the territorial level. In other words, IS would serve to anchor the academic output of the research to the NODES territory.

The present document aims at illustrating the underlying methodology to implement new innovative technologies through the activation of IS networks at the territorial scale. In particular, the developed approach seeks to (i) uncover potential IS activities within the NODES territory, (ii) provide a framework to foster IS activation in different regions. Research is indeed pointless if it remains within the boundaries of the academia. Instead, research output should be oriented toward a territorial implementation, both to valorise research findings and to foster technological and knowledge transfer to the territory.

Figure 1. RM6.4 Flowchart

Following the RM6.4 flowchart (Fig. 1), the present report seeks to demonstrate the methodology to conduct which the highlighted section illustrates. The document is therefore structure into four main sections: the first one discusses the proposed overarching framework to implement and replicate the project, the second part illustrates the identification process to associate NACE-ATECO codes to GRIP-related production sectors and the following investigation conducted through the Chamber of Commerce, the third part deals with EER code identification and the related investigation on End-of-Waste (EoW) authorisations, finally the last section discusses the methodology for the indirect engagement of regional stakeholders.

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1.

THE IDEA METHODOLOGY

In order to facilitate the implementation of the innovative GRIP platforms at the regional level and to promote further replication in other territories, RM6 has developed an overarching framework: the IDEA methodology. It is structured in four steps: firstly, the **I**dentification of the field of interest; secondly, the **D**evelopment of innovations at the laboratory level; thirdly, the **E**ngagement of the actors who will have to apply the innovations; and, finally, the integrated **A**ssessment of large-scale application.

Figure 2. The IDEA methodology

The identification of the productive sectors of interest represents the first step of the IDEA methodology. It requires a preliminary sectoral analysis at the territorial level to identify the main regional productive chains. This allows to detect the most relevant industrial effluents on which to focus the development of innovative valorisation technologies developed by each RMs. The evaluation from the outset of the current regional situation is mandatory to deliver tangible solutions to the territory. In fact, to promote the creation of NODES innovation ecosystem, hence maximising the possible impacts of the project on the regional productive fabric, technological innovation should be founded upon an understanding of the specific territorial needs. The regional sectoral analysis is therefore crucial to forecast the potential diffusion of GRIP new technologies and the formation of IS networks within the NODES territory. Similar approaches have been widely adopted by both researchers and local authorities to implement IS networks. For instance, this is the case of SUN – Symbiosis User Network (Cutaia et al., 2017, 2015), the first Italian platform dedicated to IS implementation, or the Portuguese equivalent UpValue (Soares et al., 2023), as well as the successful British NISP programme which has been replicated in other European countries (Domenech, 2021; Patricio et al., 2022). The initial step of all these renowned projects consisted of the analysis of the local

productive chains. In light of the findings of the regional sectoral analysis, existing IS practices within the identified productive chains are investigated to understand their symbiotic potential.

On the same premises, the second step of IDEA consists of the development of technological platform for residues valorisation. This can be conceived as the scientific core of the discussed methodology as it directly addresses the environmental burden of waste generation. Once main regional productive chains are identified, the related residues and effluents are mapped and evaluated. Conversion technologies are then developed for at least one of the main residues arising from the abovementioned productive sectors. These techniques are studied and applied at the laboratory level with the ultimate objective of attaining the highest technological readiness level (TRL) to foster industrial applications in the territory. The potential for IS is investigated not only at the sector level, as already mentioned, but also among the various processing platforms. In fact, as in any production process, there are inputs and outcomes (including residues), there is the possibility of creating synergies between different transformation processes.

To promote the territorial implementation of new technologies, the third IDEA phase regards the stakeholder's engagement. Within this context, stakeholders are mainly represented by production units, like industries and manufacturers, and, to a lesser extent, public bodies, such as the Chamber of Commerce, Regions or Municipalities. The collaboration between academy, industry and public bodies contributes to the effective application, test, and implementation of the developed conversion technologies. Regarding the productive units considered as possible stakeholders, three main typologies are identified: i) companies working on the project application domains, therefore in demand of innovation, ii) technology companies which can further develop the developed conversion platforms, iii) transport and logistic companies. Companies can be directly engaged in two principal ways: through the collaboration with the involved research laboratories, to which they supply their productive residues to promote industrial research, and through the application to specific calls that provide funding and grants for their internal industrial research and experimental projects. Furthermore, companies can be indirectly engaged through a variety of channels, including interviews, surveys, focus groups, and dissemination events.

Finally, the last step of IDEA pertains to the integrated assessment of large-scale applications. Multiple assessments have to be conducted for each processing platform in order to cover different perspectives, i.e., environmental preferability, economic convenience, technical efficiency, normative requirements, market opportunities, social acceptance, etc. Particularly, the assessment has to be conducted not solely on the single conversion technique, rather on the potential implementation within IS networks.

THE IDEA METHODOLOGY APPLIED TO GRIP PROJECT

The IDEA methodology has been developed as overarching framework to promote the creation of IS networks implementing innovative conversion techniques. Therefore, it can be conceived as a general approach to facilitate the implementation of the GRIP project within the NODES area, and its replication in other territories.

The IDEA methodology has been implemented and adapted in relation to the GRIP project, as explained below in detail.

The **sectoral analysis** was undertaken at the outset of the project design phase. Six main productive sectors resulted of particular relevance: i) mining and quarrying, ii) agrifood, iii) textile, iv) plastic, v) wastewater, and vi) CO₂. Not surprisingly, they correspond to those referred to as "*priority value chains*"

within the EU normative framework (European Commission, 2020), that also include Electronics and Batteries. Although Electronics and Batteries did not emerge among the primary regional productive sectors, their global significance renders research in this domain a matter of paramount importance.

Therefore, research groups (RMs) have been organised to investigate and **develop new and innovative technologies** seeking to reduce the environmental impact of the aforementioned productive chains, including some investigation on the recovery of critical raw materials from industrial effluents. Investigation domains have been allocated considering the academic background of each research groups. The following table (Table 1) illustrates the organisation of GRIP research modules (RMs). The development of specific conversion techniques for residue streams is conducted by six RMs (namely, RM1, RM2, RM3, RM4, RM5, RM7, also labelled as *applicative RMs*). For each domain, a number of residue streams are investigated to understand which ones have the greatest potential for valorisation routes.

Table 1. GRIP research domains.

RM	Research Area	Residue streams
1	Mining and Construction	C&D waste, Fly and Bottom Ashes, Ceramic and Quarry waste
2	Agrifood	Cocoa residue, Wine pomace, Grape seeds, Tomato skins ...
3	Plastic and Textile	Textile spinning offcuts, Plastic offcuts and waste...
4	Wastewater	Wastewater from textile industry, fish farming and sewage ...
5	CO ₂	Flue Gas of Power Plants
6	Industrial symbiosis	Framework system
7	Agrifood	Oil pomace, Olive leaves, Almond husks, Artichokes leaves ...
8	Urban Waste Management	Public Value

The **engagement of regional stakeholders** has been conducted both directly, through the strict collaboration between research laboratories and their industrial suppliers and through the NODES call *bandi a cascata*, and indirectly through the investigation conducted by the RM6. Regarding to the latter, the engagement of companies located in the NODES territory has been based on a regional Chamber of Commerce survey. Starting from the identification of NACE codes for each productive sector involved within the GRIP conversion platforms, companies have been identified through an investigation on the register of the Chamber of Commerce of Piedmont and Lombardy. The adopted methodology will be discussed in detail in section 2. Approaches based on NACE codes have been widely utilised in several research related to IS and waste management (Amicarelli et al., 2023; Del Borghi et al., 2008; Leurent et al., 2018). Identified companies are targeted to investigate both existing and potential symbiosis within the GRIP domains. This is done through the submission of a questionnaire and the organisation of dedicated event of sensibilisation and incubation.

Finally, the **integrated assessment** of both processes and final product firstly consists of a technical evaluation of the processing platforms to understand their industrial scalability potential. This is directly conducted by the applicative RMs (RM1-7), whilst the assessment of economic, social, and environmental sustainability is demanded to RM6. Particularly, the integrated assessment conducted by

the RM6 encompasses both single technologies and their systemic combinations within hypothetical IS network.

2.

PRELIMINARY RESEARCH TO INVESTIGATE POTENTIAL IS WITHIN THE NODES TERRITORY

This section presents the preliminary investigations conducted with the aim of engaging local stakeholders. First, the valorisation platform developed by the applicative RMs (RM1-7) is discussed, drawing the residue's trajectory from the original sector in form of scrap, to another economic sector as input for new process. Then the first in depth analysis aimed at identifying the NACE and ATECO codes encompassed by such valorisation routes are presented. It follows the investigation on the existing exchanges between the aforementioned sectors, identified by the proper ATECO code, on the Elenco Sottoprodotti platform. Finally the Chamber of Commerce survey is briefly presented.

DRAWING THE VALORISATION ROUTES OF GRIP RESIDUES

To investigate the potential of implementation of GRIP innovative platforms within the NODES territory, the first step conducted by RM6 consisted of the definition of each valorisation route developed by the applicative RMs. This was done through periodic interviews with RM leaders and Task leaders. These meetings were held with the objective of understanding and deepening the current state of the art in the development of GRIP conversion platforms. Particularly, to deepen the valorisation routes eight dimensions were considered, as explained in Table 2.

Table 2. Considered dimensions to draw the valorisation routes encompassed by GRIP platforms.

Dimension	Description
Residue (input)	The specific residue stream to be valorised.
Industry of origin	The production process from which the residue arises.
Business as Usual Scenario	Traditional alternative to recover or dismiss the residue.
Treatment process	The innovative GRIP technological platform to convert
Recovered and valorised material (output)	The output of the transformation process, therefore secondary raw materials or other types of End-of-Waste. Despite being the output of the valorisation process, it also represents the input for a further production process.
Industry of destination	The production process, or the broader productive sector, in which the valorised residue can be utilised.
Alternative to recovery	The raw material or product traditionally utilised in the latter production process.
Scale of application	Technological Readiness Level of the processing platform: laboratory, pilot project or industrial scale.

Eventually, to gather further information potential normative, economic, or social barriers to the implementation of GRIP platforms have been investigated during the interviews. However, research laboratories, being scientific-oriented, were only able to highlight main legislative references, without pointing out any specific barriers. Results of the interviews were synthesised in a database, which is shown below.

Table 3. Residues' valorisation routes.

R M	T A S K	RESIDUE	INDUSTRY OF ORIGIN	BAU SCENARIO	TREATME NT PROCESS	OUTPUT PRODUCT	INDUSTRY OF DESTINAT ION	ALTERNAT IVE TO RECOVERY	SCALE	MAIN REGULAT ORY BARRIERS
R M 1	1.1	Fine mineral waste	Mining (quarrying); Treatment of Construction and Demolition waste (CDW) and excavated soil and rocks (TRS).	Landfill for inert materials; Backfill of impaired sites for environmental rehabilitation.	Mixing aggregates with organic by-products to produce artificial substrate mixtures.	Technosoil (revegetable substrate)	Environmental remediation and reclamation of compromised sites	Use of virgin raw material: natural soil	Laboratory; Pilot projects	Pollutant content limits as in TUA 152/06 (e.g. table 1, columns A and B for habitable areas and industrial areas)
	1.2	Bottom ashes	Municipal solid waste (MSW) and special non-hazardous waste incinerator.	Recovery in the cement industry as aggregate, roadbeds (not in Italy).	High-temperature inertisation, inertisation with geopolymer formation.	Ceramic products; high-value cement materials (belitic cement)	Cement industry; Ceramic industry	Extraction of natural cementitious material	Industrial	ND
	1.3	Fly ashes	Municipal solid waste (MSW) and special non-hazardous waste incinerator.	Landfilling of hazardous materials (in Italy), after treatment attempts recovery as additional material.	Reduction of PTE through leaching cycles and subsequent recovery of leached metals through plant-microorganism consortia,	Geopolymers for ceramic products	Cement industry	Extraction of natural cementitious material	Industrial	ND
	1.4					Metal recovery	Environmental remediation and reclamation of compromised sites	Extraction of virgin metal material	Laboratory	ND

					inertisation in geopolymers.					
1.5	Fired ceramic scrap	Ceramic industry.	Recovery in the cement industry both as cement and as aggregate; recovery in the ceramic industry as aggregate/founding agent; landfilling as inert waste.	Grinding at different grain sizes, blending different types of ceramic waste.	Ceramic products	Cement industry; Ceramic industry	Extraction of natural cementitious and ceramic material (quartz and/or feldspar)	ND	ND	
1.6	Industrial mineral waste (granite and carbonate waste)	Quarry and plant waste from quarrying silicate and carbonate materials (mainly granite and marble).	Transfer to permanent storage areas in quarries (extractive landfills), environmental rehabilitation activities in quarries.	Crushing and screening to obtain suitable particle size classes for base material (for footpaths). Fine fraction added to soil and organic component for the production of technosolids.	Technosoil (revegetable substrate) and/or basic material for footpaths (drainage material, dust suppression)	Animal husbandry (Footing in animal movement areas, bedding or working fields)	Integration of other waste material from mining or marble processing (e.g. feldspathic sands, quartz sands, carbonic waste) into the technosuolo	Laboratory; Pilot projects	TUA dlgs 152/06, CER code list, European leaching standard UNI-EN 12457. Special attention to safety related to respirable dust production (silica et al.)	

1.7	Course mineral waste	Mining (quarrying); Treatment of Construction and Demolition waste (CDW) and excavated soil and rocks (TRS).	Deposition; backfill aggregate; roadbed aggregate and other types of recovery.	Upstream treatment of heterogeneous waste material: crushing, screening, magnetic separation, possible pneumatic separation for fine elements. Selection of mix materials for the production of reinforced soil for civil and infrastructure works.	Certifiable aggregates for civil, infrastructure, construction and environmental uses	Civil/infrastructure works (e.g. road foundations, embankments, morphological recovery of impaired sites, asphalt aggregate), construction (e.g. concrete, mortars), environmental (environmental recovery and morphological remodelling of impaired areas)	Use of natural aggregates (and consequent opening of new borrow pits).	Laboratory; Pilot projects	TUA 152/06; D.lgs 117/08; environmental constraints (water, soil, air impacts)
1.8	Quarry waste of silicate waste	Mining dumps, quarries of silicate materials (Luserna stone, Bargiolina, kaolinised Gneiss, lake granites, Traversella diorite).	Possible comminution, often put to deponia (or to fill gaps) without prior treatment.	Search for the presence of CRM in mining waste, focus REE (separation treatment to mineral concentrate).	Feeding material per l'arricchimento in REE (ed eventuali altri CRM)	CRM for digital/green transition. It is emphasised that, at present, processing for REE recovery is not present (on an industrial level) at Italian/European plants (a	Use of s.s. mineral resources or concentrates obtained from the treatment of WEEE	Laboratory	Legislative Decree 117/08; regional regulations (DPAE) environmental constraints (water, soil, air impacts)

							plant is being set up in Estonia).			
1.9	Digestate from Organic Fraction of Municipal Solid Waste	Anaerobic digestion plants for gas production.	Composting; landfilling.	Precipitation of struvite from digestate after enzymatic and bacterial pretreatment.	Struvite mineral fertiliser	Agriculture	Chemical fertilisers	Laboratory	Commission delegated regulation (EU) 2021/2086	
1.10	Straw bedding, rice husks, wood chips	Livestock breeding.	Farmland fertilisation; landfill; incineration.	Pyrolysis and subsequent incorporation of waste material from mining or marble processing (feldspathic sands and/or quartz sands and/or carbonaceous waste) into the technosol.	Technosoil (revegetable substrate)	Animal husbandry (Footing in animal movement areas, bedding or working fields);	Use of virgin raw material: natural soil; or use of exclusively mineral vicariants.	Laboratory	Directive 91/676/CEE	
1.11					Biochar	Energy sector (hydrogen energy storage, batteries and supercapacitors)	Pyrolysis of biomass of both animal and plant origin	Laboratory	Directive 91/676/CEE	

	1.1 2	Waste from nuts processing (e.g. hazelnut)	Confectionery industry.	Incineration.	Use as such or creation of bioactive green extract (subcritical water extraction).	Bioactive extract	Livestock breeding (feed industry)		Laboratory	Ministerial Decree of 6 July 2005 - Criteria and general technical standards for the regional regulation of the agronomic use of vegetation waters and discharges from olive oil mills as per art. 8 of Legislative Decree no. 152 of 11 May 1999
	1.1 3	Waste from fruit, tuber, and olive processing	Agrifood industry.	Biogas production (anaerobic digestion); incineration.	Synthesis and extraction of Natural Deep Eutectic Solvents (NADES).	NADES food extracts	Livestock breeding (feed industry)			

R M 2	2.1	Cocoa residue from roasting beans	Agricultural and agrifood industry.	Energy recovery; Composting.	Green extraction of polyphenols, lipids and carbohydrates; valorisation through bio-based approaches (enzymes, fermentations), application of other innovative non-thermal techniques.	Antioxidant polyphenols, colouring ingredients, fibres with prebiotic activity	Food, nutraceuticals, cosmetics and pharmaceuticals	Use of conventional fiber and other antioxidants/colorants often labeled as food additives	Laboratory; Pilot projects	'Novel Food EU Directive EC 258-97 (economic burden); Absence of specific regulation with respect to precision fermentation - referring to date only to GMOs; Directive 2001/83/EC'
	2.2	Wine pomace	Wine industry.	Energy recovery; Composting.	Green extraction of polyphenols, lipids and carbohydrates; valorisation through bio-based approaches (enzymes, fermentations), application of other innovative non-thermal techniques.	Antioxidant polyphenols, colouring ingredients, fibres with prebiotic activity	Food, nutraceuticals, cosmetics and pharmaceuticals	Use of conventional fiber and other antioxidants/colorants often labeled as food additives	Laboratory; Pilot projects	

2.3	Grape seeds	Wine industry.	Energy recovery; Composting.	Green extraction of polyphenols, lipids and carbohydrates; valorisation through bio-based approaches (enzymes, fermentations), application of other innovative non-thermal techniques.	Antioxidant polyphenols, colouring ingredients, fibres with prebiotic activity	Food, nutraceuticals, cosmetics and pharmaceuticals	Use of conventional fiber and other antioxidants/colorants often labeled as food additives; lipids from other sources	Laboratory; Pilot projects	
2.4	Apple pomace	Agricultural and agrifood industry, including beverage industry.	Energy recovery; Composting.	Green extraction of polyphenols, lipids and carbohydrates; valorisation through bio-based approaches (enzymes, fermentations), application of other innovative non-thermal techniques.	Bioactive polyphenols (e.g. phloretin/phloridzin, anthocyanins)	Food, nutraceuticals, cosmetics and pharmaceuticals	Use of conventional fiber and other antioxidants/colorants often labeled as food additives	Laboratory; Pilot projects	

	2.5				Extraction of aqueous waste with high polyphenol concentrations.	Fermentable carbohydrate fractions that can be used as a basis for the production of probiotic microorganism	Nutraceuticals		Laboratory; Pilot projects	
	2.6	Tomato skins and seeds	Agricultural and agrifood industry.	Energy recovery; Composting.	Use of Deep Eutetic Solvents (DES) (mixture of menthol and fatty acids) for the extraction of carotenoids not in purity (they remain bound to DES).	Carotenoids mixed with DES	Cosmetics	Chemical agents	Laboratory; Pilot projects	

2.7	Cold-pressing residues of fruit seeds	Agrifood industry.	Energy recovery; Composting.	Green' extraction by non-thermal techniques, recovery of high value-added lipid fractions.	Lipids, bioactive substances, inert material	Food, nutraceuticals, cosmetics; residues: cement or new materials industry	Natural cementitious material	Laboratory; Pilot projects	'Novel Food EU Directive EC 258-97 (economic burden); Absence of specific regulation with respect to precision fermentation - referring to date only to GMOs; Directive 2001/83/EC'
2.8	Whey and buttermilk	Dairy industry.	Lactose recovery; whey protein recovery; feed utilisation.	Fractionation by UF; valorisation by fermentation and enzymatic treatments.	Minor bioactive protein fractions	Enriched functional foods, nutraceuticals	Other bioactive compounds with antimicrobial, immunomodulatory, ACE-inhibiting properties	Laboratory; Pilot projects	'Novel Food EU Directive EC 258-97 (economic burden); Absence of specific regulation with respect to precision fermentation - referring to date only to GMOs; Directive 2001/83/EC'

R M 3	3.1	Textile spinning offcuts (mixed composition)	Textile industry.	Energy recovery.	Grinding	Nonwoven	Textile	Aggregates for construction or fuel base.	Industrial	D.L. n. 152/2006, CAM, NTC 2018
						Monomers	Textile		Pilot project	ND
	3.2	Textile spinning offcuts (non-animal natural fibres)	Textile industry.	Energy recovery.	Enzyme treatment	Pre-preparation of monomers, reagents and starting materials	Plastic	Aggregates for construction or fuel base.	Laboratory	ND
							Pharmaceuticals		Laboratory	ND
							Fertiliser		Laboratory	ND
	3.3	Wheat bran	Agricultural industry.	Feed production.	Enzyme treatment	Pre-preparation of monomers, reagents and starting materials	Plastic	ND	Laboratory	ND
							Fertiliser	ND	Laboratory	ND
	3.4	Plastic waste (excluding PVC escluso; including mixed fraction)	Municipal solid waste (MSW) collection.	Mechanical recycling; incineration; landfill.	Pyrolysis	Porous graphitised carbon	Environmental services (pollutant capture in water; gas storage); electrochemistry (cell construction)	ND	Laboratory; Pilot projects	ND
	3.5	Agri-food scraps	Agricultural and agri-food industry.	Energy recovery.	Pyrolysis					ND
	3.6	Wood offcuts	Sawmill.	Energy recovery.	Pyrolysis					

	3.7	Pre and post consumer plastic waste	Plastic packaging industry; Municipal solid waste (MSW) collection.	Mechanical recycling; landfill.	Mechanical recycling with odour removal treatment	Odourless recycled plastic	Plastic, packaging	Ricorso a plastica vergine	Pilot project	ND
	3.8	Pre-consumer PU, PET waste	Plastic industry.	Mechanical recycling; landfill.	Chemical recycling, pyrolysis	Chemical elements and monomers	Plastic, packaging	Ricorso a plastica vergine	PU laboratory; PET industrial	ND
RM4	4.1	Textile Wastewater	Textile Dyeing industry ATECO 13.3	Standard bacterial treatment and further filtration; transfer to sewer.	Fungal treatment by live mycelium, immobilised enzymes or both	Wastewater with improved purification parameters and/or wastewater similar to that obtained with standard treatment but with logistical-economic savings	Sewage	Standard treatment	Laboratory	Legislative Decree No. 152 of 3 April 2006 'Environmental Regulations'.

4.2	Whey permeate concentrate	Dairy industry.	Food and feed additive; lactose extraction; disposal.	Fermentazione e distillazione	Bioethanol	Biofuels, energy	Fossil fuels or ethanol from non-waste sources	Laboratory, pre-pilot	Legislative regulation for the use of products from GMO processes
4.3	Wastewater from fish farming	Fish farming.	Standard purification treatment, further return of water to rivers.	Bioremediation with bivalve molluscs	Treated water	Release into the river	Standard treatment	Laboratory, pre-pilot	ND
4.4	Wastewater polluted by heavy metals and/or valuable organic compounds	Possibilità di collaborazione con Amag Reti Idriche Spa per fonti acquose inquinate	Standard purification treatment, further return of water to rivers.	Treatment of polluting compounds with porous materials obtained from natural sources (RM2/3) by absorption processes and hydrolytic/oxidative catalytic reactions under very mild conditions. Removal/degradation of pollutants (e.g. metal ions, dyes, drugs,	Treated water; metals made available again for possible reuse '.	Release into the river	Standard water treatment; Virgin metals	Laboratory, pre-pilot	ND

					surfactants, etc.) from the treated water with subsequent purification. The metals are eventually made available again for possible reuse.					
R M 5	5.1	CO₂	Flue Gas of Power Plant	Release to the environment	Capture on mineral support (zeolite or hydroxyapatite or MOF or other calcium-based). Through a thermal process, physical bonds are created that immobilise the CO ₂ on the substrate.	Mineral with CO₂ stock	Chemical industry (depollution)		Laboratory; Pilot projects	ND
					Thermochemical conversion via hot reactor with alumina or zirconium catalyst or copper and	Methanols (fuel, detergent or base for other chemicals)	Chemical or energy industry		Laboratory; Pilot projects	ND

					ceria (less expensive type).					
					Electrochemical conversion (electrochemical cells with different electrode combinations) at low temperature and low pressure, with external electric circuit and copper or palladium catalysts.	Alcohols or small hydrocarbons, in particular methanol (from copper catalyst) -see above methanol applications	Chemical or energy industry		Laboratory; Pilot projects	ND
						CO and formic acid (from palladium catalyst) - CO to be used as a base for other elements	Chemical and various industries		Laboratory; Pilot projects	ND
					Photochemical conversion by exposure to sunlight	Methanols (detergent or base for fuels or other chemicals)	Chemical and various industries		Laboratory; Pilot projects	ND
						Formic acid	Chemical and various industries		Laboratory; Pilot projects	ND

					Acetic acid	Chemical or food industry or cosmetics (ph regulator).		Laboratory; Pilot projects	ND
					Formaldehyde	Pharmaceutical industry and energy industry.		Laboratory; Pilot projects	ND
					Metano (piccole quantità)	Energy industry.		Laboratory; Pilot projects	ND
				Biochemical conversion by protein-rich algae (galdieria sulphuraria) capable of metabolising up to 90% of the CO2 supplied.	Pigments, vitamins and proteins	Food industry; Nutraceutical industry; Pharmaceutical industry; Cosmetic industry		Laboratory; Pilot projects	ND
				Biochemical conversion by enzymes, which, immobilised on an electrode, act as an electron bridge between CO2 and the electrode.	Formate (metabolic ingredient - intermediate - food source for bacteria that cannot convert CO2 directly).	Chemical industry		Laboratory; Pilot projects	ND

R M 7	7.1	Wine pomace	Wine industry.	Distillation; Spreading in the soil.	extraction using environmentally friendly techniques	Antioxidant extracts and food supplements	Cosmetics, nutraceuticals		Laboratory; Pilot projects	ND
	7.2	Wine lees	Wine industry.	Spreading in the soil.	extraction using environmentally friendly techniques	Antioxidant extracts and food supplements	Cosmetics, nutraceuticals		Laboratory; Pilot projects	ND
	7.3	Vegetation waters	Olive oil industry.	Spreading in the soil.	extraction using environmentally friendly techniques	Antioxidant extracts and food supplements	Cosmetics, nutraceuticals		Laboratory; Pilot projects	ND
	7.4	Oil pomace	Olive oil industry.	Extraction of refined oils.	extraction using environmentally friendly techniques	Antioxidant extracts and food supplements	Cosmetics, nutraceuticals		Laboratory	ND
	7.5	Artichokes leaves	Agriculture industry.	Spreading in the soil.	extraction using environmentally friendly techniques	Inulin	Cosmetics, nutraceuticals		Laboratory	ND
	7.6	Walnut shells	Agriculture and forestry industries.	Biomass boiler fuel.	extraction using environmentally friendly techniques	Antioxidant extracts	Cosmetics, nutraceuticals		Laboratory	ND
	7.7	Olive leaves	Olive oil industry.	Biomass boiler fuel.	extraction using environmentally friendly techniques	Natural dyes and antioxidants	Textile		Laboratory	ND

	7.8	Almond husk	Agriculture and forestry industries.	Feed production.	extraction using environmentally friendly techniques	Natural dyes	Textile		Laboratory	ND
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Once valorisation routes encompassed by GRIP technologies have been identified, two further investigations have been made: one related to the productive sectors, the other related to the residues. Following the IDEA methodology, in order to facilitate broader territorial survey, both sectors and residues have been associated with their related European statistical classification codes. Therefore, the NACE and ATECO classification have been used to identify productive sector, whilst residues have been categorised according to the European Waste Catalogue (EER codes) to facilitate the survey on EoW authorisations (ref. Section 4).

THE NACE-ATECO IDENTIFICATION

NACE codes are identified for each industry of origin (the sector producing the residue to be valorised by the GRIP platform) and industry of destination (the sector in which the valorised residue is utilised as input for a new productive cycle). Additionally, NACE codes have been converted into ATECO codes to perform a survey within the register of the Chamber of Commerce. If NACE is the classification utilised at the European level and from which all the national classifications of EU states are derived, ATECO refers to the Italian nomenclature, which is slightly different. Both ATECO list and NACE list are useful to pursue the objectives of the project; the former is indeed necessary to perform the investigation on the Chamber of Commerce register, and the latter allows to investigate sectoral IS activities and waste management practices within the European territory.

The following table (Tab. 4) presents the ATECO and NACE codes of the sectors of origin and destination of each RM research line. Following the taxonomy of the Chamber of Commerce, industry of origin and of destination have been labelled as **producer** of residues and **users** of residues.

The results show that producers encompassed by GRIP transformation platforms correspond to 41 codes; whilst on the users' side 36 codes have been identified. Without considering the distinction between producers and users, a total of 71 codes have been detected. Considering the NACE nomenclature, the identified codes mainly pertain to sections A (Agriculture, Forestry, and Fishing), B (Mining and Quarrying), C (Manufacturing), and E (Water Supply; Sewerage, Waste Management and Remediation Activities). Codes related to Manufacturing activities (C) resulted to be the most frequent, demonstrating that IS and other circular solutions are mainly applied among production units (secondary sector), and less applicable among service companies (tertiary sector). Other less represented sections are D (Electricity, Gas, Steam and Air Conditioning Supply), and F (Construction).

Table 4. NACE and ATECO classification of GRIP production sectors.

RM	TASK	PRODUCER	NACE	ATECO	USER	NACE	ATECO
1	1	Mining (quarrying); Treatment of construction and demolition waste (CDW) and excavated soil and rocks (TRS).	B8.11; B8.12; B8.99; E38.11; F43.11	08.11.00; 08.12.00; 08.09.09; 38.11.00; 43.11.00	Environmental remediation and reclamation of compromised sites	E39.00	39.00.09
	2	Municipal solid waste and special non-hazardous waste incinerator	E38.21	38.21.09	Cement industry; Ceramic industry	C23.51; C23.31	23.31.00; 23.51.00
	3	Municipal solid waste and special non-hazardous waste incinerator	E38.21	38.21.09	Cement industry; metal recovery	C23.20; C23.31; C23.51; C23.61; C23.69	23.20.00; 23.31.00; 23.51.00; 23.61.00; 23.69.00
	4	Ceramic industry	C23.31; C23.42.00	23.31.00;	Cement industry; Ceramic industry	C23.31; C23.42; C23.51	23.31.00; 23.42.00; 23.51.00
	5	Quarry and plant waste from quarrying silicate and carbonate materials (mainly granite and marble)	B8.11	08.11.00	Animal husbandry (Footing in animal movement areas, bedding or working fields)	A01.61	1.61.00
	6	Mining (quarrying); Treatment of Construction and Demolition Waste (CDW) and Excavated Soil and Rocks	B8.11; B8.12; B8.99; E38.11; F43.11	08.11.00; 08.12.00; 08.09.09; 38.11.00; 43.11.00	Civil/infrastructural works (e.g. road foundations, embankments, morphological recovery of impaired sites, asphalt aggregate), construction (e.g. concrete, mortars), environmental (environmental recovery and morphological remodelling of impaired areas)	C23.61; C23.64; F42.11; E39.00;	23.61.00; 23.64.00; 41.11.00; 39.00.09
	7	Silicate quarries (Luserna stone, Bargiolina, kaolinised Gneiss, lake granites, traversella diorite)	B08.99	08.99.09	CRM for digital/green transition: REE recovery	E38.32	38.32.30

	8	Anaerobic digestion for gas production	E38.21	38.21.01	Agricultural	A1.61 end user; C20.15 intermediary	1.61.00; 20.15.00
	9	Livestock breeding	A1.41; A1.42; A1.43; A1.45; A1.46; A1.47	01.41.00; 01.42.00; 01.43.00; 01.45.00; 01.46.00; 01.47.00	Animal husbandry (Footing in animal movement areas, bedding or working fields); Energy sector (hydrogen energy storage, batteries and supercapacitors)	D35.11	35.11.00
	10	Confectionery industry	C10.82	10.82.00; 10.89.00	Livestock breeding (feed industry)	C10.91	10.91.00
	11	Agro-food industry	A1.63; C10.31; C10.32; C10.41	01.63.00; 10.31.00; 10.32.00; 10.41.20	Livestock breeding (feed industry)	C10.91	10.91.00
2	1	Agricultural and agri-food industry	C10.82	10.82.00	Food, nutraceuticals, cosmetics and pharmaceuticals	C10.89; C10.86; C20.42; C21.10; C21.20	10.89.09; 10.86.00; 20.42.00; 21.10.00; 21.20.09
	2	Wine industry	C11.02	11.02.10; 11.02.20	Food, nutraceuticals, cosmetics and pharmaceuticals	C10.89; C10.86; C20.42; C21.10; C21.20	10.89.09; 10.86.00; 20.42.00; 21.10.00; 21.20.09
	3	Wine industry	C11.02	11.02.10; 11.02.20	Food, nutraceuticals, cosmetics and pharmaceuticals	C10.89; C10.86; C20.42; C21.10; C21.20	10.89.09; 10.86.00; 20.42.00; 21.10.00; 21.20.09

	4	Agricultural industry; Agribusiness; Beverage	C10.32	10.32.00	Food, nutraceuticals, cosmetics and pharmaceuticals	C10.89; C10.86; C20.42; C21.10; C21.20	10.89.09; 10.86.00; 20.42.00; 21.10.00; 21.20.09
	5	Agricultural industry; Agribusiness	C10.39; C10.85;	10.39.00; 10.85.03	Cosmetics industry	C20.42	20.42.00
	6	Agro-food industry	C10.41	10.41.20	Food, nutraceuticals, cosmetics; residues: cement or new materials industry	C10.89; C10.86; C20.42; C21.10; C21.20; C23.65	10.89.09; 10.86.00; 20.42.00; 21.10.00; 21.20.09; 23.65
	7	Dairy industry	C10.51	10.51.20	Enriched functional foods, nutraceuticals	C10.89; C21.20	10.89.09; 21.20.09
	3	1	Textile	C13.10	13.10.00	Textile	C13.95; C20.60
	2	Textile	C13.10	13.10.00	Plastics; Pharmaceuticals; Fertilisers	C20.16; C21.10; C21.20; C20.15	20.16.00; 21.10.00; 21.20.09; 20.15.00
	3	Agribusiness	C10.61	10.61.10	Plastics; Fertilisers NACE C20.16	C20.16; C20.15	20.16.00; 20.15.00
	4	Textile	E37.00 PUT TEXTILE	37.00.00	Agriculture; Textiles	A1.61; E36.00	1.61.00; 36.00
	5	Municipal solid waste collection; Sawmill	E38.11; C16.10	38.11.00; 16.10.00	Environmental services (pollutant capture in water; gas storage); electrochemistry (cell construction)	C23.99; C27.90; E39.00	23.99.00; 27.90.03; 39.00.00

	6	Plastics, Packaging, Municipal solid waste collection	E38.11; E38.32	38.11.00; 38.32.20	Plastics, packaging	C20.16; C22.21; C22.22	20.16.00; 22.21.00; 22.22.00
	7	Plastic	C22.21; C22.22; C22.23; 22.29	22.21.00; 22.22.00; 22.23.01; 22.23.02; 22.23.09; 22.29	Plastics, packaging	C20.16; C22.21; C22.22	20.16.00; 22.21.00; 22.22.00
4	1	Textile fibre dyeing industry	C13.30	13.30.00	Sewerage network	E37.00	37.00.00
	2	Dairy industry, whey collection and handling industries	C10.51	10.51.20	Biofuels, energy	C20.14	20.14.01; 20.14.09
	3	Fish farms	A3.22	03.22.00	Surface waters	E37.00	37.00.00
	4	Civil and industrial wastewater assimilated	E37.00	37.00.00	Surface waters	E37.00	37.00.00
5	1	Flue Gas of Power Plant	F35.11	35.11.00	Chemical industry (in the sense of depollution)	E39.00	39.00.09
					Chemical or energy industry	C20.11; C20.14; C20.41	20.11.00; 20.14.09; 20.41.10
					Chemical or energy industry	C20.11; C20.14; C20.41	20.11.00; 20.14.09; 20.41.10
					Chemical and various industries	C20.11; C20.14; C20.41; C20.42; C21.10	20.11.00; 20.14.09; 20.41.10; 20.42.00; 21.10.00
					Chemical or energy industry	C20.11; C20.14; C20.41	20.11.00; 20.14.09; 20.41.10

					Chemical and various industries	C20.11; C20.14; C20.41 C20.42; C21.10	20.11.00; 20.14.09; 20.41.10; 20.42.00; 21.10.00
					Chemical or food industry or cosmetics (ph regulator).	C10.89; C10.86; C20.42; C21.10; C21.20	10.89.09; 10.86.00 20.42.00; 21.10.00; 21.20.09
					Pharmaceutical industry and energy industry.	C20.11; C20.14; C21.10; C21.20	20.11.00; 20.14.09; 21.10.00; 21.20.09
					Energy industry	C20.11	20.11.00
					Food, nutraceuticals, cosmetics and pharmaceuticals	C10.89; C10.86; C20.42; C21.10; C21.20	10.89.09; 10.86.00; 20.42.00; 21.10.00; 21.20.09
7	1	Agricultural (wine-growing)	C11.02	11.02.10; 11.02.20	Cosmetics, nutraceutics	C10.86; C10.89; C20.42	10.86.00; 10.89.00; 20.42.00
	2	Agricultural (wine-growing)	C11.02	11.02.10; 11.02.20	Cosmetics, nutraceutics	C10.86; C10.89; C20.42	10.86.00; 10.89.00; 20.42.00
	3	Agricultural (oil)	C10.41	10.41.10	Cosmetics, nutraceutics	C10.86; C10.89; C20.42	10.86.00; 10.89.00; 20.42.00

4	Agricultural (oil) NACE C10.41	C10.41	10.41.10	Cosmetics, nutraceutics	C10.86; C10.89; C20.42	10.86.00; 10.89.00; 20.42.00
5	Agricultural (fruit and vegetables)	A1.63	01.63.00	Cosmetics, nutraceutics	C10.86; C10.89; C20.42	10.86.00; 10.89.00; 20.42.00
6	Agricultural/forestry	C10.39; C10.41; C10.61	10.39.00; 10.41.20; 10.61.40	Cosmetics, nutraceutics	C10.86; C10.89; C20.42	10.86.00; 10.89.00; 20.42.00
7	Agricultural (oil)	A1.63; C10.41	01.63.00; 10.41.10	Textile	C13.30	13.30.00
8	Agricultural/forestry	C10.39; C10.41; C10.61	10.39.00; 10.41.20;; 10.61.40	Textile	C13.30	13.30.00

The adoption of NACE – ATECO classification had three main purposes:

1. To facilitate the research on IS activities related to GRIP producer and user sectors within EIPs, at the international and European level. Therefore, the NACE list was utilised to narrow the EIPs' database (ref. Deliverable Mapping IS – I° part) to the sectors encompassed by the GRIP platforms. This activity was useful to understand what kind of IS practices are currently adopted within the production chains of interest.
2. To conduct a regional investigation within the Elenco Sottoprodotti platform to understand how many NODES companies working within GRIP production sectors are currently willing to engage in IS activities. Elenco Sottoprodotti is indeed a platform run by the Chamber of Commerce on which companies wishing to exchange their byproducts can register voluntarily and for free (Ref. Mapping IS – I° part). This activity was conducted to understand the potential interest toward IS by NODES companies.
3. To conduct a Chamber of Commerce survey to identify potential stakeholders to be indirectly engaged within the GRIP project.

Activities 2 and 3 were of crucial importance in providing the basis for the mapping of potential IS within the NODES area. The results of these investigation are discussed in the following sections.

ELENCO SOTTOPRODOTTI INVESTIGATION

Elenco Sottoprodotti is a platform run by the Chamber of Commerce encompassing the entire national territory. Companies can voluntarily register to exchange their byproducts. Therefore, they can join the platform as both producers and users of production residue.

The investigation on Elenco Sottoprodotti consisted of researching the GRIP ATECO codes with the aim of understanding how many producers and users are currently involved in residue exchanges, and to assess if these exchanges encompass the same production residues of GRIP. The investigation was conducted on February 18th and encompassed only the NODES territory. Therefore, the research was geographically restricted to Piedmont, Aosta Valley, and Como, Pavia, and Varese provinces.

41 ATECO codes were searched for producers, of which 28 yielded no results (i.e. no producers with such ATECO code voluntarily registered in the platform). Therefore, only 13 codes showed some results. 45 companies with one of the searched codes are registered as producers in the platform; in particular, 28 of them are associated to the ATECO code 35.11. However, these companies mainly offer digestate and animal slurry, whilst the GRIP platform encompassing such code sector involves the production of electricity and the production of flue gas and fly ashes as production residues.

On the user side, 36 ATECO codes were searched and only 4 of them provided some results. 73 companies with one of these ATECO codes were found to be registered as users in the platform. Particularly, 67 of them are registered with the ATECO 35.11 and are willing to receive residual biomass from agriculture and farming to produce energy.

Table 5 illustrates the results of the Elenco Sottoprodotti investigation, considering the Region or Province of reference. Only ATECO codes that led to some results are shown. In general, results of this investigation show a low propensity of companies related to GRIP production sectors to engage in IS activities, except with regards to the energetic sector.

Table 5. Results of the investigation within the Elenco Sottoprodotti platform.

	Piedmont	Aosta Valley	Pavia	Varese	Como
Producers					
08.12.00	1	0	0	0	0
01.41.00	2	0	0	0	0
01.42.00	1	0	0	0	0
01.47.00	1	0	0	0	0
10.82.00	1	0	0	0	0
11.02.20	1	0	0	0	0
10.39.00	3	0	0	0	0
13.10.00	1	0	0	0	0
22.21.00	2	0	0	1	0
22.22.00	1	0	0	0	0
22.20.09	1	0	0	0	0
13.30.00	0	0	0	0	1
35.11.00	23	0	3	2	0
Users					
D35.11.00	67	0	1	1	0
C20.16.00	0	0	0	1	0
C22.22.00	1	0	0	0	0
C13.30.00	0	0	0	0	2

THE CHAMBER OF COMMERCE SURVEY

In Italy, businesses are required to be registered to the Companies Register held by the territorial Chamber of Commerce. The Chamber of Commerce Survey (“*visura camerale*”) is an official information document listing all company’s details. Particularly, it shows the legal and personal aspects of the company, its name, legal form, registered office, tax code (which uniquely identifies the company), the type of activity carried out following the ATECO nomenclature, and many other elements relating to the administrative bodies and company offices. For the purposes of the project, only few aspects of the Chamber of Commerce Survey were considered as of interest. Particularly, the investigation sought to gather master data of the companies located within the NODES territory, registered with the ATECO codes retrievable within the GRIP project.

The research criteria to conduct the survey were:

- Location in NODES provinces (Aosta, Turin, Como, Cuneo, Asti, Alessandria, Biella, Novara, Pavia, Varese, Verbano-Cusio-Ossola, and Vercelli).
- Minimum number of employees of 10.
- One of the 71 identified ATECO codes as a primary activity code of the company.

The search for the 71 ATECO codes within the register of the Chamber of Commerce resulted in a list of 1763 companies located in the NODES area. Table 4 shows the geographical dispersion of the economic activities of interest within the NODES area, whilst Fig. 3 highlights the predominant economic activities for each zone.

Table 6. Geographical dispersion of economic activities of interest within the NODES area, according to the province.

PROVINCE	N° OF COMPANIES
Alessandria	87
Asti	70
Biella	187
Cuneo	280
Novara	71
Turin	347
Vercelli	47
Verbania-Cusio-Ossola	23
Como	255
Pavia	105
Varese	291

From a geographical perspective Turin resulted the province with the highest number of companies registered with one or more ATECO codes related to the GRIP sectors of activity. Considering the primary ATECO codes, the most common economic activities related to GRIP sectors resulted to be plastic manufacturing, farming, food production, and cement production.

Figure 3. Geographical dispersion of the economic activities of interest within the NODES area, according to the primary ATECO codes. Graph elaborated through Excel Power Map.

3.

EVALUATING LEGAL FEASIBILITY OF IMPLEMENTING GRIP PLATFORMS WITHIN THE NODES TERRITORY

To assess the effective possibilities of implementing GRIP platforms at the territorial level, it is imperative to give due consideration to the legal aspects involved. Therefore, this section discusses the valorisation routes encompassed by the GRIP project from a legal standpoint, with a particular focus on the EoW authorisations regime.

The underlying methodology to assess legal feasibility is articulated in four steps:

- 1) Analysis of applicable legislation: European and Italian legislation (see 1.d), as well as soft law and best practices, serve as the foundational framework for understanding the general characteristics of waste, byproduct and EoW.
- 2) Access to RECer platform: the RECER platform is the Italian platform containing all the EoW authorisation. It has been preliminary accessed to understand which wastes and processes are included, also with the aim to verify which authorisations have been already issued (in particular, on case-by-case basis).
- 3) Analysis from a legal standpoint of residues processed by GRIP platforms, to refine the RECER research.

MAIN DIFFERENCES BETWEEN BYPRODUCT AND WASTE

As already mentioned in *Mapping IS – I° part*, production residues encompassed by the GRIP valorisation platforms can be distinguished between waste and byproduct. Despite being a scrap of a production process, byproducts never become waste, and can be legally reintegrated in subsequent production cycles, without requiring any particular authorisation.

*Box SEQ Box * ARABIC 1 Byproduct's legal requirement according to 184-bis of D. Lgs. 152/06*

Conditions to be fulfilled to consider a substance or object byproduct and not waste:

- the substance or object is produced as an integral part of a production process, the primary aim of which is not the production of that item.
- further use of the substance or object in the same or in a subsequent production or utilization process, by the producer or third parties, is certain.
- the substance or object can be used directly without any further processing other than normal industrial practice.
- further use is lawful, i.e. the substance or object fulfils all relevant product, environmental and health protection requirements for the specific use and will not lead to overall adverse environmental or human health impacts.

On the other hand, waste is defined as “any substance or object which the holder discards or intends or is required to discard” (Article 183, par. 1, lett. a) of D. Lgs. 152/06). The meaning attributed to discarding is of crucial relevance to distinguish between waste and byproduct. Such notion refers to an

event that interrupts the relationship of use and utility between the user of the object and the object itself. This event should be attributable to the objective fact of the intervening unfitness for use and, in any case, to its actual release, whether intentional or compulsory, subject to any repossession and reuse by third parties. Therefore, waste is any substance or object no more utilisable in any production process. To allow the reintegration of waste, or its components, into new production cycles, waste must be properly recovered to gather the status of End-of-Waste (EoW). Once the object or substance gains such status it can be legally handled as secondary raw material.

*Box SEQ Box *ARABIC 2. EoW legal requirements according to Article 184-ter of D. Lgs. 152/06.*

Conditions to be fulfilled to cease the status of waste and entering under the EoW regime:

- **the substance or object is commonly used for specific purposes.**
- **a market or demand exists for such a substance or object.**
- **the substance or object fulfils the technical requirements for the specific purposes and meets the existing legislation and standards applicable to products.**
- **the use of the substance or object will not lead to overall adverse environmental or human health impacts.**

The concept of EoW is markedly distinct from that one of byproduct. In accordance with the legislation (Article 6 of Directive 2008/98/EC, subsequently amended by Directive 2018/851/EU 9, implemented in Italy with Article 184-ter of D. Lgs. 152/06), specific criteria for the recognition of EoW can be determined by both EU regulations and the member states' national normative. Furthermore, the Directive explicitly refers to the case-by-case approach, through which also local administration may also issue EoW permits, even in the absence of EU regulations or ministerial decrees.

Regulations on byproducts (184-bis Legislative Decree 152/06) and EoW (184-ter Legislative Decree 152/06) are an exception to the waste regulations and, as such, must be interpreted restrictively. Failure to comply with waste legislation may lead, inter alia, to the application of criminal sanctions (as well as, depending on the circumstances, to administrative liability of the entity pursuant to Legislative Decree 231/01).

THE EER CODES IDENTIFICATION

Periodical interviews with RMs leaders led to the identification of EER codes for each residue encompassed by GRIP valorisation technologies. Data on EER codes are crucial to conduct the investigation on the RECER platform in a more precise and focused way. Table 7 shows the EER codes identified for each input of the valorisation routes encompassed by GRIP platforms. It should be noted that the provided information is purely indicative. In fact, the assessment on incoming materials (residue) is ongoing. A case-by-case verification is still to be carried out for each project. Therefore Table 7 presents hypothetical EER codes, sometimes providing only a general indication of the waste class (first two digits). Definitive EER codes will be presented and discussed in the Deliverable edited by RM6.1, which will be focused on the legislative aspects.

Table 7. Hypothetical EER codes associated to GRIP residues.

RM	INCOMING MATERIAL	Hypothetical EER codes (All. D, Part IV, Legislative Decree 152/06)
1	Fine mineral waste	E.g. 170101, 170504, 170904, 010408, 191209
	Bottom ashes	190111, 190112
	Fly ashes	Incoming waste must be treated to possibly obtain recoverable EERs: 191202, 191203
	Fired ceramic scraps	101208
	Industrial mineral waste (granite and carbonate waste)	E.g. 170101, 170504, 170904, 010408, 191209
	Coarse mineral waste	E.g. 170101, 170504, 170904, 010408, 191209
	Silicate rock quarry waste	E.g. 170101, 170504, 170904, 010408, 191209
	Digestate from Organic Fraction of Municipal Solid Waste (“FORSU”)	190604
	Straw bedding, rice husks, shavings	/
	Waste from the processing of nuts (e.g. hazelnut)	/
	Waste from fruit, tuber and olive processing)	/
2	Cocoa waste (Selected from roasting beans)	020702, 020799
	Wine pomace	020702, 020799
	Grape seeds	020702, 020799
	Apple pressing waste	020702, 020799
	Tomato skins and seeds	020702, 020799
	Cold-pressed fruit stone residue	020702, 020799
	Whey and buttermilk	020702, 020799
3	Textile spinning offcuts (mixed composition)	04 02 22
	Textile spinning offcuts (non-animal natural fibres)	04 02 22
	Wheat bran	
	Plastic waste (excluding PVC escluso; including mixed fraction)	07 02 13

	Agrifood scraps	02 01
	Wood offcuts	03 01
	Pre and post-consumer plastic waste	07 02 13, 20 01 39
	Pre-consumer PU, PET waste	07 02 13
4	Textile Wastewater	/
	Whey permeate concentrate	02 05 01
	Wastewater from fish farming	/
	Wastewater polluted by heavy metals and/or valuable organic compounds	/
5	CO ₂	05
7	Wine pomace	02 07 02, 02 07 99
	Wine lees	02 07 02, 02 07 99
	Vegetation waters	/
	Oil pomace	02 03 99
	Artichokes leaves	02 01 03
	Walnut shells	02 01 03
	Olive leaves	02 01 03, 02 03 99
	Almond husk	02 01 03

INVESTIGATION ON EOW AUTHORISATIONS THROUGH THE RECER PLATFORM

Thanks to the collaboration of the Piedmont Region, it was possible to access to the Recer platform, which represents the national database of EoW authorisations. Access took place on two separate occasions. The first access allows for a preliminary analysis of the existing authorisations. In this regard, 895 authorisations have been found, including authorisations issued according to articles 208 of D. Lgs. 152/2006, or 214-216 of D. Lgs. 152/2006, or D. Lgs. 29-bis ff. of D. Lgs. 152/2006 (Integrated Environmental Authorisation), or Presidential Decree 59/2013 (Consolidated Environmental Authorisation) and adopted, for example:

- On the basis of EU Regulation 333/2011.
- On the basis of EU Regulation 715/2013.
- On the basis of EU Regulation 1179/2012.
- On the basis of Ministerial Decree 188/2020.
- On a “case-by-case” basis.

Moreover, as to the EoW criteria are concerned:

- (a) processes dealing with inert waste from construction and demolition (in particular, included in RM1) could be authorized, depending on the circumstances, according to Ministerial Decree 127/2024;
- (b) the innovative character of some of the processes will reasonably require an EoW authorization issued on a case-by-case basis according to article 184-ter of D. Lgs. 152/06.

Finally, in case of excavated soils and rocks, the classification as by-products as per Presidential Decree 120/2017 should be specifically verified.

To perform a focused analysis, only authorisation issued for waste with EER codes related to the GRIP platforms were researched. The following Table shows the preliminary results of the RECER investigation. Finalised results and related discussion will be included in the Deliverable edited by RM 6.1.

Table 8. Preliminary results of the RECER investigation.

INCOMING MATERIAL	Hypothetical EER codes	EoW authorisation regime (hypothetical)
Fine mineral waste	E.g. 170101, 170504, 170904, 010408, 191209	EoW Ministerial Decree from inert construction and demolition waste may be applied (Ministerial Decree 127/2024); For excavated soil and rocks, Presidential Decree 120/2017 should be verified
Bottom ashes	190111, 190112	Authorization on a case-by-case basis
Fly ashes	Incoming waste must be treated to possibly obtain recoverable EERs: 191202, 191203	See EU Regulations 333/2011, 715/2013
Fired ceramic scraps	101208	EoW Ministerial Decree from inert construction and demolition waste may be applied (Ministerial Decree 127/2024); Authorization on a case-by-case basis
Industrial mineral waste (granite and carbonate waste)	E.g. 170101, 170504, 170904, 010408, 191209	EoW Ministerial Decree from inert construction and demolition waste may be applied (Ministerial Decree 127/2024); For excavated soil and rocks, Presidential Decree 120/2017 should be verified
Coarse mineral waste	E.g. 170101, 170504, 170904, 010408, 191209	EoW Ministerial Decree from inert construction and demolition waste may be applied (Ministerial Decree 127/2024); For excavated soil and rocks, Presidential Decree 120/2017 should be verified
Silicate rock quarry waste	E.g. 170101, 170504, 170904, 010408, 191209	EoW Ministerial Decree from inert construction and demolition waste may be applied (Ministerial Decree 127/2024); For excavated soil and rocks, Presidential Decree 120/2017 should be verified
Digestate from Organic Fraction of Municipal Solid Waste (“FORSU”)	190604	Regulation 2019/1009/EU and Legislative Decree 75/2010 (case by case); possible regional legislation

Straw bedding, rice husks, shavings	/	For waste exemption: check requirements Interministerial Decree 5046/2016 (annex) + regional regulations Legislative Decree 75/2010 (case by case); possible regional legislation
Waste from the processing of nuts (e.g. hazelnut)	/	To be checked if by-products ex 184-bis Legislative Decree 152/06
Waste from fruit, tuber and olive processing)	/	To be checked if by-products ex 184-bis Legislative Decree 152/06
Cocoa waste (Selected from roasting beans)	020702, 020799	Authorisation on a case-by-case basis
Wine pomace	020702, 020799	Authorisation on a case-by-case basis
Grape seeds	020702, 020799	Authorisation on a case-by-case basis
Apple pressing waste	020702, 020799	Authorisation on a case-by-case basis
Tomato skins and seeds	020702, 020799	Authorisation on a case-by-case basis
Cold-pressed fruit stone residue	020702, 020799	Authorisation on a case-by-case basis
Whey and buttermilk	020702, 020799	Authorisation on a case-by-case basis

4.

INDIRECT ENGAGEMENT OF COMPANIES LOCATED WITHIN THE NODES TERRITORY

Companies detected through the Chamber of Commerce survey can be seen as local actors that can implement GRIP innovative technologies establishing new IS networks. Therefore, they are conceived as actors capable of anchoring the academic results to the industrial productive fabric of the region.

To engage them into the project as local stakeholders, an online questionnaire was designed to be submitted to them. The main purpose of the questionnaire was to ascertain the potential for IS network creation among the targeted companies, and to highlight any potential barriers or constraints to the successful implementation of this strategy. Therefore, the questionnaire is conceived as a preliminary step in the broader engagement process. Companies are indeed involved in the survey to assess their interest in IS, whilst, only in a subsequent phase they are engaged as potential users of the symbiotic exchanges that the project allows to establish through the implementation of the technological platform. Targeted companies can indeed decide to participate at dedicated event of sensibilisation and incubation.

QUESTIONNAIRE DESIGN

The questionnaire was designed with the support of Limesurvey, an online software to create surveys. It allows the design of questionnaire with different question types, even dependent on each other, and

organised in groups. It guarantees a high degree of graphic customisation of the structure, resulting a useful and immediate tool to perform online survey.

Online questionnaire allows for a lot of flexibility and customisability, furthermore they do not have the material constraints of the paper. For these reasons online questionnaire may contain more questions than the standard paper-based questionnaire. In this way, online survey results more precise and focused, and allows for a better classification of the gathered information. Moreover, logic conditions can be incorporated into an online survey, enabling the questionnaire to follow a conditional sequence contingent on the respondent's input. In other words, logic jump can be included within the survey, allowing the customisation of the questionnaire based on the respondent profile. Consequently, questions that are not aligned with precedent answer would not be displayed.

For the purpose of the research, the questionnaire structure was organised in 6 groups of questions, for a total of 38 questions:

1. The first part is related to the company master data (i.e., location, number of productive units, number of employees, turnover, etc.).
2. The second section is related to the company's market positioning (i.e, type of businesses among B2B, B2C, main geographical markets).
3. The third part investigates the company's main production process, especially in terms of material input and outcomes.
4. The fourth group investigates the company's existing symbiotic relationship with other partner companies, in terms of exchange of byproducts, waste, and End-of-Waste, both as producer and user.
5. The fifth section deepen the perceived barriers and incentives toward the application of IS as productive strategy. Barriers and incentives are evaluated through a Likert scale of 5 levels. In such way it is possible for the respondent to provide a neutral answer.
6. The final questions assess the company's willingness to be directly involved in the project.

To illustrate the questionnaire's structure, below (Fig. 4) an example is presented in English language (the questionnaire was instead submitted in Italian). Compiled answers are fictional and represent a hypothetical respondent who is currently implementing IS as both producer and user of production residue. In such way the entire questionnaire can be displayed. Otherwise, in case of a respondent does not currently adopt IS, after the section on the production process, he would proceed directly to the section on incentives and obstacles to IS implementation.

Before sending the questionnaire to the target companies, a pilot phase was conducted. During that stage the questionnaire was tested on a small sample of 17 respondent units. The pilot phase did not led to any substantial change on the structure. The final questionnaire was sent by email to the targeted companies between the 6th of June and the 20th of July. The reason of such time-lag can be explained as not all companies shared their mails with the Chamber of Commerce Register. Therefore, their contacts had to be researched through an online investigation.

COMPANY MASTER DATA

*Name of the company:

*Head office or operational unit:

Choose one of the following answers

In the event that the place of business and head office coincide, please select head office.

*Province of the responding unit:

Choose one of the following answers

The following questions are intended to be addressed to the responding unit.

*Please indicate the primary Ateco code:

The primary Ateco code indicates the activity that contributes most to the added value of production.

Please indicate any secondary Ateco codes:

[?](#) Secondary Ateco codes indicate the company's non-prevalent activities.

*Please, indicate the number of employees:

[?](#) Choose one of the following answers

- Less than 50
- Between 50 and 250
- More than 250

Indicate the annual turnover:

[?](#) Choose one of the following answers

- One million euro or less
- Between one million and fifty million euro
- Over 50 million euro
- No answer

MARKET POSITIONING

*Your company is configured as:

[?](#) Check all that apply

- Business to Business, wholesale trades
- Business to Consumer, targeting final consumers

*Which geographical market do you target?

[?](#) Check all that apply

- Regional
- National
- International

PRODUCTION PROCESS

*What is the main end product of your production process?

Animal feed

List the main raw materials involved in the production cycle of the good Animal feed:

Please fill in at least one answer

Maize

Malt

Rice

Peanut seeds

Oats

Meat bones

Water

Energy

Additives

In the space provided, indicate the main raw materials used in the production cycle.

Example:

1. Synthetic yarns
2. Natural dyes
3. Additives
4. Water

Up to 15 inputs can be listed.

*Indicate whether the inputs used within the production cycle are virgin material or not:

	Virgin material	Non virgin material
Maize	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Malt	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Rice	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Peanut seeds	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Oats	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Meat bones	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Water	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Energy	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Additives	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Non-virgin material refers to recycled material, mixed material, other end-of-waste and by-products.

List the main outcomes (scraps, by-products or waste) generated during the production cycle of Animal feed:

Please fill in at least one answer

Meat fat

Wastewater

Heat

Up to 15 outcomes can be listed, among which the final product intended for the market is not to be included.

Example:

1. Cuts and trimmings of fabric;
2. Post-dyeing waste water;
3. Heat.

Indicate whether the outcomes listed above are currently managed as waste or as by-products.

	Byproduct	Waste
Meat fat	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Wastewater	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Heat	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

A by-product is a residue originating from production of which it is not the primary purpose, which can be reused directly, or through processes of normal industrial practice, in a certain and legal manner within the same production cycle or in others.

The main difference between by-product and waste lies in the subjective will of the producer to dispose of the residue if it is waste.

Industrial Symbiosis

Does your company adopt industrial symbiosis in terms of production residue exchange and/or other related circular economy practices?

Yes No

Industrial symbiosis refers to a production strategy based on the exchange of production residues between different companies, reducing the overall volume of waste and encouraging the use of non-virgin materials.

Production residues refer, regardless of the solid, liquid, or gaseous state in which they are found, to by-products, waste and End-of-Waste generated during the production cycle.

To recirculate production residues, various circular actions are counted within industrial symbiosis, such as reuse, recycling, remanufacturing, redesign and energy recovery.

Do you implement Industrial Symbiosis as:

Choose one of the following answers

Producer of residues

User of residues

Both producer and user of residues

According to the terminology adopted by the Chambers of Commerce, a producer is defined as the actor who generates residues to be sent to the symbiotic exchange, while a user is defined as the one who adopts these residues as an input within another production cycle.

Please note that residues are defined as all those wastes, regardless of the solid, liquid or gaseous form in which they are found, generated during the production cycle, whether they are by-products, waste or end-of-waste.

*As a user, please select which inputs of the production process listed above are involved in the symbiotic exchange.

- 📌 Check all that apply
- 📌 Please select at least one answer

- Maize
- Malt
- Rice
- Peanut seeds
- Oats
- Meat bones
- Water
- Energy
- Additives

*Please indicate how the selected residues are utilised in your production cycle

	utilizzo
Meat bones	ground into flour, it is used as feed ingredient
Energy	to cook and dry

📌 E.g. waste water from a neighbouring plant used to feed the heat pump; use of fabric trimmings for garment manufacture.

*For each residue exchanged, indicate the location of the partner company.

	Within the same park or district	Within the same city	Within the same province	Elsewhere in the national territory	Elsewhere, in bordering EU territories	Elsewhere, in non-border EU territories	Elsewhere, in non-EU non-border territories
Meat bones	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Energy	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

*Provide an estimate in km of the distance to the company, or companies, with which you exchange the residue.

📌 Only numbers may be entered in these fields.

Meat bones	21
Energy	2

*As a user, how do you organise the collection and transport of production residues from producers?

	With only internal resources	With resources shared with other companies	Outsourcing the service to external providers
Meat bones	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Energy	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

*As a producer, please select which residues from the production process listed above are involved in the symbiotic exchange:

- Check all that apply
- Please select at least one answer

- Meat fat
- Wastewater
- Heat

Indicate, where known, the future use of the residue or, in general, the production cycle into which it will be reintroduced.

	Futuro utilizzo/ciclo produttivo
Meat fat	to produce energy

*For each exchanged residue, indicate the location of the partner company

	Within the same park or district	Within the same city	Within the same province	Elsewhere in the national territory	Elsewhere, in bordering EU territories	Elsewhere, in non-border EU territories	Elsewhere, in non-EU non-border territories
Meat fat	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Provide an estimate in km of the distance to the company, or companies, with which you exchange the residue.

Only numbers may be entered in these fields.

Meat fat

*As a producer, how do you mainly organise the transport of waste to users?

	With only internal resources	With resources shared with other companies	Outsourcing the service to external providers
Meat fat	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>

If there is more than one mode of transport for the same material, the mode of transport with the highest km should be chosen.

*As a manufacturer, what is the main mode of transport by which you organise your logistics?

	Road transport	Railway transport	Air transport	Maritime transport
Meat fat	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Incentives and barriers

*To implement industrial symbiosis, or related circular economy practices, have you benefited from economic-fiscal incentives?

Yes No

Examples of economic-fiscal incentives can be: direct economic contributions, tax relief

*What economic incentives has your company received or used to implement Industrial Symbiosis strategies or other Circular Economy practices?

Check all that apply

- Tax incentives
- Direct financing (grants or specific subsidies)
- Loans on favourable terms
- Support for the purchase of capital goods and sustainable technologies
- Tax reliefs for training and environmental certification

Other:

Other circular economy practices refer to all those actions aimed at extending the life cycle of a material or product (e.g. recycling, remanufacturing, redesign, etc.) and those aimed at reducing resource consumption (space sharing, utility sharing, logistics sharing).

For each incentive indicated, please provide a brief detail of how it was used.

Horizon programme grants

You may include any regulatory references or links to relevant sites.

*Express the importance of the following factors in promoting industrial symbiosis.

	Not relevant at all	Of little importance	Moderately important	Important	Extremely important
Economic convenience, in terms of lower production costs (e.g. cost of non virgin raw materials compared to traditional ones, avoided disposal costs, etc.).	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Improved image	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Fulfilment of commitments under industry framework conventions, code of ethics or other voluntary agreements, regarding environmental protection	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Restrictive environmental regulations	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Incentives and/or public contributions for ecological transition	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Access to external (private) funding linked to sustainability targets	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Collaborative environment (business networks, clusters, etc.)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>

*Express the importance of the following factors in hindering industrial symbiosis.

	Not relevant at all	Of little importance	Moderately important	Important	Extremely important
Regulations on EoW treatment parameters too restrictive	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Absence of economic incentives, including tax breaks	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Lack of appropriate technology	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Costs of technologies too high	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Costs of processing non-virgin raw materials too high	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Fluctuation and/or seasonality of secondary raw materials, leading to insecurity of supply	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Organisational difficulties (e.g. lack of appropriate skills)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Logistical difficulties in waste flow management and logistical costs	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Direct engagement

*Would you be interested in being involved in future outreach, experimentation and incubation activities on Industrial Symbiosis and related logistics management?

Si No

*Please provide direct contact details

Il commento è permesso solo quando l'opzione relativa è stata scelta.

E-mail

Tel.

Figure 4. Questionnaire design with fictional responses.

As of 1 September, only few responses had been received. Of 15 respondents, only 6 responded to the entire questionnaire, whilst the remaining only provides incomplete answers. This posed serious problems to the project advancement, particularly in terms of engaging regional stakeholders. The questionnaire was therefore shortened, eliminating the group sections pertaining to (i) market positioning, and (ii) master data. In particular, master data questions were eliminated because authors decided to adopt telephonic interviews instead of online format. Therefore, master data information is already known at the time of the interview (ref. Chamber of Commerce Survey). Moreover, a smaller sample (n=57) was invited to respond. It only comprises large companies (more than 250 employees). The decision was made considering that large companies are often representative of their production sector and, moreover, they often have a dedicated office to deal with environmental management.

The new survey is still ongoing. Telephonic interviews started on September 20th, after a pilot test of the new questionnaire structures. Results of these interviews are expected to be analysed and reported in the last report of the deliverable *Mapping IS* edited by RM6.4, which should be published in December.

FINAL REMARKS

The present report discussed the overarching methodology to embed academic research into the territory, or, in other words, to ease the knowledge and technology transfer to the local community. Valorisation routes implemented at the laboratory scale within the GRIP project are expected to be applied at the industrial level, whenever possible, by the regional stakeholders. To guarantee the feasibility of implementing such valorisation platforms a dedicated investigation on residues is being undertaken, through the identification of EER codes and the investigation on the RECER platforms. Understanding the state of the art of the current EoW authorisation regime is of crucial importance to assure the effective possibility to replicate GRIP technology by regional businesses. On the other hand, the investigation related to the identification of NACE-ATECO allows for the identification of potential stakeholders, or rather, potential users of GRIP new technologies. The Chamber of Commerce Survey led to the determination of the number of companies in the NODES area which may be willing to apply the new valorisation technique to both reduce their environmental impact and save production costs. This activity lays the foundation for the engagement of the regional economic actors, thereby representing the fundamental element that facilitates the transfer of knowledge to the local communities. Future Deliverables will discuss in detail both the EoW authorisation possibilities and the engagement of the regional stakeholders.

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NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

FLAGSHIP PROJECT GRIP

SPOKE N 2 – Title GREEN TECHNOLOGIES AND SUSTAINABLE INDUSTRIES

DELIVERABLE 6.4 III part
MAPPING LOCAL INDUSTRIAL SYMBIOSIS

Version history

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MAPPING INDUSTRIAL SYMBIOSIS

III part

AIM OF THE REPORT

The present report is intended to deliver the results of the investigation into Industrial Symbiosis (IS) practices and their attractiveness within the NODES territory. Particularly, it represents the last part of the broader study on IS practices and case studies (D.6.4 I, D.6.4 II). This third section of *Mapping Industrial Symbiosis* focuses on the NODES territory and its objective is to investigate and uncover IS practices occurring within the regional economic fabric. The adopted IS operational definition define IS as a “network of different productive actors belonging to different productive sector that establish a series of physical synergies to exchange and reuse production residues and effluents, optimising the overall resource use and thereby achieving a better system performance”. Therefore, following the nomenclature of the Italian Chamber of Commerce, IS involves two main actors: Producers of residues and Utilisers of residues. The primary objective of the study consists of providing insight into symbiotic practices implemented at the local level, i.e., Piedmont and bordering provinces of Como, Pavia, and Varese. The extent to which IS is employed by NODES companies is a key question, which is further investigated by examining the symbiotic profile of companies engaged in IS network and identifying the production residues most exchanged within symbiotic transactions. Furthermore, the present investigation seeks to evaluate which are the main perceived barriers and incentives to the adoption of IS according to the local companies. Understanding which are the key drivers to promote the application of IS is of paramount importance to effectively foster the industrial ecological transition. A sectoral analysis is furtherly employed in order to facilitate cross-case comparisons and to deepen the understanding of possible structural differences between manufacturing divisions.

Results of the present survey will be useful in providing guidance to policymakers and administrations in the formulation of effective frameworks agreements, with a view to fostering the ecological transition of industrial systems.

INTRODUCTION

As reported in D.6.4 Mapping Industrial Symbiosis II part, a total of 71 ATECO codes were searched within the NODES territory. Those codes were previously identified due to their pertinence to GRIP's transformation platforms. Indeed, they represent producer and utiliser codes associated with the production residues being valorised through the GRIP project. The Aosta Valley did not disclose any information, which meant that the results of the Chamber of Commerce investigation were limited to Piedmont and bordering provinces of Pavia, Varese and Como. Table 6 and Figure 3 of D.6.4 II part, showed the preliminary results of the Chamber of Commerce investigation, reporting the number of active companies for each Ateco code and their geographic distribution. A total of 1763 companies located within the NODES territory were identified. A questionnaire (fig 4 D.6.4 II part) was sent to them, with the aim of engaging local companies within the project and promoting the innovative GRIP's transformation platforms.

The distribution of the questionnaire started on 6 June and concluded on 30 November, 2025. This substantial timeframe was foreseen in order to ensure an adequate response rate. In fact, the initial response rate was found to be low, and the authors were compelled to devise alternative solutions to solve this gap. Initially, the sample size was reduced to consider only large companies, and the questionnaire modality was changed to telephonic interviews. However, a second attempt was made between 1 October and the final deadline, which, through the online administration, targeted the initial sample (1763).

At the end of the designated period, a total of 65 complete answers and 40 partials were obtained. These 105 questionnaires constituted the preliminary sample.

The present document is structured into four sections. The first section provides an overview of the sample, indicating its sectoral composition and the production processes included. The second section is related to IS practices declared by the companies, investigating which is the symbiotic profile of the respondents. The third section deepens the perceived incentives and barriers to the application of IS strategy. Finally, the last section reports the main findings of the survey.

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SAMPLE OVERVIEW

DATA CLEANING

To ensure the reliability and quality of the dataset, a rigorous data cleaning process was implemented based on the number of unanswered questions per observation. The goal was to retain only those responses that provided a sufficient level of information, whilst filtering out those that were incomplete or unreliable. Initially, responses with an excessive number of unanswered questions were removed, as they did not contribute meaningful data. This led to the exclusion of a portion of the sample. Additionally, one anomalous response (ID 56), which appeared to have been filled in randomly and lacked any analytical value, was discarded. In total, 44 observations were excluded, reducing the dataset from the initial 105 questionnaires (65 complete and 40 partial) to a final sample of 61 valid observations. This selection ensures that the dataset remains both representative and analytically robust for subsequent analyses. Consequently, the validity rate of the sample, defined as the proportion of retained responses relative to those collected, is 58%.

SAMPLE REPRESENTATIVENESS

The representativeness of the sample is evaluated by considering the sectoral distribution of the respondent units. Companies were indeed targeted on the basis of their ATECO codes, which correspond to those involved within the GRIP technology platforms. In order to facilitate the reading of the data, the sectoral classification shown in Graph 1 considers 7 macro sectors rather than the whole list of ATECO codes. Table 1 reports the correspondence between the two nomenclatures.

Figure 1. Sample sectoral representativeness.

With the exception of the Chemical and Energy sectors, the remaining divisions are adequately represented within the sample. The expected frequencies (F. CCIA) are slightly higher than the observed ones (F. RESPONSE) only in the cases of Agrifood and Petrochemical sectors. In fact, the Construction, Textile, and Waste sectors are even over-represented. The Electrical equipment and machinery industries are grouped as Others.

Table 1. Correspondence between sectors and ATECO codes.

Sector	ATECO codes
Agrifood	A01.41.00; A01.42.00; A01.43.00; A01.45.00; A01.46.00; A01.47.00; A01.61.00; A01.63.00; A03.22.00; C10.31.00; C10.32.00; C10.39.00; C10.41.10; C10.41.20; C10.51.20; C10.61.10; C10.61.40; C10.82.00; C10.85.03; C10.86.00; C10.89.00; C10.89.09; C10.91.00; C11.02.10; C11.02.20.
Chemical	C20.14.01; C20.14.09; C20.15.00; C20.16.00; C20.41.10; C20.42.00; C21.10.00; C21.20.09.
Construction	B08.99.09; B08.11.00; B08.12.00; C16.10.00; C16.24.00; C23.20.00; C23.31.00; C23.42.00; C23.51.00; C23.61.00; C23.64.00; C23.65.00; C23.69.00; C23.99.00; F41.2; F43.11.00; C22.23.01; C22.23.02; C22.23.09.
Energy	D35.11.00.
Petrochemical	C20.11.00; C22.21.00; C22.22.00; C22.29.00.
Textile	C13.10.00; C13.30.00; C13.95.00; C20.60.00; C13.2; C13.96.2; C14.13.1; C14.19.1; C14.39.
Waste	E36.00.00; E37.00.00; E38.11.00; E38.21.01; E38.21.09; E38.32.20; E38.32.30; E39.00.00; E39.00.09; E38.32.1.
Others	C27.90.03; F47.99.1.

SAMPLE DESCRIPTION

The geographical distribution of companies reveals a preponderance in the presence of companies in Piedmont, with 74% of companies located in this region. The remaining 26% of companies are instead dispersed throughout the three bordering provinces of Lombardy. A further analysis of the company size reveals that two-thirds (66%) of companies have a workforce of less than 50 people, while only 20% of companies employ more than 200 people (Figure 2). With respect to the turnover of companies, it is observed that two out of three companies (66%) report a turnover between one and 50 million euros, 13% report a turnover less than one million euros, and 21% report a turnover more than five million euros (Figure 3).

Figure 2. Sample by company size (employment).

Figure 3. Sample by company size (turnover in € / mln).

The sectoral composition of the sample appears to be highly diversified, with one in three companies belonging to the textile sector and one in five to the agri-food sector. The petrochemical sector (15%), the waste sector (15%) and the construction sector (13%) complete the list of respondents, with equal representation.

Figure 4. Sample by sector.

INSIGHTS INTO THE PRODUCTION PROCESSES OF THE RESPONDENTS

The production processes included in the sample are of various nature. Indeed, they cover different production sectors and different final products (Table 2). Furthermore, production lines vary even when the end product is the same, i.e. companies employ different production methods even within the same market segment. For instance, a significant variation can be observed in the cereal mix used to feed cows among respondents engaged in the production of milk and dairy products, indicating distinct input requirements. Similar arguments apply to the fabric manufacturing, where input requirements are highly dependent on the desired final properties of the textile product. In this context, different fibres, dyes, or textile auxiliaries can be employed, contingent on the desired final characteristics.

Table 2. Sample compositions, considering production sector and main final products of respondents.

Sectors	%	Companies' main products	%
Agrifood	20%	Animal feed	17%
		Flours	8%
		Milk and dairy products	33%
		Bakery products	8%
		Plant-based products	17%
		Wine	17%
Constructions	15%	Buildings	11%
		Concrete artifacts	22%
		HPL Decorative Laminates	11%
		Outdoor solar shower	11%
		Wooden artifacts	33%
		Recovered Inert Materials	11%
Petrochemical	15%	Extruded PVC profiles	11%
		Injection molded thermoplastic resins	11%
		Plastic packaging	44%
		Thermoplastic compounds and polymers	33%
Textile	33%	Cotton terry items	5%
		Dyed and printed textile	10%
		Fabrics	45%
		Household linen	5%
		Semi-finished textile	15%
		Yarns	15%
Yarns and Fabrics	5%		
Waste	13%	Biomethane	13%
		End-of-Waste materials	13%
		Waste management service (collection, transport)	50%
		Water and sewage	25%
Others	5%	Electrical wiring	33%
		Slicer blades	33%
		Transport tape	33%

To carry out the production lines outlined by Table 2, companies usually utilise a combination of different input materials. Indeed, on average, companies employ about three input materials. The number of inputs declared by the companies varies between 1 and 11. Nonetheless, 44% of respondents declared to refer on only a single input material. Considering the nature of these input materials, it should be noted that 70% of the companies declared to rely only on virgin raw materials. Conversely, 18% of companies utilises only non-virgin materials. The remaining cases employ a mix of

virgin and non-virgin raw materials (Figure 5), with the share of non-virgin input materials ranging from 17% to 67% of total requirements.

Figure 5. Percentage of non-virgin raw materials employed by the respondents.

Regarding to the production residues arising from the production lines delineated in Table 2, most of the companies (52%) declared to generate only a single outcome. However, the average number of production residues arising from the production activity of the respondent companies is close to 2, and it ranges from 1 to 5. Production residues can be treated either as waste or byproducts. In the first case, they are usually disposed of by incineration or landfill. However, with a specific authorisation, they can be further processed to obtain End-of-Waste materials. Byproducts, on the other hand, can be directly employed in other production lines, without requiring a permit for their transformation. 41% of the respondents declared to treat all their production residues as byproducts. Conversely, 38% of the companies reported that they disposed of all their production residues as waste. In the remaining cases, companies foresee different destinations for their production residues, treating them both as waste and byproduct. The share of production residues treated as byproducts in total production residues varies between 25% and 80% (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Percentage of production residues treated as byproduct by the respondent

In light of the above, it can be concluded that 72% of the sample implement circular practices, either for the procurement of inputs or for the treatment of residues. Nonetheless, only 47,5% of companies claimed to implement IS practices. Therefore, a relevant portion of respondents (24,5%) rely on circular practices that differ from IS (Figure 7). However, a resounding majority of the respondents, amounting to three-quarters of the total (76%), have expressed a firm conviction in the potential for the successful implementation of IS strategies within their respective sectors.

Figure 7. Sample distribution according to the implemented circular practice.

INDUSTRIAL SIMBYOSIS

In response to the question regarding the adoption of IS practices, 47% of the surveyed companies confirmed that they implement them. These companies will constitute the sub-sample of reference for the following paragraphs, and they will be referred to as “Symbiotic Companies”. The majority of Symbiotic Companies are qualified as small-medium size. Indeed, considering only those that provide sensitive data, 60% of them are classified as small enterprises according to their number of employees, whilst 75% are classified as medium size considering their turnover. Nevertheless, it should be noted that, despite large companies represent a minority of companies implementing IS practices, they account for 62% of the large companies listed in the entire sample (Figure 8). From a geographical perspective, most of the companies included within the sub-sample related to IS practices are located in Piedmont (85% of those providing sensitive data).

Figure 8. Symbiotic Companies size basing on the number of employees

From a sectoral perspective, Symbiotic Companies mainly operate within the textile (28%) and petrochemical (24%) manufacturing divisions. The sectoral distribution is fairly similar to that of the entire sample (Figure 9). As demonstrated in detail by Table 1, a wide variety of production processes are engaged within IS activities, and the list of companies’ final products encompasses different commodity products.

Figure 9. Symbiotic Companies by sectors.

Table 3. Symbiotic Companies' main products

Animal feed	3%
Flours	3%
Plant-based products	7%
Wine	3%
Outdoor solar shower	3%
Wooden artifacts	10%
Extruded PVC profiles	3%
Injection molded thermoplastic resins	3%
Plastic packaging	10%
Thermoplastic compounds and polymers	7%
Cotton terry items	3%
Fabrics	10%
Semi-finished textile	3%
Yarns	7%
Yarns and Fabrics	3%
End-of-Waste materials	3%
Waste management service (collection, transport)	3%
Water and sewage	3%
Slicer blades	3%
Transport tape	3%

The number of input materials involved within the symbiotic production lines ranges between 1 and 11. In this regard, 62% of companies declare to rely only on virgin raw materials as input whilst 14% relies only on non-virgin materials. Remaining production processes refer on a mix of input materials, and in

10% of cases the share of non-virgin raw materials is comprised between 50 and 67%. Conversely, the number of residual materials declared by the Symbiotic Companies range between 1 and 5. 62% of companies manage all their production residues as byproduct, whilst only 14% manages all of them as waste. In the remaining cases, residues are treated both as waste and byproduct, with 10% of Symbiotic Companies managing a share of their production residues comprises between 30 and 40% as byproducts. In light of the above it is possible to assume that most of the respondent Symbiotic Companies are configurable as Producers within the IS exchange, considering the Italian Chamber of Commerce nomenclature. Further analysis confirmed such result. In aggregated terms, the sub sample of Symbiotic Companies is composed by 70% Producers and 30% Utilisers. Particularly, there is a relevant number of companies that classify themselves as both producers and utilisers (27%) (Figure 10). These cases should be regarded to as particularly virtuous.

Figure 10. Symbiotic Companies breakdown according to their role within the symbiotic exchange.

The IS practice of 72% Utilisers involve only one input of the production process. Therefore, in most of the cases, a single input material is derived from a symbiotic exchange, i.e., it consists of a production residue originating from a different production line. The remaining cases rely on symbiotic sources at a higher level, with more than one input material resulting from symbiotic exchange.

Symbiotic inputs are mostly reprocessed through mechanical recycling practices, especially in terms of polymer extrusion or shredding and carding of textile fibres. Only one case is related to energy recovery, involving the use of fruit shells to feed the biomass boiler.

Most of the Utilisers source their symbiotic inputs within the national territory (42%). Nonetheless, symbiotic exchanges occurring within the boundaries of districts (21%) and provinces (26%) boundaries

remain relevant. In these cases, inputs are sourced from companies located close to the production site. In fact, the average estimated distance travelled to obtain inputs at the district and province level is 28,3 km, and ranging from 0 and 50 km. In these cases, inputs are derived from different productive chains, being either agrifood, textile, or petrochemical residues. Symbiotic exchanges with non-EU countries occur in two instances. Both cases are related to textile production residues, specifically, yarn and knitting offcuts, which are sourced between 2500 and 5000 km away. As regard to plastic and related residues, they are mainly sourced at the national level.

Table 4. Geographical Scale of Utilisers IS exchange, considering the residues typology

District	21%	Agrifood residues	25%
		Petrochemical residues	75%
Province	11%	Textile residues	40%
		Wood residues	20%
		Petrochemical residues	20%
		Metal residues	20%
Nation	42%	Petrochemical residues	88%
		Special waste	13%
Extra Ue	11%	Textile residues	100%

Among the Utilisers who disclosed information regarding their logistic organisation, 83% declare to utilising road transportation for the management of input transport. In contrast, for the residues sourced from non-EU countries, maritime transport is employed. The option of transport by rail is not considered by respondents. Furthermore, 83% of Utilisers declared that they employ external resources for the management of input transportation. Therefore, in most of the cases, the responsibility for organising and financing transportation lies with the producer of the residues. In a single instance, the logistics resources employed are entirely internal, whilst in another instance, the logistics is organised in collaboration with the sourcing company. This latter case pertains to the transportation of special waste, and therefore it could be assumed that it involves higher costs.

Regarding the respondent classified as Producers, as already mentioned, they represent the 70% of the subsample of Symbiotic Companies. In terms of amount of production residues supplied, usually each Producer exchange only a single residue (50%). Remaining Producers rely on symbiotic exchanges to manage 2 or 3 of their total manufacturing residues. The nature of symbiotic residues varies across initiatives and, particularly, in relation to the production line from which they originate.

Production residues vary across initiatives and, especially, in relation to the production lines from which they arise. However, some recurring patterns can be identified in relation to the intended use of residues,

considering their respective commodity categories. For instance, textile and petrochemical residues are mainly directed towards mechanical recycling processes, and mineral residues are typically employed as filler in construction materials. By contrast, organic residues are directed towards a variety of production processes. A share of them, including wood and plant-based materials, is directed towards energy recovery. Other typologies of organic residues, including sewage sludges, grape stems, and sawdust, are destined to the agriculture production in the form of soil amendments. Other residues deriving from wine production, such as lees and pomace, are instead furtherly distilled to obtain different products, i.e., *grappa*, yeast lysates, tartaric acid.

In relation to the logistic dimension, 34% of the symbiotic exchanges occur at the national scale involving an estimated distance ranging from 25 to 500km. The highest travelled distance is observed in three cases of textile residues, which are exchanged with companies respectively located between 400 and 500 km away, two in Italy, and one in another European country. However, in most of the cases the travelled distance of the residues is lower, and is extended at the province (52%), city (7%), or district (3%) scale. In particular, the majority of organic residues are exchanged within this range, travelling an average distance of 16 km. In only a single case an agrifood residue is exchanged on higher distance equal to 340 km, i.e., wine lees.

Table 5. Geographical Scale of Producers IS exchange, considering the residues typology

City	7%	Agrifood residues	50%
		Textile residues	50%
District	3%	Agrifood residues	100%
Province	52%	Agrifood residues	20%
		Textile residues	33%
		Construction residues	40%
		Other	7%
Nation	34%	Agrifood residues	30%
		Textile residues	20%
		Petrochemical residues	50%
EU-country	3%	Textile residues	100%

All the Producers respondents declared to organise the transport of their production residues by road. In 72% of cases logistic is managed with external resources, hence organised by the Utiliser partner

company. Regarding the resources to organise such exchanges, in 67% of cases they are external, meaning that the future utiliser of the residues is in charge to manage the transaction (i.e., organising the transport ecc.) In only 7 cases (22%) the organisation is internal. By contrast, in 24% cases, Producers declare to manage the logistics of the symbiotic exchange in partnership with the future Utilisers.

INCENTIVES AND BARRIERS TO IS PRACTICES

USE OF ECONOMIC AND FISCAL INCENTIVES

The questionnaire section on incentives and barriers to IS aimed to explore respondents' experiences with factors that facilitate or hinder the adoption of IS practices. The initial part sought to ascertain whether companies had direct experience with economic or fiscal incentives to implement IS or similar circular economy practices and, if so, what types of incentives they benefited from and how they were employed. However, only one company reported having benefited from economic incentives. This company was asked to specify the type of incentive received from a predefined list, which included: tax incentives, direct funding (non-repayable grants or specific subsidies), financing under favourable conditions, support for the purchase of capital goods and sustainable technologies, and facilitations for training and environmental certification. The respondent indicated that they had used tax incentives and support for the purchase of capital goods and sustainable technologies, specifically to finance the acquisition of machinery.

Subsequently, all respondents were asked whether they considered IS to be a viable production strategy in their sector. Table 6 presents the distribution of positive and negative responses, categorised by industrial sector. Among the 50 respondents, 37 (74%) viewed IS as feasible, while 13 (26%) considered it unviable. A sectoral breakdown of responses reveals notable differences in perception. The construction industry exhibited the highest percentage of positive responses (100%), followed by the agrifood sector (82%) and the petrochemical sector (80%). These results suggest that in these industries, companies may already be aware of or engaged in forms of IS, making them more inclined to view it as a realistic strategy. The textile sector, which had the highest number of respondents, showed a slightly lower—but still substantial—level of confidence in IS, with 72% of companies deeming it feasible. Given the well-documented challenges in textile waste management and resource reuse, this result may indicate a growing awareness of circular economy principles in the industry, even if barriers remain. In contrast, the waste management sector was the only industry where the majority of respondents (66%) believed that IS was not a viable option. This finding is particularly striking, considering that waste management plays a crucial role in IS by facilitating the exchange and valorisation of byproducts and secondary raw materials.

Given that IS is already implemented across all these industries, understanding the reasons behind these perceptions is particularly relevant. Notably, 75% of those who found IS unfeasible were small businesses, whereas this percentage dropped to 62% among those who considered it viable. This disparity suggests that smaller companies may perceive greater challenges in adopting IS, potentially due to limited financial resources, lack of technical expertise, or difficulties in establishing partnerships with other firms.

Larger companies, on the other hand, may have more capacity to invest in symbiotic practices, whether through dedicated sustainability initiatives or participation in industry-wide collaborations.

Table 6. Responses on the feasibility of IS by sector.

	Total	Textile	Agrifood	Constructions	Petrochemical	Waste	Others
No	13 (26%)	5 (28%)	2 (18%)	-	1 (20%)	4 (66%)	1 (50%)
Yes	37 (74%)	13 (72%)	9 (82%)	8 (100%)	4 (80%)	2 (33%)	1 (50%)
Totale	50	18	11	8	5	6	2

INCENTIVES FOR THE ADOPTION OF IS

Companies that considered the implementation of IS feasible were asked to evaluate, using a five-point scale (ranging from 1 = “not important at all” to 5 = “extremely important”), the factors that incentivise or hinder its adoption. To assess the key drivers of IS adoption, respondents were asked to what extent they believed specific factors could encourage companies to engage in IS. The options provided were based on critical incentives identified in the literature and included:

- **Economic convenience**, in terms of lower production costs (e.g., cost of non-virgin raw materials compared to traditional ones, avoided disposal costs, etc.)
- **Image gain** in the eyes of consumers
- **Commitment compliance** in accordance with sectoral framework agreements, ethical codes, or other voluntary agreements related to environmental protection
- **Strict environmental regulations**
- **Public incentives and/or grants** for ecological transition
- **Access to external (private) financing** linked to sustainability targets
- **Collaborative environment** (business networks, industrial districts, etc.)

The results, presented in Figure 11, illustrate the distribution of importance levels assigned to each incentive factor. Factors are ranked based on their perceived importance, measured as the sum of responses rating them as "extremely important" or "important". The most influential factor is economic convenience, with 70% of respondents considering it either "extremely important" or "important." A similar level of importance is attributed to the presence of a collaborative environment, indicating that companies value networks and partnerships as enablers of IS practices. Corporate image enhancement ranks third, highlighting the role of consumer perception as a motivating factor. Stringent environmental regulations follow closely in fourth place, with 61% of respondents recognising them as at least "important". The next two factors, compliance with sectoral agreements and public incentives, received comparable evaluations, with 53% of companies rating them as "moderately important" or higher. Finally, the least influential factor is access to external financing, which 36% of respondents rated as

having little to no importance in driving IS adoption. This suggests that financial barriers, while relevant, may not be the primary concern for companies compared to other structural or regulatory challenges.

Figure 11. Distribution of importance classes assigned to different incentive factors for IS, based on the total responses of survey participants.

Figure 12 illustrates the average scores assigned to different incentive factors for IS, divided by region (Piedmont and Lombardy). The scores are based on a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 represents "not important at all" and 5 signifies "extremely important". The comparative analysis between the two regions reveals several notable trends and differences. First of all, economic convenience stands out as the highest-rated factor in Piedmont, with an average score of 4.0, highlighting its critical role in driving IS adoption. In contrast, Lombardy assigns economic convenience the lowest average rating (2.2), suggesting that cost-related considerations are perceived as less influential in the decision-making process for IS adoption in this region.

Figure 12. Average score assigned to different incentive factors for IS, divided by region (Piedmont and bordering provinces of Lombardy). The score is based on a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 means "not important at all" and 5 means "extremely important".

The collaborative environment is another highly valued factor in both regions, with an identical score of 3.6. This underscores the importance of networking opportunities, partnerships, and industrial clusters in facilitating symbiotic practices. Interestingly, while Lombardy provinces tend to assign lower average scores to most factors, the collaborative environment emerges as the highest-rated incentive in the region, possibly reflecting the strong presence of well-established industrial districts and business networks. Corporate image enhancement is rated higher in Piedmont than in Lombardy, indicating that companies in the former region may place greater emphasis on sustainability-driven marketing and consumer perception as a motivation for adopting IS. Strict environmental regulations and compliance with sectoral agreements receive similarly high scores in both regions, suggesting that companies across territories recognise the significant role of regulatory frameworks and voluntary commitments in encouraging IS adoption. Finally, access to external financing emerges as the least influential factor in both regions, indicating that companies generally do not perceive external financial resources as a decisive enabler for IS. This finding aligns with previous insights, where operational, regulatory, and network-related factors were considered more crucial than direct financial incentives in driving IS adoption.

Figure 13. Average score assigned to different incentive factors for IS, divided by company size. The score is based on a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 means "not important at all" and 5 means "extremely important".

Figure 14 presents the average score assigned to different incentive factors for IS, categorised by sector. When analysing each sector individually, some notable differences emerge. The textile sector (the most represented in the survey) exhibits a relatively balanced evaluation across all factors, with average scores ranging between 3.0 and 3.5. This suggests that companies in this industry view multiple drivers as moderately important rather than relying on a single predominant factor. Agrifood sector displays more pronounced variations in factor importance. Corporate image enhancement stands out as a particularly relevant incentive, reinforcing the idea that businesses in this sector may prioritize sustainability-related marketing and consumer trust. Construction sector assigns higher-than-average ratings to all factors, indicating a broad recognition of the importance of multiple drivers in IS adoption. However, economic convenience is perceived as the most critical factor, reinforcing the notion that cost savings are a primary motivator for companies in this sector. The petrochemical sector exhibits a unique pattern, where strict environmental regulations are perceived as the most influential driver. This suggests that compliance with regulatory frameworks plays a central role in shaping IS practices within the sector, likely due to stringent environmental laws and industry-specific sustainability requirements. Conversely, public incentives receive lower-than-average ratings, indicating that government support is not seen as a decisive factor in driving symbiosis adoption. Overall, the findings suggest that economic convenience and collaborative environments are the most relevant enablers across sectors, while the impact of regulatory pressure, public incentives, and corporate image varies by industry. These insights emphasise the need for sector-specific policy interventions and support mechanisms to effectively promote IS adoption.

Figure 14. Average score assigned to different incentive factors for IS, divided by sector. The score is based on a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 means "not important at all" and 5 means "extremely important".

BARRIERS FOR THE ADOPTION OF IS

In analysing the factors that hinder the adoption of IS, this section presents the perceptions of respondents, who were asked to assess the extent to which the following barriers impact the feasibility of IS:

- Overly restrictive regulations on End-of-Waste (EoW) treatment parameters
- Lack of economic incentives, including tax benefits
- Absence of appropriate technologies
- High costs of technologies
- Excessive treatment costs for non-virgin raw materials
- Fluctuation and/or seasonality of secondary raw materials, leading to supply chain uncertainty
- Organizational challenges (e.g., lack of adequate skills)
- Logistical difficulties in managing residue flows and high logistical costs

The results, presented in Figure 15, illustrate the distribution of importance levels assigned to each barrier. The barriers are ranked based on their perceived significance, measured as the sum of responses rating

them as "extremely important" or "important". The most significant barrier identified is the high cost of technologies, with 64% of respondents rating it as at least "important". Notably, no respondent rated this factor as "not important at all," indicating a widespread perception that expensive technologies are a critical obstacle to IS implementation. Similarly, the absence of appropriate technologies ranks as the second most important barrier, emphasising how technological availability is a major constraint for companies aiming to transition toward more circular production systems. The third most cited barrier is the lack of economic incentives (e.g., tax benefits), further reinforcing the notion that financial support mechanisms play a crucial role in enabling or limiting IS adoption. This suggests that without adequate financial incentives, many companies struggle to justify investments in IS. Regulatory constraints also play a notable hindering role, with overly restrictive End-of-Waste (EoW) treatment regulations perceived as an "important" or "very important" barrier by 59% of respondents. In contrast, only 11% of respondents consider regulations a negligible issue, underscoring the challenges companies face in navigating legal frameworks for IS implementation. Economic considerations are further reflected in the perceived impact of excessive treatment costs for non-virgin raw materials, which 56% of respondents rate as at least "important." This highlights how the financial burden of processing secondary raw materials remains a significant disincentive for companies exploring symbiotic practices. At the other end of the spectrum, organisational and logistical challenges are ranked among the least significant barriers. Factors such as lack of adequate skills and difficulties in managing residue flows and associated logistics costs are considered important by only a minority of respondents. This suggests that while operational complexities exist, they are perceived as less critical compared to technological and financial constraints. Finally, supply chain uncertainty due to the fluctuation and/or seasonality of secondary raw materials is rated as the least significant barrier, with only 36% of respondents considering it important. This indicates that, while variability in material availability is a concern, it is not the most pressing issue for most companies. Overall, the findings highlight that technological and economic constraints are the most critical barriers to IS adoption, whereas organisational and logistical challenges are perceived as relatively less significant. This underscores the need for policy interventions that promote access to affordable technologies and financial incentives, while also addressing regulatory barriers to facilitate the transition to IS.

Figure 15. Distribution of importance classes assigned to different obstacles to IS, based on the total responses of survey participants.

Figure 16 illustrates the average scores assigned to various barriers to IS, segmented by region (Piedmont and Lombardy). The scores are based on a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 represents "not important at all" and 5 indicates "extremely important". A comparison between the two regions reveals notable differences and insights. First, the overall evaluations from Lombardy-based companies are consistently lower across all factors, suggesting that businesses in Lombardy, on average, attribute less importance to these barriers. Additionally, the trend observed in Piedmont closely aligns with the general pattern shown in Figure 16, as Piedmontese companies are more numerous and thus exert a greater influence on the overall trend. Examining the differences in more detail, the most significant disparities between the two regions emerge in relation to cost-related and economic factors. For instance, high technology costs are considered the most critical barrier in Piedmont, with an average score of 4, whereas this factor is perceived as less significant by respondents from Lombardy. Similarly, the lack of economic incentives and excessive treatment costs for non-virgin raw materials are not deemed particularly important in Lombardy. Finally, supply chain uncertainty shows the most substantial variation between the two regions. While it is the least important factor in both cases, its evaluation is significantly lower in Lombardy (2.2) compared to Piedmont (3.3).

Figure 16. Average score assigned to different obstacles to IS, divided by region (Piedmont and bordering provinces of Lombardy). The score is based on a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 means "not important at all" and 5 means "extremely important".

Figure 17 presents the differences in average scores assigned to various barriers to IS based on company size. The three most significant barriers overall—high technology costs, absence of appropriate technologies, and lack of economic incentives—do not exhibit substantial differences across company size categories. Similarly, excessive treatment costs are considered a fairly important factor across all three groups, without notable variation. However, some differences emerge in specific cases. For example, overly restrictive regulations are not perceived as particularly critical by medium-sized companies but receive higher importance ratings from both small and large enterprises. Another noteworthy aspect of these results is that even factors generally considered less significant barriers to IS adoption still receive relatively high scores among small businesses. This suggests that small companies face a broader range of obstacles that can hinder their adoption of IS practices. In particular, logistic and organisational difficulties are rated as major concerns for small enterprises, whereas they are assigned much lower importance by larger companies.

Figure 17. Average score assigned to different obstacles to IS, divided by company size. The score is based on a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 means "not important at all" and 5 means "extremely important".

Figure 18 presents the average scores assigned to various obstacles to IS, categorised by sector. The scoring scale ranges from 1 ("not important at all") to 5 ("extremely important"), allowing for a comparative analysis of perceived barriers across industries. Starting with the textile sector, the most represented in the dataset, no single barrier stands out significantly above the others. The scores follow the overall trend observed previously, with only slight variations between the highest and lowest-rated barriers, ranging between 3 and 3.5. A similar pattern can be observed in the agrifood sector, although with generally higher values compared to other industries. The scores range from 3.75 for the least critical barriers to 4.37 for the most significant ones, indicating that in this sector, all barriers are perceived as important obstacles to the implementation of IS. The construction sector follows the general trend but places greater emphasis on technological barriers, both in terms of costs and availability. Notably, overly restrictive regulations emerge as the most significant barrier for companies in this industry. The waste services sector exhibits the greatest variability in the evaluation of different barriers. While companies in this sector align with the general ranking of key obstacles, the most critical barriers receive particularly high scores, exceeding 4, while the least important ones, such as logistic difficulties and supply chain uncertainty, are rated as low as 2.5. This suggests that the perception of barriers in the waste services sector is more polarised compared to other industries.

Figure 18. Average score assigned to different obstacles to IS, divided by sector. The score is based on a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 means "not important at all" and 5 means "extremely important".

The outlined sectoral differences underscore the need for targeted policies and tailored support mechanisms to address industry-specific challenges and facilitate the adoption of IS practices across different sectors.

DISCUSSION ON THE SURVEY RESULTS

The results of the questionnaire demonstrate that IS practices are already implemented to some extent within the NODES. It should be stressed that the limited size of the sample, and the absence of some targeted GRIP sectors, i.e., the energy and chemical sectors, may affect the generalisability of the overall results. IS practices were undercover within 6, out of 8, of the GRIP production chains, demonstrating the high potential of such productive strategy. The fact that IS is implemented within a variety of production lines demonstrates that it represents a feasible strategy in most of the manufacturing sectors. This finding is further corroborated by companies' perceptions of the feasibility of IS implementation in their industry. Indeed, most of the companies have declared that IS could be implemented within their manufacturing segment. In this context, it is worth highlighting the striking result obtained by waste management companies, which showed the lowest level of confidence for the adoption of IS strategies within their activity. A possible reason for this low confidence in IS could be the fact that waste companies often manage post-consumer waste instead of byproducts or other industrial residues. As IS only refers to the recirculation of pre-consumer residues, companies dealing with municipal waste and similar are excluded from the adoption of IS practices. Nonetheless, waste companies are often multiutility businesses, the awareness on IS potentialities should be increased.

Although the results on companies' perceptions of the feasibility of IS in their sectors show that textile companies seem to be less confident, among the symbiotic companies surveyed, textile manufacturers seem to be particularly active. However, their symbiotic exchanges are mostly related to textile scraps being mechanically recycled to produce new textile. This practice may be in contrast with the strictest IS definition (Chertow, 2000), according to which IS involves production residues that are reutilised in different production chains from which they originate and for different purposes with respect to the original ones. The exchange of production residue is therefore not sufficient to fall within the IS framework. The relevant number of textile companies may give rise to questions regarding the level of understanding that local companies have of IS and its associated benefits. Nonetheless, despite the academic literature provides several examples of IS related to textile, on which textile residues are subsequently employed in different manufacturing segments, i.e., as insulant materials or filler in concrete, the high value of textile and its high demand, validates the reintegration of such scrap materials within similar production lines. IS cases within the textile industry should be therefore further investigated, in order to understand which practices can be effectively considered as symbiotic, and which fall into the broader Circular Economy framework.

A further salient finding of the investigation pertains to the geographical break-even point of symbiotic residues. Indeed, it can be posited that textile and petrochemical residues can be profitably exchanged over longer distances, i.e. on a national and international scale. Agrifood residues, conversely, are exchanged at the local level, especially district and provincial. This can be attributed to both the intrinsic value of the residue commodity and its perishability. In fact, in light of the results on the perceived incentives to adopt IS, economic convenience resulted the most important factor. Therefore, the economic convenience of the symbiotic exchange defines which is the maximum geographical distance that can be travelled.

Declared transport modalities almost always refer to road transport and never to rail transport. This raises serious questions about the environmental impact of symbiotic exchanges. Especially over long distances, rail transport should be prioritised as it has the lowest carbon footprint. The reason why rail transport is not considered by companies may be that it is difficult to organise logistics by train, especially in terms of timing. Trains have a greater carrying capacity than lorries, but they can only leave the starting point when they are fully loaded. Organising logistics by rail therefore means that a company has to adapt to the needs and schedules of other companies.

Among the most quoted incentives for IS implementation, the collaborative environment results one of the main relevant factors. Beside large companies, this dimension is considered particularly important by small size enterprises. Small size enterprises indeed have limited financial resources and, consequently, lower level of technical expertise. Therefore, the possibility to rely on a highly collaborative environment, where knowledge and resources are shared, could increase the likelihood of implementing symbiotic practices. Environmental legislation seems to be an incentive for the adoption of IS, especially for large-size enterprises. In this context, it is possible that legislation is perceived as an incentive rather than as a barrier, because large companies have more financial capacity to adapt to changes in legislation and therefore to invest in symbiotic practices. From a sectoral perspective, it is worth noting that environmental legislation is considered a key driver particularly by the petrochemical industry. The petrochemical sector represents both a highly profitable sector and a highly polluting manufacturing segment. Consequently, petrochemical companies can have the economic means to address their pollution if they have policy benchmarks as a guide.

Considering the perceived barriers for the implementation of IS, technologies related factors resulted the most relevant dimensions. Technological costs, transformation costs and technological viability were indeed found as the most significant barriers, regardless to the company size. Large enterprises in particular cite the absence of appropriate technological platforms as a barrier to IS adoption. This testify that even companies with a consistent financial capacity struggle to find suitable technology.

Furthermore, it is worth noting that stringent legislation acts as a barrier to IS implementation for small enterprises.

Overall, the findings highlight that economic and technological dimensions are perceived as key drivers of IS. Economic convenience represents indeed the key driver for the adoption of IS. By contrast, technological availability and cost are considered the most limiting factors toward the implementation of IS. Therefore, legislation should promote access to affordable technologies and financial incentives, considering also the different capabilities of companies according to their size. Furthermore, the disparity in perceptions between different industries highlights the need of framework agreement and specific sectoral legislation.

CONCLUSION AND FURTHER RESEARCH

The present study provided useful information on local IS practices within the GRIP production chains. It demonstrated that IS is already implemented within the NODES territory to a certain extent. However, IS practices described by the respondents widely differ from the innovative transformations considered in the GRIP project. Indeed, production residues are typically reintegrated in subsequent production chains through mechanical recycling processes. This may represent a relevant leverage to promote and spread GRIP platforms within the territorial productive fabric, especially considering the high interest toward IS demonstrated by local companies.

Given the small size of the analysed sample, results generalisability may be undermined. Further research should be conducted to evaluate the sample representativeness of the overall regional productive fabric. Nonetheless, the survey results have highlighted significant structural differences between sectors and between companies' sizes, which should be highly considered and furtherly deepened. Additional further research should also investigate the barriers that hinders the adoption of rail transportation.